

D2.1: GEMINI framework version 1 & MLLs evaluation plan

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About this deliverable	This deliverable presents the first version of the GEMINI evaluation framework focussing on the evaluation of new and shared mobility services. In addition, based on the outlined evaluation framework, detailed evaluation plans for the 8 Mobility Living Labs (MLLs) are presented. Lastly, a chapter is dedicated to identifying and addressing potential threats when implementing smart mobility services as part of an effort to enhance their resilience and effectiveness by design.
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Full meaning
ACAP	Portuguese Automobile Association
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMP	Porto Metropolitan Area
ANPR	Automatic Number Plate Recognition
a.o.	amongst others
API	Application Programming Interface
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
B2B	Business-to-business
B2C	Business-to-customer
BM	Business Model
CIM	Common Impact Model
CPS	Cyber-Physical System
CPS	Communauté d'agglomération Paris-Saclay

Acronym	Full meaning
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DTU	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet
EC	European Commission
e.g.	Exempli gratia (meaning “for example”)
EU	European Union
EPAPs	Land Planning Public Authority of Paris-Saclay
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group
HMA	Helsinki Metropolitan Area
IoT	Internet-of-Things
FCP	Futebol Clube do Porto
f.e.	For example
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEMINI	Greening European Mobility through cascading innovation INItiatives
GPS	Global Positioning System
GTFS	General Transit Feed Specification
HSL	Helsinki Regional Transport Authority
km	Kilometre
l	Litre
LUR	Ljubljana Urban Region
MaaS	Mobility as a Commons
MaaS	Mobility as a Service
MER	Measure Evaluation Report Sheet
MiD	Mobilität in Deutschland
MLL	Mobility Living Lab
MOL	City of Ljubljana
MVG	Münchner Verkehrsgesellschaft
MVV	Münchner Verkehrs- und Tarifverbund
NMS	New and Shared Mobility Services
NO _x	Nitrogen Oxides

Acronym	Full meaning
OSM	OpenStreetMap
PM	Particulate Matter
PD	Porto Digital
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
PT	Public Transport
SIN	Smart Innovation Norway
SUMP	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan
t.b.c.	to be confirmed
t.b.d.	to be determined
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
TOTEC	Total Ownership Tracking Economics Calculator
VIF	Virtual Vehicle Research
XIPE	Cross Impact Performance Emissions

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the first version of the GEMINI evaluation framework, focussing on the evaluation of the impact and implementation process of new and shared mobility services (NMS). It aims to develop an efficient, comprehensive, and consistent evaluation approach of the implemented NMS within and across the 8 GEMINI Mobility Living Labs (MLLs) that can be used as a future reference when evaluating the introduction of NMS in an urban or peri-urban context. Specific evaluation tools are presented, such as the GEMINI evaluating sheets and an open-source tool to estimate the reduction in air pollution and CO₂ emissions attributed to the introduction of NMS.

Furthermore, based on the outlined evaluation framework, this deliverable presents the detailed evaluation plans of the 8 GEMINI MLLs. For each MLL, the urban context and specific objectives are presented, as well as the specific MLL impact and process evaluation approach, detailing the selected indicators, the data collection methodology, the different stakeholders involved and phases of the implementation process.

Lastly, a chapter of this deliverable is dedicated to the identification of possible threats when implementing smart mobility services, aiming to ensure fair, safe, and accessible technological development when introducing NMS.

The objective of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive and consistent evaluation approach when implementing NMS and to present a detailed plan of the evaluation activities that will be undertaken during the GEMINI project. Over the course of the project the evaluation framework will be updated and finetuned based on further validation and optimisation of the approach during the project. The final version of the GEMINI evaluation framework (D2.3) will be delivered in month 41 of the GEMINI project (October 2026).

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 GEMINI in brief

The Greening European Mobility through cascading innovation INitiatives (GEMINI) project is a 3.5-year Innovation Action project funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme running over the timeframe 2023–2026. It designs, implements and evaluates new and shared mobility services (NMS; e.g. car-sharing, bike-sharing, ride-hailing) in 8 mission cities¹. These cities are the 4 GEMINI lead Mobility Living Labs (MLLs): Amsterdam, Copenhagen, Munich and Turin, and the 4 GEMINI twinning MLLs: Helsinki, Ljubljana, Paris and Porto (see FIGURE 1). The twinning MLLs will begin operations later than the lead MLLs, enabling them to replicate positive experiences of the lead MLLs.

FIGURE 1: The 8 GEMINI Mobility Living Labs

The aim of this project is to accelerate progress towards climate neutrality by strengthening a modal shift through demonstration and application of NMS, active transport modes, micromobility and their integration with public transport in Mobility as a Service (MaaS) services. The project puts a specific emphasis on developing sustainable business models for NMS and integrating social and behavioural strategies for NMS adoption.

The GEMINI MLLs will demonstrate their contribution to an increased share of NMS in the modal distribution and integration with public transport, and to a reduction of congestion, CO₂ emissions, air pollution and road risk, whilst fostering accessibility and social inclusion.

1.2 Purpose of this document

This deliverable D2.1 presents a first version of the GEMINI evaluation framework. Starting from the overall CIVITAS 2020 process and impact evaluation framework, this document delivers a comprehensive framework for the evaluation of new and shared mobility services that are being implemented in an urban or peri-urban context. Here a strong focus is put on the evaluation of NMS business models based on collaboration platforms or public-private partnerships (PPPs).

This framework describes the methodology for evaluating the impact and implementation process of NMS, including specifications of possible indicators, to enable a consistent evaluation approach across the GEMINI MLLs. To strengthen this, specific GEMINI evaluation tools were developed by different GEMINI partners (SIN, DTU and Cenex). Following this evaluation methodology, the GEMINI evaluation plans of each of the 8 GEMINI MLLs have been

¹ 100 cities from European Union member states, along with 12 cities from associated countries, have been chosen to participate in the EU Mission for 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030, also known as the Cities Mission. The designated cities aim to become climate neutral by 2030 while pioneering innovative approaches and engaging citizens and stakeholders. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/climate-neutral-and-smart-cities_en

developed. These plans are presented, detailing the evaluation approach in light of the specific context and objectives of each MLL.

In addition, as part of Task 2.3 “Privacy by design, Resilience & Safety”, GEMINI partner Virtual Vehicle Research (VIF), produced a specific chapter of this deliverable based on input delivered by the GEMINI Task 2.3 partners. The chapter provides examples and mitigation actions for data misuse, cyber attacks and data protection when designing and implementing smart mobility services, to ensure fair, safe, and accessible technological development of new mobility services.

Over the course of the project the evaluation framework will be validated, updated and finetuned based on the monitoring and evaluation experiences in the GEMINI MLLs gained during the project. The final GEMINI evaluation framework (D2.3) will be delivered in M41, in the final months of the GEMINI project, and made available to other cities, stakeholders, partners, to allow them to implement and assess NMS more efficiently and evaluate them in a consistent way.

1.3 Document structure

This deliverable presents the first version of the GEMINI evaluation framework.

Chapter 2 presents the GEMINI evaluation methodology on how to successfully monitor, evaluate and understand the impact and implementation process of NMS. Here different indicator types will be introduced to help structure the evaluation approach. In addition, specific GEMINI evaluation tools will be presented, such as an open-source user-friendly tool to help cities calculate the air pollution and CO₂ reduction attributed to shared mobility.

In Chapter 3, an analysis of cases of data misuse, cyber attacks and data protection in relation to smart (mobility) services is presented, to help identify threats related to privacy and technological development when designing and implementing smart mobility services.

Chapter 4 introduces the structure and approach of the MLL evaluation plans, which are presented, for each of the 8 MLLs, in chapters 5 to 12.

Provisional conclusions are presented in chapter 13.

2 THE GEMINI EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the first version of the GEMINI evaluation framework, to ensure an efficient, comprehensive, and consistent evaluation methodology of the implemented NMS within and across the MLLs.

GEMINI builds on the evaluation framework outlined in the **CIVITAS 2020 process and impact evaluation framework** (Engels, 2021). The CIVITAS initiative was launched in 2002 by the European Commission (EC) as part of its efforts to promote sustainable urban mobility across Europe. Over the years, the CIVITAS projects gained extensive experience regarding evidence-based evaluation and monitoring of sustainable mobility measures, which was thoroughly recorded in the CIVITAS 2020 process and impact evaluation framework. It offers fundamental components for establishing a robust, transparent, and consistent evaluation methodology, with comprehensive guidelines, practical recommendations, reporting structures, and illustrative examples drawn from various CIVITAS initiatives.

The GEMINI evaluation framework will expand on the CIVITAS 2020 process and impact evaluation building blocks, by placing a strong focus on the evaluation of NMS and business models scenarios based on collaboration platforms or public-private partnerships (PPPs). The GEMINI framework will present:

- specific **impact indicators** for the evaluation of the impact of NMS, in line with the GEMINI objectives
- **additional indicators** to understand the functioning of the NMS and to gain insight into the overall impact
- **tools** to measure and understand the mechanisms underlying the adoption and use of NMS
- an **open-source user-friendly tool** to help cities calculate the reduction in air pollution and CO₂ emissions, by introducing NMS
- an analysis and mitigation actions to help identify **threats related to privacy and technological development**, such as data misuse, cyber attacks and data protection, when implementing NMS

2.2 CIVITAS impact and process evaluation framework

Impact evaluation: The evaluation of the effects of the implemented measures, using a set of selected impact indicators

Process evaluation: Analysis of how the measure was implemented:

- ⇒ Identify barriers and drivers of the implementation process
- ⇒ Understand the role and effect of supporting activities to ease the implementation and to strengthen the impact

FIGURE 2: Two complementary activities for a complete and consistent CIVITAS evaluation approach

Within the CIVITAS context, the primary objective of the CIVITAS 2020 evaluation is to comprehend the process and impact of mobility measures that are being implemented, discerning what proves effective and what doesn't, and comprehending the underlying reasons. Such an understanding, encompassing both successes and failures, is pivotal for other cities and for establishing an evidence-based European knowledge repository.

The question to address is: "What is the impact and what are the important aspects of the implementation process of (sustainable) mobility measures that are being implemented in an urban or peri-urban area?" The evaluation work therefore includes two complementary activities, as summarised in FIGURE 2:

1. **Impact evaluation:** the monitoring and evaluation of the effects or impact of the implemented measures in relation to the objectives of the measure, using a set of selected indicators.
2. **Process evaluation:** an analysis of how the measure was implemented. It identifies the barriers and drivers of the implementation process, and the important elements or activities that facilitated the implementation of that measure and increased the envisaged impact.

The integration and interpretation of the results from both the impact and process evaluation provide the necessary insights and understanding of the effectiveness and efficiency of the measures in the context of the urban area. The two complementary analyses – impact and process evaluation – help us to understand the reasons behind the observed changes.

What is a measure in the CIVITAS context?

A measure refers to a mobility-related action implemented by a city, government or other stakeholder, to respond to the mobility challenges that a city or local area is facing. E.g., new infrastructure, new mobility services, activities aimed at changing citizen behaviour. Often an integrated package of measures is implemented to tackle these challenges.

2.3 GEMINI objectives and MLL focus

GEMINI develops and tests sustainable business models for NMS in 8 MLLs, engaging local communities in the co-creation, development and adoption of these NMS and aims to demonstrate the positive impact on social inclusion and accessibility, while reducing congestion, greenhouse gas emissions, air pollution and road risk. These main GEMINI objectives are summarised in TABLE 1.

TABLE 1: GEMINI main objectives

No.	GEMINI objectives
1	25% increased share of NMS in the modal split
2	20% reduction of congestion
3	20% reduction of traffic related air pollution
4	20% reduction of traffic related CO ₂ emissions
5	reduction of road risk
6	improved accessibility public transport (PT)
7	improved social inclusion

Each of the 8 MLLs will contribute to the main GEMINI objectives, as well as additional local objectives. Each MLL has its unique focus and therefore not all the main GEMINI objectives are pursued with the same intensity. For example, the MLL Amsterdam does not only aim to improve social inclusion by making NMS accessible to a larger group of people beyond high-income young professionals in its city, but also aims to create more liveable cities thanks to freeing up parking space. The MLL Porto aims to increase the share of NMS in the modal split, while also focusing on increasing the sense of security at the Porto stadium during games, when large crowds take over the city.

Reduced road risk (objective 5) is an important aspect for GEMINI since with the implementation of NMS, new transport modes with new characteristics are introduced in the existing mixture of transport modes. To ensure safe mobility, the road safety aspects will be monitored in each of the MLLs in a qualitative way, based on feedback from the users, records of collisions and injuries by the NMS providers, a qualitative analysis of the infrastructure at NMS stations and from road safety statistics collected by the city, based on police and hospital data. Although most of the MLLs lack specific road safety measures, all measures will be developed with a safety focus, ensuring that the road safety situation remains at least as safe as it was before implementing the NMS.

In recent years we have seen a swift rise in the adoption and popularity of NMS. Multiple studies have explored the impact of shared mobility on aspects related to urban mobility, such as car ownership (Zhou, 2020), modal shift (Guo, 2021) or the environment. Many research contributions have found that NMS mainly seem to substitute sustainable modes such as active mobility or public transport instead of complementing them, while some studies highlight the potential environmental benefits of NMS once mainstreamed (Tikoudis, 2021).

There are many open questions when trying to understand the effect or potential of NMS. For example: Does car-sharing have an effect on the ownership of private car vehicles? Do shared (e-)bikes or e-scooters trips replace car trips or PT or walking trips? Does car-sharing reduce the number of vehicle kilometres driven? Are NMS only used by the high-income population?

The GEMINI evaluation work aims to provide answers to these questions and increase the understanding of the effects of NMS in an urban and peri-urban area:

- by monitoring the impact of the implementation of NMS on selected impact indicators such as modal share, CO₂ emissions, car ownership, PT accessibility, etc.,
- by creating a better comprehension of the mobility behaviour by a modelling exercise,
- by trying to understand the different aspects of the implementation process,
- and by bringing these results together in light of the specific (peri-)urban context.

2.4 GEMINI impact evaluation

2.4.1 Introduction

The impact evaluation assesses the changes in the mobility system due to the implementation of new and shared mobility services in each MLL. It monitors the changes and tries to understand them, assessing also whether the objectives or expected impacts in each MLL are achieved.

For this purpose, a set of indicators has been selected and the value of these indicators is measured before and after the implementation of the NMS. It is to note that many factors influence the value of these indicators and also the city characteristics and functioning of the mobility situation need to be considered when interpreting these values. To help this process, 3

indicator types are identified in the GEMINI evaluation framework, as explained in the next section.

2.4.2 Indicator types

FIGURE 3: Three types of GEMINI indicators

In each MLL, 3 types of indicators are identified (see FIGURE 3):

1. **City context indicators:** these indicators at city level give an overall understanding of the mobility situation in the city. These include indicators such as modal split, car ownership, the quality of the cycling network, etc.
2. **Impact indicators:** these indicators at the level of the MLL area monitor the objectives or expected impact of the implemented NMS.
3. **Additional indicators:** these indicators at the level of the MLL area give additional information to understand the functioning of the NMS and gain insight into the overall impact of the implemented measure.

2.4.2.1 City context indicators

The city context indicators characterise the mobility situation of the city where the measure is being implemented. Data on these indicators are collected at the start of the project, before the implementation of the NMS, and represent the baseline situation of the urban area in which the measure of the MLL is being implemented. It is important to note that these indicators are collected at city level, and not at the level of the MLL area. Having a characterisation of the city context helps to give a correct understanding of the impact of the implemented measures in the MLLs and why certain measures are being easily adopted, especially in light of the introduction of new mobility services.

Some of the MLLs introduce a measure in the peri-urban area (e.g. in the Copenhagen MLL, an NMS is introduced in the commune Rudersdal, about 20 km from Copenhagen city). Collecting context indicators at the level of the city Copenhagen is still important since it provides insights in the mobility options and habits, that the inhabitants of the region are already acquainted with when commuting or travelling to the city.

TABLE 2 lists the most relevant city context indicators to have a good characterisation of the mobility situation of the city, keeping in mind that new and shared mobility services will be introduced in the MLLs. They include the modal split, indicators on road safety, a

characterisation of the current availability of shared mobility options and whether a Mobility as a Service (MaaS) platform is available, including details on its format (is f.e. combined ticketing possible?), car ownership, traffic congestion levels, and the quality of the cycling network.

Ideally, data is collected for all these indicators by each MLL. However, this is not always possible due to a lack of data availability. Then, a qualitative description (e.g. for quality of the cycling network) can suffice.

TABLE 2: GEMINI city context indicators

City context indicators		
#	Indicator	Definition
1	Modal split	Percentage of trips in the city by inhabitants and/or commuters done walking, cycling, by micromobility, by moped, by car, by public transport or by other. ²
2	Number of road crashes	Number of road crashes caused by any means of transport.
3	Number of seriously injured	Number of seriously injured people caused by any means of transport. A person seriously injured is a person who was hospitalised for a period of more than 24 hours as a result of a road crash.
4	Number of road deaths	Number of persons fatally injured caused by any means of transport. A person fatally injured is a person killed immediately or dying within 30 days as a result of a road crash.
5	Density of shared mobility services	The shared mobility options available in the city. Ideally a map is given with the different stations and, if possible, the number of shared vehicles available.
6	Availability of shared mobility services	For each available shared mobility service (car-sharing, bike-sharing, shared e-scooters): number of vehicles, number of users, number of journeys/week.
7	Availability MaaS	Availability of a MaaS app (yes/no) and details on the available functions (e.g. routeplanner, payment of combined/single tickets, ...).
8	Car ownership at city/regional level	Number of owned cars (including company cars) per 1 000 inhabitants >18 years.
		Percentage of households that have no car.
9	Congestion levels	Delays in road traffic during peak hours versus free flow traffic.
10	Quality of the cycling network	Quality score of the cycling infrastructure.
		User satisfaction of the cycling network.

2.4.2.2 Impact indicators

The impact indicators are key indicators to understand the impact of the implemented measure in the MLLs, in different impact categories, such as environment (green areas, reduced greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution), safety and security, society (neighbourhood cooperation, social inclusion, accessibility), etc.

The stepwise approach on how these indicators are selected per MLL is visualised in FIGURE 4.

² If shared mobility is documented as a mode option, it's encouraged to include this, but usually this data is not collected yet.

FIGURE 4: Schematic of the applied approach in selecting the impact indicators.

First, for each MLL, the objectives are identified, such as improving the accessibility of public transport, or reducing greenhouse emissions due to a modal shift from car use to cycling. If possible, these objectives are quantified. E.g., thanks to the introduction of the NMS, the MLL aims to reduce car induced CO₂ emissions by 10%.

Secondly, based on the list of identified objectives, both quantitative and qualitative indicators are selected that can best monitor this expected impact. Different data collection methods are possible. For example, sometimes the data is already collected at local or city level by the mobility department or shared mobility or public transport operators. On the other hand, sometimes a survey needs to be organised or information can be collected from interviews with relevant stakeholders or users. When selecting the appropriate impact indicators, not only the relevance of the indicator but also the accuracy and availability of data are considered.

As a starting point for selecting the relevant impact indicators considering the GEMINI objectives, the indicators list of the CIVITAS 2020 process and impact evaluation framework (Engels, 2021) was consulted. In addition, inspiration was found in the recently published paper "measuring new mobility" (ITF, 2023) and in the evaluation plans and evaluation reports of previous CIVITAS projects³. Note that the Coordination and Support Action project MUSE⁴ is developing a tool to help select relevant indicators after specifying the expected impact of the measures that are being implemented. The CIVITAS MUSE online evaluation tool should become available by the end of 2024.

³ <https://civitas.eu/projects>

⁴ <https://civitas.eu/coordination/muse>

TABLE 3: GEMINI impact indicators in the MLL area

Impact indicators				
#	Objective/Expected impact	Possible indicator	Possible sources	Frequency
1	Reduction of congestion	Average vehicle speed (peak/off-peak)	Floating car data, Bluetooth	start & end project
		Time travelled from areas A-B	ANPR camera data	
2	Increase share of NMS in the modal split	Modal share NMS in modal split	Survey	
3	Reduction of road risk	Number of collisions	Police data, hospital data, own registration	
		Number of persons fatally, seriously or lightly injured		
4	Improved accessibility PT	Number of multimodal hubs	Countings	
		Inhabitants in the area around PT stops or NMS point giving access to PT stops	Countings – GIS maps processed	
5	Improved awareness of NMS	Awareness of NMS	Survey	
6	Improved acceptance of NMS	Acceptance of NMS	Survey	
7	Improved social inclusion	Mobility level of societal groups whose ability to access activities is influenced by specific factors such as language, immigration status, ethnicity, religious beliefs, age, reduced mobility, gender, sexual orientation, etc.	Interviews, survey	
8	Reduction of traffic related air pollution	NO _x , PM emissions	Calculated based on reduced car-vkm from traffic simulations	end project
			XIPE model	
9	Reduction of traffic related CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂ emissions	Calculated based on reduced car-vkm from traffic simulations	
			XIPE model	

TABLE 3 lists possible impact indicators to monitor the main GEMINI objectives, as well as the awareness and acceptance of the NMS. For some objectives, multiple indicators are listed. Different sources to collect these indicators are given. In most cases, the aim is to collect this data at the start and end of the project.

TABLE 3 serves as a basis for the selection of the final impact indicators and the data collection method, for each MLL. Moreover, additional impact indicators are selected to monitor the specific objectives in the different MLLs. This selection is done in close collaboration with the GEMINI partner coordinating the MLL and local evaluation managers of the MLLs, and it is a

balance between the feasibility of data collection and the importance of monitoring the key objectives of each MLL.

2.4.2.3 Additional indicators

The third set of indicators are the additional indicators. These indicators help to understand specific aspects of the functioning of the implemented measure. They facilitate a clearer understanding of the implementation process and the overall impact of the implemented measure.

A specific focus is given to the performance of the NMS and the business model (BM) characteristics since the GEMINI project aspires to develop and test financially viable NMS business model scenarios with the ambition to increase the share of new mobility services in each MLLs' modal distribution.

NMS performance

TABLE 4 lists possible indicators to monitor the performance of the NMS. They characterise the overall functioning and usage of the NMS. This information is important to get a clear understanding and interpretation of the impact of the measures in the MLLs. Several of these indicators are also used as input data for the Cross Impact Performance Emissions (XIPE) model (see Section 2.6.4). This list is non-exhaustive and serves as a starting point for the MLLs. It includes indicators such as the number of available shared vehicles, the number of registered users for the different shared services, number of trips per week and average trip distance for each shared mode and satisfaction with the service. This data is collected from the shared mobility provider, ideally during different phases of the project to see its evolution.

TABLE 4: GEMINI additional indicators to characterise the NMS performance in the MLL area

Additional indicators => NMS performance				
#	Indicator	Method/Source	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Number of vehicles per shared mode	Data from NMS provider	(intermediate &) end project	MLL area
2	Number of users per shared mode			
3	Number of trips/week per shared mode			
4	Average trip distance per shared mode			
5	Number of trips/week per shared mode in combination with PT			
6	NMS user satisfaction			NMS users

BM performance

TABLE 5 lists possible indicators to evaluate the business model. It includes typical indicators such as investment and operational costs, whether the MLL has benefitted from subsidies, revenues and the number of generated jobs. This data is collected from the partner implementing the measure and its main stakeholders, such as the NMS provider. Most of the data is collected at the end of the project, after successful implementation of the measure.

TABLE 5: GEMINI additional indicators to characterise the BM performance in the MLL area

Additional indicators => BM performance				
#	Indicator	Method/Source	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Investment costs	Data from MLL coordinator and/or NMS provider	end project	MLL area
2	Operational costs			
3	Subsidisation			
4	Revenues			
5	No. jobs generated			
6	Costs per user and/or per trip and/or per km-driven			
7	Total Cost of Ownership	TOTEC model	start/end project	

Other operational indicators

Other than the indicators characterising the business model and the functioning of the NMS, specific additional indicators are selected in each MLL in relation to their specific focus and implemented measure. These are elaborated in the individual MLL evaluation plans (Chapters 5 to 12).

2.5 GEMINI process evaluation

Complementary to the impact evaluation, an analysis is done of the implementation process of the GEMINI measures, the so-called process evaluation.

During the process evaluation, the **barriers and drivers** of the implementation process are identified and a clear understanding is gained of the role (or lack of) of the **supporting activities** in the success or failure of the implementation process. Examples of supporting activities include stakeholder engagement, a communication campaign, co-creation workshops, etc. In the process evaluation, the important elements or activities are identified that facilitated the implementation of that measure and increased the envisaged impact.

The integration and interpretation of the results from both the impact and process evaluation provide the necessary insights and understanding of the effectiveness and efficiency of the measures in the context of the urban area.

In the GEMINI project, the process evaluation activities will be based on interviews with the main stakeholders involved in the implementation process, complemented by a qualitative appraisal of the effect of the supporting activities.

Additional process evaluation activities to monitor the implementation process include a.o. focus group meetings, stakeholder surveys and a learning history session, but these are beyond the scope of the GEMINI project. For more information, additional process evaluation data gathering activities are described in chapter 4.2 of the CIVITAS 2020 process and impact evaluation framework (Engels, 2021).

2.6 GEMINI tools

This section describes the different tools developed in GEMINI under WP2, to support the evaluation. Some of these tools are still in their development phase and will be finalised over the course of the GEMINI project. In this section, the following tools are described:

1. **GEMINI evaluation sheets:** a template for a step-by-step approach to a mature evaluation plan,
2. The **Common Impact Model:** a methodology and tools to facilitate acceptance of new technical solutions,
3. **Modelling individual mobility behaviour:** a modelling framework to analyse how different transportation modes interact and influence overall accessibility, to study the impact or potential of new mobility infrastructure, such as mobility hubs or the addition of NMS,
4. **The XIPE model for shared mobility:** an easy-to-use tool to calculate the saved CO₂ emissions and air pollutant emissions thanks to the introduction of shared mobility in a city,
5. **The TOTEC model for shared mobility:** a tool to calculate the Total Cost of Ownership for various types of vehicles, to be able to compare the costs of private car ownership to the costs of using different car sharing models.

2.6.1 GEMINI evaluation sheets

The GEMINI evaluation sheet is an easy-to-use template that allows the MLLs to set-up their evaluation activities, identify the objectives, outputs and select the appropriate indicators. It was developed at the start of the GEMINI project. Inspiration for these evaluation sheets was found in the Measure Evaluation Report Sheet (MER) template of the CIVITAS 2020 process and impact evaluation framework (Engels, 2021).

GEMINI evaluation sheets were used intensively by the MLL partners to build up the evaluation work. The different MLLs used this template to identify the objectives, the test area and (sub-) target groups, to give a description of the implemented measure and list the outputs, to identify the main actors involved in the measure and eventually select the appropriate indicators to monitor the impact of the implemented measure.

FIGURE 5 visualizes the GEMINI evaluation sheets, the template itself is provided in Appendix A: GEMINI evaluation sheets.

The GEMINI evaluation sheets consist of the following main subsections:

- Objectives
- Measure description (incl. a specification of the output and supporting activities)
- Test area and target groups
- Stakeholders
- City context indicators
- Impact indicators
- Additional indicators
- Planned implementation phases

Based on these templates and detailed discussion with the main stakeholders of the MLLs, fully fledged evaluation plans were developed for each MLL, as documented in Chapters 5 to 12.

FIGURE 5: Screenshot of the GEMINI evaluation sheet template

2.6.2 The Common Impact Model

The Common Impact Model (CIM) is a methodology to facilitate community acceptance of new technical solutions (Petrovich et al., 2021). The GEMINI tailored CIM considers user and community acceptance in the process of designing and implementing a new mobility service through three steps. In the GEMINI CIM, these steps are labelled as 1) Inspiration, 2) Ideation, and 3) Implementation. For each step, specific tools for exploring and measuring user acceptance are provided.

FIGURE 6: Common Impact Model for NMS with Toolbox as described in GEMINI D2.2

The GEMINI Common Impact Model is used as a theoretical framework basis for the structure of deliverable D2.2 GEMINI user acceptance sheets, delivered by GEMINI partner Smart Innovation Norway (SIN). Since the GEMINI CIM considers user and community acceptance in the process of designing and implementing new mobility solutions, it provides **support in understanding why behaviour is changing, and which elements are the contributing factors to this behavioural change**, which will enable developers to test and tailor solutions to the highest level of user acceptance.

To test acceptance of NMS, multiple tools must be used in different phases of the development process depending on the solution in question. The GEMINI CIM model suggests tools for the **Inspiration phase** such as a *Guide for questions to explore the context of a NMS*, a *Stakeholder*

mapping to truly understand user needs and tailor services to the different stakeholders, and a *Template for NMS Dashboard* that helps to visualise the results from the inspiration phase and is a valuable input for the co-design workshops in the next phase. In the **Ideation phase** tools for *co-design workshops* are recommended to identify opportunities and generate ideas from a user-centric approach, before testing and refining solutions with continuous feedback loops. Last, in the **Implementation phase** both a *Survey template* and *Interview guide* for evaluating user acceptance is suggested to evaluate final user acceptance. The acceptance of NMS will be higher if we can ensure user-centric, behavioural tailored solutions, which is enabled by the recommended tools suggested in the CIM model. Comprehensive details on these tools are published in GEMINI deliverable D2.2.

The CIM model suggests processes and evaluation tools to gather data points that can be followed up both during and after the implementation of NMS. Holistic understanding and coherent evaluation of progress throughout the different phases of the implementation will not only ensure best possible processes and measures towards user acceptance, but also ensure systematic data monitoring for the final evaluation.

The CIM model suggests processes and evaluation tools that can gather data points that can be followed up both during and after the implementation of NMS. Holistic understanding and coherent evaluation of progress throughout the different phases of the implementation will not only ensure best possible processes and measures towards user acceptance, but also ensure systematic data monitoring for the final evaluation.

2.6.3 Modelling individual mobility behaviour

2.6.3.1 Introduction

Evaluation of mobility initiatives like GEMINI typically uses aggregated data, aiming at a macroscopic analysis to capture the impact of an intervention such as the introduction of new shared mobility services. Analysing data in compartments, the macroscopic approach can overlook nuanced aspects, including temporal changes over daily, weekly and seasonal timescales, as well as heterogeneities in behaviours and motivations driving usage of new services (e.g. cost, convenience, or environmental concerns). These motivations differ notably among age groups, income levels, and geographic areas. Moreover, macro-level evaluation may miss complex usage patterns, like frequency and preferences for specific shared mobility modes, and the usage of multiple transport modes in combination.

To address these limitations, GEMINI partner Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU) proposes a computational framework that leverages detailed, largely passively collected data across transport modes to examine the impact of shared mobility services on user mobility patterns. This approach integrates granular data to provide a comprehensive understanding of how interventions influence individual behaviour and broader mobility trends, thereby informing the development of effective mobility solutions.

The modelling framework is based on open-source libraries, that ensure a broad application to all GEMINI MLLs. The modelling framework constructs a multilayer network for a given area using OpenStreetMap (OSM) and General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) data (see Section 2.6.3.2), and it computes measures like accessibility (see Section 2.6.3.4). It is crafted to integrate mobility data in standard formats, enabling robust data analysis and easy scalability to apply to other cities.

This setup allows each MLL to independently apply the modelling framework using their own data, ensuring that they can adapt the standardized methods to their specific local contexts while safeguarding data privacy and security.

2.6.3.2 General modelling framework: data sources

Individual-level mobility data analysis involves integrating various mobility data sources (see TABLE 6) with information on amenity distribution, transportation networks, and both built and natural environments (see TABLE 7), within a unified framework .

Most European cities can easily access the listed data sources, making it broadly applicable for different living labs.

In the context of GEMINI, the collection and analysis of mobility data before, during, and after allows us to frame the changes in travel patterns within urban infrastructures, which can drive understanding of the impact of new shared mobility modes on the entire urban transport network.

Mobility data sources

TABLE 6 provides a list of different sources that can be used to study individual mobility behaviour by different transport modes.

TABLE 6: Mobility data sources

Data Source	Key data	Applications in the context of shared mobility analysis
Smart-card data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Individual trip information (location/time of origin/destination, fare,...) -User information (age-group, area of residence,...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -PT demand for different groups -Factors underlying PT routing strategies
Smartphone data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -GPS data -Accelerometer data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Mobility demand for different groups through different transport modes -Assessing the impact of external factors on mobility (e.g., weather, events)
MaaS data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -GPS data -Transport model -Booking information -User information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Analysing preferences for shared versus private transport -Studying the effectiveness of multi-modal transport solutions
Private cars data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -GPS tracking data -User information (area of residence, age-group) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Understanding private car usage patterns -Mapping typical routes and travel times -Identifying areas with high private traffic -Analysing peak travel times and congestion patterns -Adjusting shared mobility operations to traffic conditions
Data from shared mobility providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -User registration and trip data -Vehicle usage statistics -Location and duration of use -Service demand patterns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Evaluating the impact of shared mobility on traditional transport -Optimizing the location and number of vehicles

Data Source	Key data	Applications in the context of shared mobility analysis
Detailed survey data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Attitudinal data towards different transport modes -Perceived service quality -Personal and household demographics -Detailed travel diaries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Understanding user satisfaction and barriers to use -Capturing detailed user behaviour and preferences not available from other data sources

Urban data sources

Additional data, capturing transport infrastructure and urban features are key to model urban transportation systems. In TABLE 7 a list of sources is provided that can be collected for a wide range of cities worldwide.

TABLE 7: Urban data sources

Data Source	Key data	Applications
GTFS (General Transit Feed Specification) https://gtfs.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Timetables -Route information -Stop locations -Fare information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Analysing public transportation efficiency -Modelling PT routing strategies
OpenStreetMap Data https://www.openstreetmap.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Road network -Points of interest -Building footprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identifying strategic locations for shared mobility hubs -Enhancing navigation and routing for shared mobility services -Urban infrastructure impact analysis
Land Usage Data https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Land Cover -Land Usage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Planning and zoning for shared mobility parking and stations -Monitoring the environmental impact of shared mobility

2.6.3.3 General modelling framework: modelling multimodal mobility

Multimodal transportation is modelled using the established modelling framework of multilayer transport networks. Our approach incorporates two innovative aspects: (i) the use of real individual-level data for modelling mobility on the network; and (ii) the integration of shared mobility into the modelling framework.

Mathematical modelling framework of multilayer networks

A multilayer transport network is a model that represents various modes of transportation as individual layers within a larger network structure. Each layer corresponds to a different transportation mode, such as buses, trains, pedestrian paths, or bike lanes. The nodes in each layer represent stops, stations, or junctions specific to that mode, and links between nodes represent direct routes or paths available within that mode, with the weight associated to each link representing the travel time of the route.

Formally, a multilayer network in transportation can be described by a set of layers $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_m\}$, where each layer G_α is a graph $G_\alpha = (N_\alpha, L_\alpha)$. Here, N_α denotes the set of nodes and L_α denotes the set of links in layer L_α . Connectivity within a layer represents paths or routes specific to a

transportation mode, while inter-layer connections represent possible transitions between different modes, such as transferring from a train to a bus or switching from a bus to a bike for further travel.

Building multilayer transport networks with OSM and GTFS

The two main data sources we used to construct a multilayer network for urban transportation analysis are OpenStreetMap (OSM) and the General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS), see TABLE 7.

Public transport data, obtained from GTFS, forms one layer, while data for walking, cycling and driving can be retrieved from OpenStreetMap, collectively forming the other layers (FIGURE 7). The public transport can be further divided into multiple sublayers, with each sublayer representing an individual transit line. This granular division enables accurate simulation of multimodal trips, effectively capturing the complexities and interdependencies within the transportation infrastructure.

In our multimodal network, nodes represent hexagons of 100 meters in size, and weighted links capture connections between areas via different transport modes via combinations of public transit, cycling, walking, or driving. Links are weighted based on the travel time. This simplification standardizes the network's scale and reduces computational time analysis.

FIGURE 7: Multilayer structure of the transportation network of Rudersdal in the Greater Copenhagen area

Each layer represents a distinct transport mode: yellow for public transport, red for driving routes, green for walking paths and orange for cycling structure. Inter-layer connectivity is established through spatial proximity, see text for further details.

Adding dynamics: demand and trips

The transportation network described above captures structural aspects of urban transportation. Mobility data (see TABLE 6) enables us to incorporate in the analysis actual behaviour, including travel demand and routing strategies.

On the one hand, we can use the real-world data to incorporate current demand across the various layers over time, including differences in daily or weekly usage patterns, as well as variances among socio-demographics groups.

On the other hand, individual-level data (see TABLE 6) capturing actual trips can be used to accurately model routing on the network, moving beyond the traditional assumption of shortest-path routing. By incorporating actual trajectories into the model, or by developing models that reflect real-world choices of routes and transportation modes, we can better simulate how people navigate from origin to destination, including which transport mode and which route they choose.

Integrating shared mobility

Shared mobility within this infrastructure can be embedded into two ways to integrate and enhance the multilayer transportation network.

First/Last-mile connectivity: While the layers for driving, walking, and cycling in a multilayer transportation network provide extensive coverage, the public transport layer lacks the same capillarity. The addition of shared mobility can close this gap. This integration effectively allows for modelling multimodal paths that were previously "forbidden" or inaccessible within the original network setup. For instance, shared mobility unlocks paths that start by bus and terminate by bike, subject to the availability of shared vehicles.

Alternative transportation options: For individuals without access to private vehicles, bicycles, or e-scooters, shared mobility can be modelled as an alternative layer within the network. This layer provides routes and connections that mimic the availability and usage patterns of shared mobility services, offering users practical alternatives for their entire trips.

2.6.3.4 General modelling framework: application to GEMINI MLLs

Evaluation of the MLLs and understanding of behavioural change

The modelling framework outlined above provides a more detailed way to evaluate the GEMINI MLLs, allowing us to assess their impact and effectiveness beyond just observing general changes in travel behaviour through broad evaluations. Specifically, the modelling framework enables to investigate several key aspects:

- **Changes in accessibility to amenities:** Through the multilayer analysis, we can directly examine how interventions impact accessibility to various local amenities, such as schools, healthcare facilities, shopping centres, and recreational areas.
- **Changes in accessibility for different demographic groups:** It enables to compute changes in accessibility for different segments of the population. Subject to data availability, it enables a particular focus on vulnerable groups who may face greater mobility challenges.
- **Modelling of routing strategies:** Individual-level data enables to analyse how people navigate through complex transport networks—public transport, shared mobility, walking, and driving. The decisions involved in traveling from origin to destination include selecting transport modes and routes. Influenced by cost, time, personal preferences, and awareness of the system, individual-level information enables more accurate modelling of routing strategies.

- **Detailed analysis of modal shifts:** We can focus on precisely understanding what shared mobility is used for, both as a standalone option and in conjunction with public transport. This involves identifying the specific types of trips—whether they are linked to daily commutes, specific events, or particular times of day during peak congestion—that are being shifted from private cars to these more sustainable modes. This detailed insight can help us optimize interventions to target the most effective opportunities for encouraging a shift towards shared mobility and public transport.

Co-design of the MLL

The insights derived through the proposed framework can directly inform the co-design of the MLLs and future shared mobility solutions. Key applications include:

- **Optimal placement of shared mobility infrastructure:** Analysing detailed routing strategies and modal shifts allows us to identify strategic locations for mobility hubs and other infrastructure elements that maximize accessibility and convenience for the widest range of users, including vulnerable groups.
- **Fare system design:** Insights into how different demographic groups respond to shared mobility can guide the development of equitable and attractive pricing strategies that encourage broader adoption of shared mobility and public transport options.
- **Development of new public transport options:** Understanding the specific travel needs and preferences highlighted by the modal shift analysis helps in designing new public transport services that effectively integrate with shared mobility to offer efficient travel experiences.

2.6.3.5 Case study for Copenhagen

The Copenhagen MLL aims to enhance shared mobility in Copenhagen by extending services to Rudersdal. It will introduce several multimodal mobility hubs, integrating shared e-scooters, cars, and bikes from 3 shared mobility providers. These hubs aim to serve as both physical and digital points for changing transport modes, optimizing local transport patterns and promoting public transport use.

Collected data

In the context of the MLL, our analysis relies on data such as:

- **Smart-card data:** Utilizing the Rejsekort travel card, which is widely used across Denmark by both regular public transport users and visitors.
- **Private car data:** This includes demand data for private cars and anonymized individual trips for approximately 15% of cars in Denmark, gathered through GPS sensors installed on vehicles. The beginning and end of each trip are obscured to maintain anonymity.
- **Data from shared mobility providers:** Kinto, TIER, and Green Mobility contribute shared mobility trip data, which helps to analyse demand and usage patterns throughout the development of the MLL.
- **Detailed Survey data:** Surveys conducted by the National Transport Survey Denmark assess attitudes towards public transport and shared mobility, with hundreds of respondents from Rudersdal included.

The analysis relies on data gathered before, during, and after the implementation of the MLL, focusing on trips departing from or arriving in Rudersdal. Data gathered in the year before the deployment of the MLL enables to quantify the effectiveness of the intervention against baseline travel behaviour.

Analysis of urban accessibility

Building upon the previously mentioned data sources and the modelling framework of multilayer networks, we can study accessibility via different transport modes in Rudersdal. This framework allows us to analyse how different transportation modes interact and influence overall accessibility. In particular, we can evaluate how the newly introduced shared mobility options in Rudersdal enhance access to different areas and amenities for different groups.

FIGURE 8A illustrates accessibility in Rudersdal as the fraction of destinations reachable within a given travel time from a specific origin point, averaged across origins. Looking at the fraction of areas reachable within 15 minutes from each origin (FIGURE 8B), we observe that public transport in Rudersdal is not capillary. Instead, the bike layer offers high access to a large number of destinations. Given the peri-urban nature of the area under study, the combination of bus and bike offers a level of accessibility comparable to the private car layer.

To capture spatial differences in accessibility between the bike and bus networks, we employ a comparative analysis. FIGURE 9 illustrates the inefficiencies of each individual layer in providing access to destinations within Rudersdal. Specifically, we calculate the average ratio of travel times to reach a destination using only one layer (either bike or bus) compared to utilizing all available transportation options within the area.

Our analysis reveals key spatial patterns. In the lower region of Rudersdal, where the presence of public transport is more prevalent, the bike layer demonstrates inefficiencies, indicating that relying solely on cycling may lead to longer travel times compared to utilizing the comprehensive transportation network. Conversely, in the upper region of Rudersdal, where bike infrastructure is more abundant, particularly near amenities such as parks, the bus layer exhibits inefficiencies. This suggests that in areas with robust bike infrastructure, cycling alone may offer more efficient travel options compared to relying solely on public transport.

FIGURE 8: Accessibility of the Rudersdal multilayer network
 Panel A: Cumulative average accessibility over time for various transport modes.
 Panel B: Spatial accessibility of each hexagon for different transport modes.
 Subplots display the percentage of reachable destinations within 15 minutes, computed via shortest path analysis.

FIGURE 9: Comparison of time inefficiency: bike vs public transport.
 Time inefficiency of each hexagon using only a bike (left) or public transport (right) to reach possible destinations within the Rudersdal region.

Co-design of multimodal mobility hubs.

A primary goal of the Copenhagen living lab is to encourage a shift from private car use to public transport combined with shared mobility. Our analysis helps in the co-design of mobility hubs by developing a strategic framework for their placement. Our framework will enable to analyse private car usage data to determine demand and propose locations for mobility hubs that offer practical routes using public transport and shared mobility, appealing to a broad spectrum of car users.

Initially, our strategy focuses on providing alternatives that match the travel times of private car use. As the MLL evolves and we collect more detailed data on the demographics and trip purposes of shared mobility users, we will be able to refine our approach. This will enable us to make more precise recommendations aimed at converting the highest possible number of private car users to more sustainable mode of transportation.

2.6.4 The Cross Impact Performance Emissions (XIPE) model

The Cross Impact Performance Emissions (XIPE) model for shared mobility is developed by Cenex as part of the GEMINI project. It is a free, open access and easy to use tool for cities, policy makers and shared mobility providers to estimate the emissions saved by the introduction of shared mobility in a city. The model is a continuation of the work done by the TU Delft during the EIT C-KIC funded SuSMo project⁵.

The model can be used both before and after introduction of the shared mobility services: After introduction by helping cities to understand the impact on emissions and check if their goals are reached and if their policies have the expected effects; before introduction by making it possible to model different scenarios and adjust accordingly during the planning and implementation phase.

2.6.4.1 XIPE Model structure

The model is easy to use while being as flexible as possible. This is achieved by prefilling almost all variables by data collected from literature or previous work. For a basic model run, users only really need the current modal split, the average trip distance for the traditional modes, the average age and diesel percentage of the city car fleet, the number of shared vehicles per shared services and the number of inhabitants.

Flexibility is created by making every prefilled variable changeable by the user and by making it possible to input case specific data when available. Furthermore, all calculations are presented to the users making it possible to check them for themselves (white box). This results in a model that is both easy to use and valid in its outputs. However, outputs are still based on averages and assumptions and are no replacements of real world measurements.

The XIPE model for shared mobility is an Excel tool and consists of a dashboard, a variable sheet, five calculation sheets and two constants sheets. All cells except for the user input cells are protected. Users will be able to see the calculations in the cells but won't be able to change them.

⁵ <https://www.cenex.co.uk/projects-case-studies/susmo/>

2.6.4.2 XIPE Model Dashboard

The dashboard sheet shows the basic inputs needed to run the model (FIGURE 10) and the estimated emission reduction as outputs (FIGURE 11).

FIGURE 10: XIPE basic model inputs

The general model **inputs** are city and country specific variables like the number of inhabitants, the age of the car fleet, the city modal split and average trip distance. For the shared mobility services the number of shared mobility vehicles are listed including the share of electric vehicles. The model considers car, bike, moped and e-scooter sharing. Additionally an 'other' service' can be added (see Section 2.6.4.3), which is fully customisable for a different sharing service.

FIGURE 11: XIPE model outputs

The model outputs present for each of the shared services the estimated emission reduction for:

- CO₂ emissions, split by the Tank-to-Wheel and Well-to-Tank emissions caused by the fuel used in the vehicles
- Additional life-cycle CO₂ emissions, caused by the life-cycle components besides the fuel component above:
 - Vehicle component, manufacturing to end of use
 - Infrastructure component, construction and use
 - Operational component, redistribution of modes by other means than regular use
- Air pollution emissions from the exhaust of the vehicles:
 - NO_x
 - Particulate Matter (PM)

The model **outputs** listed in FIGURE 11 are presented separately for each shared service to increase transparency, making it possible to see where shared mobility impacts emissions. Finally, the emissions are also presented per day, per year, and per year per 1 000 inhabitants.

2.6.4.3 XIPE Variables

Most variables of the model are prefilled, only really requiring the input data on the dashboard to be provided by the user. Users can also replace these prefilled values in the variable sheet with their own values. Prefilled values are listed in the light grey cells where users can fill their own values in the light green cells, values that are not used are greyed out. Variables are divided into general variables, variables for traditional modes and variables for new shared modes, see FIGURE 12 and FIGURE 13.

General Variables:					
Average CO2 emission intensity for electricity generation (gCO2/kWh)	133.00				
Well-to-Tank emissions fraction of Well-to-Wheel-emissions ICE cars (%)	20%				
Traditional Modes:					
	Private Car (per VKT)	Public Transport (per passenger km)		Active modes (per VKT)	
	Road	Rail	Walking	Cycling	
CO2 emission factors for traditional modes Tank-to-Wheel (g/l/km)	227.50	83.00			
Average NOx emissions (mg/km)	131.00	30.67			
Average PM emissions (mg/km)	11.00	0.67			
Average efficiency of public transport Rail (kWh/pkm)		0.09			
Emission factor for life-cycle phases excluding use phase (gCO2/km)	55.00	20.00	13.00		12.00

FIGURE 12: XIPE model general and traditional mode specific variables

New Shared Modes:	ICE		Hybrid		Active		E-Car		E-Bike		E-Vs	
	User Input	Default	User Input	Default	User Input	Default	User Input	Default	User Input	Default	User Input	Default
Average number of trips per day	5.00				5.00	4.00		5.00		4.00		
Average Tank-to-Wheel CO2 emissions (g/km)	133.30			37.00								
Average NOx emissions (mg/km)	60.00			60.00								
Average PM emissions (mg/km)	4.50			4.50								
Average efficiency of a shared EV (kWh/km)							0.17				0.51	
Emission factor for life-cycle phases excluding use phase (gCO2/km)	55.00		11.00		55.00		81.00				71.00	
Previously used traditional mode	Car	48%		48%	48%	48%	0%	48%		0%	48%	0%
	Public transport	0%	18%	0%	18%	0%	18%	0%	18%	0%	18%	0%
	Road		10%		10%		10%		10%		10%	
	Rail		8%		8%		8%		8%		8%	
	Active Modes	0%	34%	0%	34%	0%	34%	0%	34%	0%	34%	0%
	Walking		33%		33%		33%		33%		33%	
Cycling		1%		1%		1%		1%		1%		
Total	0%	100%	0%	100%	0%	100%	0%	100%	0%	100%	0%	
Average Trip distance of shared mode	Car	8.00		8.00		2.50		8.00		3.75		3.75
	Public transport		8.00		8.00		2.50		8.00		3.75	
	Road		8.00		8.00		2.50		8.00		3.75	
	Rail		8.00		8.00		2.50		8.00		3.75	
	Active Modes		1.75		1.75		1.75		1.75		1.75	
	Walking		1.00		1.00		1.00		1.00		1.00	
Cycling		2.50		2.50		2.50		2.50		2.50		

FIGURE 13: XIPE model new shared mode variables

The variable sheet makes it possible to input specific data available to a city for each different mode, both traditional and new shared modes. This is also where the ‘other’ service can be set up if needed.

2.6.4.4 XIPE Calculations

Each shared service has its own calculation sheet and follows the same calculations using different inputs. Cells are colour coded by function, see FIGURE 14, to increase readability. CO₂, air quality and life-cycle emissions have separate sections in the sheet.

	Car	E-Car	
1			
2	-	10.00	User Inputs
3	5.00	5.00	Calc. Trips
4	-	50.0	Calc. Distance
5	80%	48%	Calc. CO2
6	5%	8%	
7	5%	8%	
8	5%	33%	
9	5%	3%	
10	-	24.00	
11	-	4.00	
12	-	4.00	
13	-	16.50	
14	-	1.50	
15	8.00	8.00	
16	8.00	8.00	
17	8.00	8.00	
18	1.00	1.00	
19	2.50	2.50	
20	-	192.00	
21	-	32.00	
22	-	32.00	
23	-	16.50	
24	-	3.75	
25	252.00	252.00	
26	0.20	0.20	
27	176.68	176.68	
28	63.00	63.00	
29	0.09	0.09	

Dashboard | Variables | **Car Sharing** | Bike Sharing | Moped Sharing | E-Scooter Sharing | Other Sharing | Country Specific Constants | Air Pollution

FIGURE 14: XIPE model calculation sheet

2.6.4.5 XIPE Constant Sheets

The two constants sheets, which can be seen on the bottom of FIGURE 14, are country specific constants and air pollution constants. There are two country specific constants:

- The emission intensity of electricity production for each European country:
 - Used to prefill the average CO₂ emission intensity for electricity generation
- The average CO₂ emissions per km from new passenger cars produced in a certain year for each European country:
 - Used to prefill the CO₂ emission factors for traditional modes Tank-to-Wheel

In the air pollution constant sheet the European limits for NO_x and PM emissions are listed for each manufacturing year, which is used to calculate the NO_x and PM emissions saved.

2.6.5 The Total Ownership Tracking Economics Calculator (TOTEC) model

The Total Ownership Tracking Economics Calculator (TOTEC) model for shared mobility calculates the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) for various types of vehicles and compares car ownership and car sharing models. The tool provides a better understanding of the economic impacts of different vehicle usage strategies, including private ownership, commercial shared cars (such as Cambio, GreenMobility), and community shared cars (Mobility as a Commons - MaaC).

The TOTEC tool is divided in three sections:

1. Privately owned cars
2. Shared cars (both commercial and MaaC)
3. Results

2.6.5.1 Privately owned cars

The tool calculates the TCO by considering both fixed and variable costs:

- Fixed Costs include annual expenses such as parking permits, vehicle insurance, and registration fees, amongst others.
- Variable Costs are usage-based and include the cost of fuel (with options for either diesel or gasoline), fuel efficiency (km/l), and tank capacity. The tool accommodates different usage patterns, allowing calculations based on daily, weekly, monthly, or yearly driving habits.

FIGURE 15 shows the TOTEC start screen for privately owned cars, where the user can input custom values for fixed costs, usage costs, timespan of usage and type of fuel. As can be seen in the figure, besides the OWNED CAR tab there are two more tabs the user can interact with: shared commercial cars and shared community cars (SHARED CAR) and the RESULTS tab.

2.6.5.2 Shared commercial cars and shared community cars

For vehicles operated under commercial sharing schemes, the TCO includes different pricing models like subscription fees or other payment structures typical of commercial sharing services.

For MaaC, the tool considers community-specific payment methods, which might include membership fees or per-use payments, providing a clear financial picture of participating in a community car share versus other forms of vehicle access.

Users can input specific data related to their car usage and cost factors, and the tool will dynamically calculate the TCO. This functionality supports a wide range of scenarios.

2.6.5.3 Results

In the results section, a series of graphs are shown explaining, the percentage of the different costs across time and how they evolve. As such, a main chart with a timeline – with forecasting calculations – will indicate the comparison between shared community cars, shared commercial cars and privately owned cars. The user can see the TCO based on the initial parameters selected and can make adjustments to these parameters within the results page to observe how the results change over time.

FIGURE 15: TOTE model dashboard.

3 IDENTIFYING THREATS WHEN IMPLEMENTING SMART MOBILITY SERVICES

3.1 Introduction

The development of new smart services⁶, particularly new and shared mobility services, focuses on digital technologies and components. This creates requirements for users regarding the protection of their data. The use of new technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), further intensifies this focus.

Within this context, this chapter, produced by GEMINI partner VIF, identifies requirements for effective data protection, based on a case study approach. In this case study approach, relevant cases from the recent past were collected, described in a structured manner and examined. The cases were selected according to the following criteria:

- They pertain to the field of mobility and mobility services, specifically focusing on smart mobility systems.
- They involve issues related to privacy, data security, and product security.

To ensure the right to privacy and the associated task of ensuring data security for a long time, the case study approach should help learn from others' mistakes. Studying these specific cases should raise awareness of recognizing potential risks, creating threat scenarios for smart services, or in the context of GEMINI, implementing services within the MLLs in WP4, and implementing appropriate countermeasures at an early stage.

Furthermore, an introduction to the EU framework of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and the guidelines provided for it, is outlined in Section 3.7.

3.2 Case study approach

The first theoretical section provides a brief overview of terms in the context of smart mobility⁷. It also examines what information is worth protecting from the perspective of individuals and companies and who is responsible for providing, managing, processing, and protecting this data. In addition, a list of threats to smart services is attached and described.

One first outcome of this theoretical review of smart mobility is a subdivision of threats into main categories with different characteristics (see the final result of categories of threats in Section 3.8.2). A second result are 27 cases describing real incidents involving smart services, such as data protection breaches, data misuse, cyber attacks, or flawed product design. These cases were discussed with the GEMINI partners participating in the task, and mapped according to the main- and subcategories of threats. This mapping between cases and threats is a third outcome of this case study approach.

This categorisation of threats and the mapping to the cases is intended to help find concrete examples of fictitious threats and use these examples to promote awareness of data protection and data security and to identify weaknesses in the implementation of smart mobility at an early stage and take countermeasures timely.

⁶ Smart services are intended to increase customer benefits through the digitalization of physical processes and thus create new value chains for companies (plusserver GmbH, 2024).

⁷ Smart mobility is the application of smart services in the context of mobility.

Additionally, the European Commission has defined several sets of rules regarding the protection of privacy, data protection and the processing of this data, which are appended to the theoretical section.

3.3 Definitions of Terms

In today's digital world, digital technologies and networked services are an integral part of our daily lives.

To ensure privacy and data security, corresponding threat scenarios should be formulated at an early stage in addition to the functional requirements for these services and appropriate countermeasures should be implemented in the operation of these services.

3.3.1 Mobility as a Service (MaaS)

The concept of MaaS is a user-centric, intelligent mobility management and distribution system in which an integrator brings together the offerings of multiple mobility service providers (e.g. bike- and scooter-sharing, carpooling, car-sharing, public transport, shuttle services), and provides end users with access to these offerings via a digital interface so that they can plan and pay for mobility seamlessly (ARISTEK Systems, 2023).

Mobility as a Service (MaaS) is an extension of the concept of smart services and Cyber-Physical Systems⁸ (CPS) in the field of mobility. It refers to the integration of various transportation services into a central platform. On this platform, users can combine different mobility offerings and optimize them according to their needs, as well as book and pay for them seamlessly.

Mobility as a Service is characterized by the following features:

- MaaS integrates **various transportation services** such as public transport, bike-rental, car-sharing, ride-hailing services, and others into a single platform.
- Based on centrally available timetables, real-time availability and prices, as well as current traffic conditions, MaaS enables users to **plan a multimodal journey** in which different modes of transport can be optimally combined.
- Utilizing **digital technologies** for bookings, payments, and other interactions to be automated, thus improving the user-friendliness and efficiency of mobility services.
- Based on user preferences and behaviour, MaaS can offer **personalized recommendations** for the best route or preferred transport service.
- A one-stop-shop single platform can significantly simplify the **billing and payment process** for the user. This can be further enhanced by offers such as subscriptions or pay-per-use models.

By combining smart services with MaaS, traffic efficiency can be enhanced, environmental impacts minimized, and individual mobility improved.

3.3.2 Privacy

The right to privacy refers to the individual right of a person to protect their personal information, their actions, and their relationships with others from unauthorized interference or disclosure. It is a fundamental human right and is recognized in various international human rights documents as well as in the legal systems of many countries (Privacy International, 2024).

⁸ Cyber-physical systems are systems in which information and software technology components are connected to mechanical components, with data transfer and exchange as well as monitoring and control taking place in real time via an infrastructure such as the Internet. (Gabler Wirtschaftslexikon, 2021)

The right to privacy encompasses various aspects:

- The protection of personal data refers to the fact that personal information, such as health data, financial information, or personal correspondence, may not be collected, stored or passed on without the consent of the person concerned.
- The protection of privacy refers to the protection against unauthorized intrusion into one's own living space, for example that searches of one's own living space may not take place without an appropriate legal basis.
- The protection of one's own communications refers to ensuring that communications with others are treated confidentially. This includes letters, emails, telephone calls and other forms of communication.
- The protection from surveillance refers to protecting individuals from unwarranted surveillance by government agencies or private organizations.

Data protection laws and regulations govern how personal information must be collected, used and protected, or assist organizations in these tasks.

3.3.3 Data Security

Data security helps to protect sensitive information and intellectual property, prevent financial loss and maintain customer confidence, while complying with various legal regulations.

This includes all measures and strategies required to protect information from unauthorized access, loss, theft or damage. This includes implementing technologies, policies and procedures to ensure that data is protected during its storage, transmission and processing. The security of data can be threatened by cyber attacks, unauthorized access, data breaches and other risks.

For their own interest, businesses and individuals are also encouraged to handle data consciously and implement best practices for data security.

3.3.4 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) is used to simulate human intelligence, supported by computers or other technological systems. Techniques such as machine learning, neural networks, natural language processing, expert systems and others are used for this purpose, and appropriately trained models are used to attempt to process tasks and solve problems that would normally be performed by humans or would require human intelligence.

Training and optimizing AI models typically require large amounts of data.

3.4 Sensitive information

3.4.1 Personal data

If personal data is collected unnecessarily or without consent, or if this data is inadequately protected against unauthorized access, there is a risk that individuals' digital identities could be stolen and misused using this personal data.

Examples of information that should be protected include:

- personal information:
 - of the individual
 - of their contacts
- credentials
- location and track
- personal content in multimedia files (photos, videos, audio)

- Information on human needs and feelings and belonging:
 - personal emotional state,
 - traffic or transport behaviour,
 - health,
 - personal (political) opinions
 - public safety,
 - culture,
 - entertainment,
 - education,
 - entrepreneurship.
 - ethnic origin,
 - political opinions,
 - religious or philosophical beliefs,
 - trade union membership,
 - genetic data,
 - biometric data for the unique identification of a natural person (fingerprint, face...),
 - sexual life or sexual orientation,
 - ...
- Usage data:
 - sensors,
 - cameras,
 - actuators⁹,
 - smart meter,
 - activities in web platforms,
 - activities with mobile devices
 - ...
- Financial status:
 - bank account data,
 - credit card number,
 - ...

3.4.2 Company data

Companies aim to ensure their economic success in the future. For this reason, data that they do not wish to disclose to other companies or individuals must be protected:

- Trade secrets:
 - research and development,
 - sales and marketing strategies,
 - intellectual property,
 - profit and loss information,
 - business partners,
 - tax information
- Financial data:
 - financial transactions,
 - cash withdrawal receipts,
 - credit or debit card statements and receipts,

⁹ An IoT device is made up of a physical object, a controller, sensors, actuators and network. An actuator moves or controls the mechanism of the system (Actuators in IoT – GeeksforGeeks, 2024).

- rejected checks,
- pre-confirmed credit applications,
- investments,
- stocks,
- real estate transactions
- Physical documents:
 - printed documents,
 - boarding passes (contact details are stored in the barcodes),
 - shipping labels (address labels on packages may contain confidential information),
 - advertising materials (personal data is often included in correspondence),
 - photos (even if identities cannot easily be stolen with a photo, a false identity can be created with one),
 - post-it notes (many people write passwords on them),
 - payslips (these may contain details such as health insurance or account numbers)
- Digital documents & storage media:
 - office documents (email attachments),
 - old hard drives (data stored on them can be recovered with specialized software),
 - USB drives

3.5 Responsibilities

In the operation of smart services, different roles interact with various tasks. This includes the operators of the services, as well as the customers and users of these services.

Accordingly, in the context of privacy and data security, there are tasks for all interacting individuals or roles.

3.5.1 Responsibility of the user

The protection of privacy is primarily a personal responsibility. This can be compromised by:

- lack of skills,
- a lack of training,
- lack of awareness of how to use platforms and services securely,
- and non-compliance with suggested privacy settings

People often prioritize short-term concrete benefits ("I easily find the best travel tips") over long-term abstract benefits ("Protection of my privacy").

3.5.2 Responsibility of the operator

Users entrust the operator of the system with their personal data and information. In return, the operators of these systems should take every measure not to disappoint this entrusted trust. Therefore, the protection of private data and the security of this data should be considered very early in the development of these services.

In compliance with the current state of the art, current standards, and legal regulations and requirements involves considerations such as how data is stored and processed, how the necessary access to this data is designed, and how unauthorized groups are kept away from this system. From a user's perspective, these considerations should also include the business model of the operator and extend beyond the lifetime of the system.

With the GDPR, the European Commission has provided a framework that safeguards the rights of individuals and provides operators of internet services with guidance on how to handle user data. It obliges operators of digital services to protect the private data of their customers, to communicate their policies on this and to give customers the opportunity to make informed decisions about the use of their personal data.

3.6 Challenges and Threats

Smart systems, whose services are based on artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things, are ubiquitous in many areas of life. While these services offer many advantages over traditional systems, they are also becoming more vulnerable to various threats. From cyber attacks to data breaches, these systems are exposed to a variety of threats.

By attacking these services or the privacy of users, malicious actors can trigger fears and concerns and at the very least damage or destroy trust in these platforms. This can lead to people avoiding these systems or users registering with inaccurate or false data.

Since new technologies (AI, data analysis, data linking) can generate new data from existing data sources and this data can also be circulated quickly, additional data protection and security issues arise.

MaaS is at least a Cyber-Physical System, which means that these systems contain physical, cyber, and human aspects. Usually, these components interact with each other. Therefore, each component can threaten each other or be used to protect the other components (Valenza, 2023).

FIGURE 16 shows the link between physical, cyber, and human components. These links are not necessarily one-to-one relationships, and the components can also be used in combination.

FIGURE 16: The main components of a hybrid system threat model
(Source: Valenza, 2023)

Threat scenarios in the context of smart services or CPS describe potential risks and dangers that users, organizations, and systems may face. However, the hybrid system threat model also shows that the respective components can also be the starting point of a threat.

- Security vulnerabilities in devices or networks, or the use of outdated protocols and standards, pose the risk that attackers will exploit these weaknesses to gain access to the systems, ultimately threatening the integrity, security, and reliability of the system. This can also make access to confidential data too easy.

- Targeted cyber attacks actively seek to find and exploit weaknesses in the system.
- The threat can come from various attackers:
 - other users within the service,
 - the operator of the service, or their employees and
 - external organizations.

Various named attack scenarios are briefly described below.

3.6.1 Spam and phishing emails

Phishing occurs when fraudsters send emails aimed at obtaining sensitive information and data from the recipient. Typically, these emails appear to originate from reputable companies or even official institutions and service providers (police, insurance companies, etc.). The text often informs the potential victim that their account is compromised, prompting them to click on a link to provide confidential information for account verification.

3.6.2 Social engineering

Criminals attempt to gain access to a user account and then expand its permissions. Preferably, methods are used where the target voluntarily hands over their username and password to the attacker. In this case, the victim is unaware of whom they are providing access credentials to.

3.6.3 Botnets

A botnet refers to a network of interconnected computers or Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices on which a bot has been installed via malware (see also Section 3.6.9). Attackers often exploit the computational power, network connectivity, and data of the remotely controlled computers to carry out further attacks.

3.6.4 Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks

In a DDoS attack, attackers intentionally attempt to block a website, server, or network resource by overwhelming it with targeted requests until it can no longer accept and process legitimate service requests.

3.6.5 Exploitation of vulnerabilities in software and hardware

During the development of software and hardware, security-related aspects may not receive the necessary attention. The resulting security vulnerabilities should be addressed as early as possible through software and security updates or the implementation of current standards. If these vulnerabilities remain open, there is a possibility that external attackers can gain complete access to the network. Cybercriminals are constantly searching for such vulnerabilities and attempt to fully exploit them.

3.6.6 Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs)(unauthorized access and intrusion)

An unauthorized individual gains access to a network and attempts to remain undetected for as long as possible. Attackers primarily aim to steal data without leaving traces or causing other damage.

3.6.7 Impact of unstable infrastructure

Disruptions in infrastructure (internet connection, power supply, backend servers) can lead to data loss. If this data is essential for the functioning of the system, then the functionality and reliability of the system may suffer. Disruptions can also create security vulnerabilities, making systems more susceptible to hacker attacks and data breaches.

3.6.8 Manipulation of individual networked devices

By manipulating individual devices (smart vehicles, smart measuring instruments, etc.) within a smart service infrastructure, the entire system can be disrupted. This can lead to system malfunctions or a complete failure of the service.

3.6.9 Malware (malicious software, malfunction)

The most well-known types of malicious software are viruses, trojans, and worms.

3.6.10 Ransomware

With ransomware, criminals gain access to the IT system and encrypt the data contained within it. To regain access to this data, the victim needs a decryption code, which is usually only available for a very high ransom payment.

3.6.11 Misuse of algorithms

Algorithms used in smart systems are often complex and opaque. This can lead to the disadvantage of certain groups, and the results are often not transparent. If smart services incorporate currently collected data into decision-making, there is a risk that decision-relevant data may be deliberately manipulated, influencing the outcomes.

3.7 EC Regulations & Frameworks

3.7.1 GDPR

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is a European regulation (EUR-Lex - GDPR, 2016) that governs the protection of personal data in the European Union (EU). It came into force on May 25, 2018, and replaces the previous Data Protection Directive (EUR-Lex - DPD, 1995). The GDPR sets out uniform rules for the processing of personal data and gives individuals more control over their own data (EC - GDPR, 2024).

Since this framework is publicly available and individual countries provide a guide to it in their respective languages, this framework is only summarized here in a very condensed form.

The GDPR (EUR-Lex - GDPR, 2016) defines rules about privacy, data storage, data processing and data security.

3.7.1.1 Privacy

Personal data may only be collected and processed for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and only the personal data that is necessary for processing may be collected. In other words, the data must be limited to what is necessary for processing.

Data subjects must be informed about the processing. If the processing is based on the consent of the data subject, this must be voluntary, specific, and unambiguous. At least, consent to this data processing can also be withdrawn at any time.

In addition to this general definition, specific rights of data subjects are outlined here.

Rights of data subjects

To enable data subjects to assert their rights, relevant information and notifications should be provided in:

- easily understandable language,
- writing or electronically, but also
- in oral form.

Requests for information, rectification or erasure, an objection or a request for restriction of processing or data transfer must be answered to the data subject without delay and in any case within one month. Electronic inquiries must be answered electronically.

The exercise of data subjects' rights must generally be free of charge. In unfounded cases, the operator may levy administrative costs.

Right to information

The data subject may request confirmation as to whether data concerning him or her is being processed, including negative information. If data is processed, the data subject has the right to the following information:

- Purpose of processing,
- Categories of data,
- Copy (e.g., printout) of the processed data content,
- Recipients or categories of recipients,
- Planned duration of storage (or criteria for determining it),
- Existence of rights to rectification, erasure, restriction of processing, or objection,
- Existence of a right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority,
- Available information on the data source and
- Existence of automated decision-making (including profiling), logic, and implications of such processes. The GDPR shortens the deadline for providing information to one month, with a possible extension to three months.

From the perspective of data subjects, GDPR ensures access to their own data, the right to rectification, the right to be forgotten (erase the data), the right to data portability and the right to object to the processing of personal data in certain situations.

3.7.1.2 Data storage and data processing

Data must be accurate and up-to-date, and the processing of this data must be carried out lawfully. Therefore, measures must be taken to ensure that inaccurate or outdated data is corrected or deleted. To ensure the rights of individuals, corresponding obligations arise for the storage and processing of personal data.

The operator and processor must maintain a record of processing activities (EUR-Lex - GDPR, 2016, p. Art. 28). In principle, companies with up to 250 employees are exempt from this regulation (EUR-Lex - GDPR, 2016, p. Art. 30), but not if the processing of the data:

- poses a risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals,
- is regular and not occasional,
- involves sensitive data, such as criminal convictions and offenses.

Data transferred to a recipient in a third country or to an international organization must be subject to a level of protection essentially equivalent to that in the EU.

3.7.1.3 Data security

Appropriate security measures must be taken to protect the data and ensure its confidentiality and integrity. Responsible bodies must be able to demonstrate that they comply with the principles of the GDPR (EC - GDPR, 2024). This also includes keeping records of processing activities.

Before implementing a new data processing system that is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, a data protection impact assessment (EUR-Lex - GDPR, 2016, p. Art. 29) must be conducted. Appropriate security measures must be taken to protect

the data and ensure its confidentiality and integrity. Responsible bodies must be able to demonstrate that they comply with the principles of the GDPR. This also includes keeping records of processing activities. Breaches of personal data protection must be reported to the supervisory authority (EUR-Lex – GDPR, 2016, p. Art. 33), and if necessary, data subjects must also be notified, and the appointment of a data protection officer is mandatory. Violations of the General Data Protection Regulation can result in substantial fines.

3.7.2 Data Governance Act

In a digital world, data is collected and managed across various sectors such as health, environment, energy, agriculture, mobility, finance, manufacturing, and public administration. Organizations are primarily concerned with data privacy and are reluctant to share data externally. However, the availability of data could provide added value for businesses and society.

The Data Governance Act (EUR-Lex – DGA , 2022), introduced by the European Commission, aims to establish, and develop common European data spaces in strategic areas to increase trust in data exchange, strengthen mechanisms for enhancing data availability, and overcome technical barriers to data reuse. The Act regulates processes and structures enabling voluntary data exchange and came into effect in June 2022, with enforcement since September 2023 (EC – Data Governance Act, 2024).

In addition to improving efficiency and sustainability, data availability also drives advancements in artificial intelligence. Furthermore, innovations are expected across various sectors:

- Mobility and environmental data can minimize travel times and combat climate change through targeted measures.
- Agricultural data can advance the agriculture and food sector.
- Public administration data can improve official statistics and facilitate evidence-based decision-making.

3.7.3 Data Act

When users use products or services and increasingly also networked devices from the Internet of Things (IoT) (EC – IoT, 2024) environment, data is recorded by the manufacturer or the operator of the service platform.

In the past, users only had limited opportunity to access this data themselves or to make it available to third parties. It was also not possible for third parties to develop new business areas based on this data.

With the Data Act (EUR-Lex – Data Act, 2023), the EU aims to open the market opportunities arising from the exploitation of this data to a wider audience, while maintaining the protection of personal data (EC – Data Act, 2024). The data act came into force in January 2024 (EC – New Rules, 2024) and supplements the Data Governance Act mentioned above (EUR-Lex – DGA , 2022). It aims to clarify who can create value from this data and under what conditions. In this case the data act also enables **public authorities** to access private sector data in the public interest and to use this data for specific purposes.

The companies concerned must therefore ensure that their products are designed in such a way that they can be made available quickly, easily, and securely. The user must be able to choose between different providers of data processing services (EC – Data economy, 2024).

The Data Act applies to both **personal and non-personal data**. E.g., this includes raw data generated by the user interface and device itself but does not extend to information inferred or derived from this data. It also does not apply to data that sensor-equipped products generate

when the user records, transmits, displays, or plays content, as well as the content itself regarding data sharing.

3.7.4 AI Act

Artificial intelligence applications influence, among other things, the online behaviour of people by predicting what might be of interest to individual users and filtering the content offered accordingly. They capture and analyse data from faces to enforce laws or personalize advertising and are used for the diagnosis and treatment of cancer. AI affects many aspects of modern life (EC - AI Act, 2024).

AI encompasses machine applications capable of mimicking human intelligence. Machines with artificial intelligence learn, assess, and solve problems as well as humans. Artificial intelligence can continuously learn with machine learning, natural language processing, and deep learning. When artificial intelligence is deployed, a large amount of data is processed to train it. In return, this artificial intelligence is also capable of processing large amounts of data (Ambient Innovation: GmbH, 2024).

Artificial intelligence, as is known today, learns within predefined possibilities. If something goes wrong because it was learned or trained incorrectly from the beginning, the artificial intelligence will not recognize this itself. The decision-making processes within AI are not always comprehensible, and in communication, the AI is not always recognizable as such. In most cases, it is also not clear who is responsible in case of errors. This becomes even more apparent when AI makes decisions that are ethically relevant; And the larger the amount of data processed by AI systems, the greater the risk of data misuse and theft.

The AI Act (EUR-Lex - AI Act, 2021) aims to provide AI developers and deployers with clear requirements and obligations regarding the specific use of AI. At the same time, the regulation aims to reduce administrative and financial burdens for companies, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The AI Act is part of a broader package of political measures to support the development of trustworthy AI. This regulation aims to ensure the security and fundamental rights of people and businesses regarding AI (EC - AI Act, 2024).

FIGURE 17: Four levels of risk for AI systems
(Source: EC - AI Act, 2024)

The AI act categorises AI applications into four risk categories:

Unacceptable Risk

Applications falling into this category are prohibited by the AI Act. State-operated social scoring, such as that used in China, is banned in the European Union.

High-Risk Applications

Examples of systems and application areas with high risk include:

- Critical infrastructures, such as transportation, which could endanger the lives and health of citizens.
- Education, or decisions that could determine a person's career path (e.g., exam assessments or resume scanning for applicant ranking).
- Security components of products (e.g., AI applications in robotic surgery).
- Employment, employee management, and access to self-employment (e.g., CV sorting software for hiring processes).
- Essential private and public services (e.g., creditworthiness, where citizens are denied the opportunity to obtain a loan).
- Law enforcement that could interfere with people's fundamental rights (e.g., assessment of the reliability of evidence).
- Migration, asylum, and border control management (e.g., automated examination of visa applications).
- Administration of justice and democratic processes (e.g., AI solutions for searching court judgments).

These applications are subject to strict regulations, including:

- Adequate risk assessment and mitigation systems.
- High quality of datasets supplying the system to minimize risks and discriminatory results.
- Logging of activities to ensure traceability of results.
- Detailed documentation containing all necessary information about the system and its purpose for authorities to assess compliance.
- Clear and adequate information for the operator.
- Appropriate human oversight measures to minimize risk.
- High robustness, security, and accuracy.

Limited-Risk Applications

Limited risk exists when the use of AI is associated with a lack of transparency. To address this issue, the law introduces specific transparency obligations. For example, people interacting with chatbots should be made aware that they are interacting with a machine. Subsequently, people should be able to decide whether they want to interact with the service provider in this manner.

AI-generated content must be identifiable. This applies to AI-generated text as well as to audio and video content representing deepfakes.

Applications with Minimal or No Risk

The AI Act does not impose restrictions on AI with minimal or no risk. This includes applications such as AI-enabled video games or spam filters. Many AI systems currently deployed in the EU fall into this category.

3.7.5 Framework of Trustworthy AI

In April 2019, the High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) on Artificial Intelligence, representing the European Commission, published an ethical guideline for trustworthy AI (EC - Trustworthy AI, 2024). This framework is structured as follows:

FIGURE 18: The Guidelines as a framework for Trustworthy AI
(Source: European Commission, 2024)

A trustworthy AI should be:

- lawful and comply with all applicable laws and regulations,
- ethical, ensuring adherence to ethical principles and values, and
- robust, both technically and socially.

Since AI systems can unintentionally cause harm even with good intentions, these requirements should be met throughout the entire lifecycle of the system.

3.7.5.1 Lawfulness as a Foundation of Trustworthy AI

Lawfulness serves as the cornerstone of trustworthy AI. AI systems do not operate in a legal vacuum. A set of legally binding regulations exists at the European, national, and international levels that must be adhered to or are relevant for the development, deployment, and use of AI systems. The framework for Trustworthy AI outlines the following regulatory frameworks:

- EU primary law (the Treaties of the European Union and its Charter of Fundamental Rights),
- EU secondary law, which includes:

- the General Data Protection Regulation,
- the Product Liability Directive,
- the Regulation on the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data,
- anti-discrimination Directives,
- consumer law, and Safety and Health at Work Directives,
- the UN Human Rights treaties,
- the Council of Europe conventions (such as the European Convention on Human Rights), and
- numerous laws of EU Member States.

Additionally, there are various domain-specific regulations that apply to specific AI applications, such as the Medical Device Regulation in the healthcare sector.

It's important to note that existing laws not only define prohibitions (what one must not do) but also mandates (what one should do).

3.7.5.2 Ethical Principles as a Foundation of Trustworthy AI

Legislators often can only react to technological advancements, and laws may not always be capable of addressing ethical and technical issues. Therefore, trustworthy AI systems must be ethical and aligned with ethical norms.

3.7.5.3 Robustness as a Foundation of Trustworthy AI

Individual citizens and the society as a whole must be able to trust that AI systems will not cause unintentional harm. AI systems should therefore fulfil their functions in a secure and reliable manner. To prevent undesirable negative impacts, security measures should be taken in advance.

3.7.5.4 Requirements of Trustworthy AI

To ensure compliance with the requirements, stakeholders take on different roles and perform various tasks:

- Developers implement the specified requirements during the conception and development of processes.
- Operators should ensure that the systems they deploy, as well as the products and services offered, meet the requirements.
- End users and the broader society should be aware of the requirements for AI systems and be able to insist on their compliance.

The framework defines, without claiming completeness, the following requirements:

- Human agency and oversight, including fundamental rights, human agency, and human oversight.
- Technical robustness and safety, including resilience to attack and security, fallback plans, general safety, accuracy, reliability, and reproducibility.
- Privacy and data governance, including respect for privacy, quality, and integrity of data, and access to data.
- Transparency, including traceability, explainability, and communication.
- Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness, including the avoidance of unfair bias, accessibility and universal design, and stakeholder participation.
- Societal and environmental well-being, including sustainability and environmental friendliness, social impact, society, and democracy.
- Accountability, including auditability, minimization and reporting of negative impact, trade-offs, and redress.

These requirements are fundamentally equal, and their implementation should apply throughout the entire lifecycle of an AI system. However, tensions between the requirements may arise due to the context. Nevertheless, particular attention must be paid to AI systems that directly or indirectly affect people.

3.7.5.5 Assessing Trustworthy AI

The framework provides a non-exhaustive assessment list or questionnaire to evaluate the trustworthiness of AI systems, organizing them into the following main and sub-chapters:

- Human agency and oversight
 - Human agency
 - Human oversight
- Technical robustness and safety
 - Resilience to attack and security
 - Fallback plan and general safety
 - Accuracy
 - Reliability and reproducibility
- Privacy and data governance
 - Respect for privacy and data protection
 - Quality and integrity of data
 - Access to data
- Transparency
 - Traceability
 - Explainability
 - Communication
- Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness
 - Unfair bias avoidance
 - Accessibility and universal design
 - Stakeholder participation
- Societal and environmental well-being
 - Sustainable and environmentally friendly AI
 - Social impact
 - Society and democracy
- Accountability
 - Auditability
 - Documenting trade-offs
 - Ability to redress

3.8 The case studies review

To move from fictitious threats to concrete incidents and to learn from the experience of concrete incidents, current and past incidents in the field of smart mobility have been collected, documented in a structured form and categorised.

3.8.1 Cases: incidents around smart mobility

Research was carried out into incidents that occurred in the past in the context of smart mobility and which had an impact on users, but also on the systems themselves. The sources used for this case study were publications of all kinds, e.g. internet forums, social media, but also press releases from operators of smart mobility services.

A template was used for a uniform documentation of individual cases, with the following structure:

User context

This chapter describes how a user or a customer can benefit from a smart mobility service in its own context.

Business model

The business model describes the perspective of the provider of a service, especially how the provider tries to support their customers and how to make or to save money.

Incident (date & description)

This chapter describes the incident that happened in a detailed way. When did this incident occur and what happened step by step.

Identified risks

If the effects of the incident are not included in the description of the incident, additional foreseeable risks are described in this section.

3.8.2 Categorisation scheme: mapping theory to incidents

In a very first run a categorisation scheme was created with the categories:

- Sensitive information
- Responsibilities
- Challenges and threats

This first scheme helped to align the structure of the case-description, so that the partners in the task could describe the gathered cases in good quality. By the first mappings to the cases some findings had to be added to the concept and the scheme. The final scheme contained the following categories:

Responsibility of the user

When it comes to sensible data, the owner of this data is responsible for the data he/she shares. Data that has not been made available cannot be misused. In some cases, the user is not aware, what he/she is sharing and what impact misuse of the provided information can have.

Responsibility of the service-provider

If private data is made available, responsibilities arise for the operator of the service. The subject of the data must be informed about the processing of the data and consent of the subject is required to process this data. Among other things, the service provider must also ensure the correctness of the processing, the storage of the data and restricted access to this data.

Attacker

The attacker of a system can be another user in the system, an employee of the provider, a subcontractor and of course a hacker from outside the system.

Vulnerabilities within the system

Vulnerabilities can source in human factors, faulty hardware, but also higher power, like earthquakes or fire. But also technical causes, like outdated standards, poorly defined processes, weak access control, interoperability between components or vulnerabilities in third-party components, can lead to vulnerabilities.

Type of cyber attack

This is a given list of known and described kinds of attacks from the theory section of this Case study.

Type of physical attack

Smart mobility is an expression of a CPS, but when considering smart mobility, the physical hardware is often forgotten. Vandalism, manipulation, and theft of physical components of the CPS may lead to malfunction or failure.

3.8.3 Results of case analysis

Twenty-seven cases were collected as part of the field study. These cases can be found in the annex and deal with different topics:

- disclosure and misuse of data
 - #1 GIS – Data disclosure
 - #2 British Airways – Data breach
 - #3 TRENITALIA – Data breach
 - #4 EasyPark – Data breach
 - #5 Waze – Data breach and data misuse
 - #6 Blink Mobility – data breach
 - #7 Blablacar – Data theft
 - #8 Careem – Data breach
 - #9 Uber – Data breach
 - #10 Bycycklen – Database hacked
- violation of privacy
 - #11 CityScoot – GDPR violation
 - #12 Lyft – Privacy abuse
- cyber attacks
 - #13 Ledger – Cyber attack
 - #14 Public Hospital – Cryptolocker
 - #15 TfL Oyster cards – Credential stuffing
 - #16 CODT – Cyber attack
- misuse of the system
 - #17 DPD – AI Chatbot fails
 - #18 google.com – #googlemapshacks
- outdated standards
 - #19 TESLA – Security flaw with keyless entry
 - #20 Jeep Cherokee – Remote car-jacking
- thefts and vandalism
 - #21 ToBike – Vandalism
 - #22 Share – Thefts & vandalism
 - #23 Turin Micromobility – Vandalism
 - #24 Car2Go – Vehicle theft
- misbehaviour of customer
 - #25 Autolib / Reachnow – Customer misbehaviour
- safety and design of vehicles
 - #26 Lyft – E-bike malfunction
- terminated business
 - #27 VanMoof – Bankruptcy

These incidents were mapped to the categorisation scheme described above, so that several dimensions of these incidents could be made visible, see FIGURE 19. The index map shows the resulting threat categories based on the examination of the selected cases. As a result of this examination this map also shows the occurrence of a threat category in different cases.

As part of the GEMINI project, Task 2.3 aims to identify the requirements for the implementation of smart mobility services in WP 4. In this project context, the scheme of categorised threats, developed in this study and used in this index map, can help to identify similar threats for smart mobility services or to formulate additional threat scenarios and then define appropriate protective measures.

3.8.3.1 Statistical summary

In the context of the collected incidents, users' personal information was affected eleven times (41%). Access data to financial accounts and information about location and travel routes were of interest four times each (15%).

When it comes to responsibility to the security of MaaS systems, users being unaware of what can happen to their data (lack of awareness: 11%) leads them to provide more information than required.

In 3 cases (11%), operators of smart services have not ensured sufficient access control to the data they manage. In 2 cases (7%), insufficient security training for employees, unnecessarily linked data and the storage of temporary data were the reasons for security problems. Occasionally, users were not informed about the processing of their data (2 times, 7%).

Basically, the systems were attacked from outside in 15 cases (56%). Four times (15%) the systems were misused or threatened by other registered users and twice (7%) data was misused by employees of the system operator.

In most cases (16 times / 59%), security gaps were used to penetrate the system, with inadequate access control (5 times / 19%) and outdated security standards and inadequate processes (3 times / 11%) specifying these security gaps in more detail. Human error (6 times / 22%) and faulty hardware (3 times / 11%) also facilitated unauthorized access to the system.

Of the reported cyber attacks, exploitation of security gaps was found in 8 cases (30%). Unauthorized access and intrusion were found 6 times (22%). Misuse of the system occurred 3 times (12%).

The physical hardware used in the context of smart mobility systems was manipulated or damaged 3 times (11%) and stolen just as often.

3.8.3.2 Risk analysis

When evaluating the risks described in the cases, these were divided into 3 main categories. Risks have an impact on the service, the service provider, and the customer.

Impact on the service

- Service quality:
 - Due to the shutdown of servers, products owned by customers are not working to their full extent.
 - Poor service quality leads to a poor user experience.
 - Damaged vehicles (e-scooters, bikes, cars, ...) poses safety hazards to users and pedestrians.
 - Algorithms that misunderstand or misinterpret customer queries provide incorrect answers and confuse customers.
 - The suspension of car-sharing services disrupted the daily routines and travel plans of customers.

Impact on the service provider

- Business implications:
 - Financial losses due to unavailable services.
 - Financial losses due to remediation measures caused by damage, theft, and misuse.
 - Financial losses due to loss of market share.
 - Loss of trust and reputations ultimately affects the company's position among consumers, investors, and regulators.
 - Financial losses due to cyber attacks and ransom payments.
- Operational implications:
 - Physical components
 - Misuse or manipulation of physical devices compromises the security of physical components.
 - The increasing integration of internet-connected functions in modern vehicles harbours additional security risks.
 - The unavailability of vehicles due to theft or damage leads to a limited or to a poorer quality of services.
 - Vulnerabilities in third-party components can jeopardize the integrity of services.
 - Data security
 - Unauthorized access to operational data can lead to data breaches.
 - The loss or the theft of data requires additional effort to make the systems secure and operational again.
 - Inadequate security measures can lead to theft or damage of vehicles or relevant hardware.
 - Linked data can facilitate the misuse of data.
 - The involvement of third parties or external service providers can jeopardize data security.
- Legal implications
 - Non-compliance with legal regulations and requirements can lead to possible legal consequences (legal liability or fines and penalties).

Impact on the customer

- Privacy:
 - Exposed personal data impacts the subject's freedom.

- The user's personal information, such as workplace, place of residence or leisure activities, can be extracted from the disclosed track data.
- Identity theft:
 - Private data can be passed on to other criminals on the darknet.
 - Private data can be analysed unlawfully and automatically.
 - Hackers could use stolen personal information for identity theft and fraudulent activities.
- Harassments:
 - Based on private data, customers may be threatened and harassed by home visits, potential stalking or surveillance, phone calls, unsolicited telephone surveys and spam emails.
- Privacy invasion:
 - Information from data breaches, or data leaks, could easily be used for malicious purposes.
 - Criminals can possibly invade the data subject's privacy.
- Financial loss:
 - Financial loss for customers due to unauthorized transactions using compromised payment card information.
- Loss in value:
 - Due to the shutdown of servers, products owned by customers are not working to their full extent.
- Safety concerns:
 - Safety concerns arising from careless vehicle handling by other users.
 - Threats and potential accidents due to remote manipulation of critical systems.
 - Malfunction due to deliberate incorrect operation of the system.

3.8.3.3 Countermeasures to security threats

In the individual cases, countermeasures to increase the security of smart mobility services were also formulated. They were derived from the identified risks and unified and structured afterwards. These countermeasures were assigned to different categories.

- Service design
 - Data management
 - Record necessary personal data only.
 - Pass on sensitive data in encrypted form only.
 - Store data outside the internal IT infrastructure in encrypted form only.
 - Transparency
 - Provide clear rules for the collection, use and transfer of user data within the service.
 - Obtain user consent and control over the processing of personal data.
 - Log every data request to ensure accountability and transparency when accessing data.
 - Inform users about current costs incurred.
 - Flexible implementation when processing user data, depending on their consent.
 - Inform users about the use of AI services.
 - User interaction
 - Develop possible scenarios for misuse of the system.
 - Develop concepts to prevent misuse or unwanted behavior.

- Develop a catalog of incentives and punishments to encourage customers to behave as desired.
 - AI
 - Pay attention to the quality of training data for AI services.
 - Integrate human feedback loops.
 - Answers from chatbots should be checked by human feedback loops.
 - Vehicles
 - out of service
 - Implement secure storage or parking spaces for movable infrastructure (bicycles, cars, ...).
 - Use smart locking mechanisms.
 - Implement GPS tracking systems to monitor vehicles that are not in use.
 - Implement remote-controlled immobilizers.
 - Cooperate with authorities or traffic monitoring and share vehicle and booking information.
 - in operation
 - To be more independent of individual vehicle models, vehicle fleets should be heterogeneous.
 - Follow cyber security by design strategy in vehicle development.
 - Product design
 - Enable short-term vehicle security updates over the air.
 - Implement encryption protocols to prevent unauthorized access to vehicle systems.
- IT-Security
 - Access control
 - Implement multifactor authentication
 - Improved authentication methods for accessing data
 - Use strong passwords
 - Introduce graded access controls to ensure that only roles with specific task-related requirements have access to data.
 - Cyber attacks
 - Minimize the potential external attack surface and protect sensitive components from direct internet access.
 - Implement robust filters for incoming malicious emails
 - Introduce ReCaptcha to prevent access through automated attacks
 - Secure central IT infrastructure
 - SotA
 - Better secure data interfaces
 - Implement encryption, access controls and regular security checks
 - Ensure that computer systems are up to date with the latest security standards
 - Processes
 - Continuous monitoring of network traffic for early detection of unusual activity indicative of a cyber attack
 - Regular security checks for IT infrastructure
 - Implementing data protection guidelines technically
 - Regular system backups including network segmentation.
 - Fully implemented and ready-to-use action plans in the event of cyber incidents

- Define and adhere to processing protocols, including automated alerting mechanisms.
 - Implement data security protocols
 - Generate test data for development purposes
 - Create a data management plan for external commissioning
 - Architecture
 - Segment the network to isolate potential malware.
 - Employees
 - Conduct regular employee training and raise awareness of cyber security.
 - Educate employees about data protection, company roles and policies.
 - Restrict access to certain employees.
 - Install a role or person who monitors the privacy of users within the system and checks the use of the system.
 - Conduct cyber security training for employees.
 - Monitor company employees more closely.
 - User-service interaction
 - Users should use separate account data for different services.
 - Encourage users to use different passwords for different services.
 - Create awareness of collective responsibility and vigilance.
 - Offer training programs for users.
 - Educate customers about criminal phishing strategies.
 - Call on customers to help in the event of data breaches.
- Business
 - Conscious comparison of company and customer interests when processing personal data.
 - When implementing services, compare user convenience and privacy.
 - Pay additional attention to data security when merging companies or services.
 - Provide resources for the implementation of strong cyber security measures, such as regular software updates and patches for the immediate elimination of vulnerabilities.

Of course, this is not an exhaustive list, but this categorised list of countermeasures can also help increase the security of smart mobility services.

3.9 Conclusion

This case study approach shows real threat scenarios and gives insight into the vulnerability of smart services and especially Mobility as a Service (MaaS).

Section 3.8.2 outlines a categorisation scheme categorising various threats, enabling the assessment of potential risks to smart mobility services. Regardless of the threat scenario, section 3.8.3.3 lists measures in general terms that can be used to increase the security of smart mobility services fundamentally.

Privacy by design and data security from the very beginning of the development of smart systems cannot be guaranteed by following rules and regulations only. Awareness about possible incidents is based on experience, which is created in a mental process by own experience or by experience others made.

When considering smart mobility or smart products in common, the physical hardware is often forgotten. Vandalism, manipulation, and theft of physical components of the Cyber-Physical System may lead to malfunction or failure.

This case study provides several results:

- The selected cases provide information about the threats to smart services and how incidents occurred.
- Reading the descriptions of these cases will help create awareness of privacy and data security among responsible parties.
- An overview of EC rules and regulations shows which legal framework conditions must be adhered to.
- A categorisation scheme for threats to smart mobility services can be used for a detailed analysis of the design of specific implementations of a smart services.

4 THE MLL EVALUATION PLANS

In parallel with the development of the first draft of the GEMINI evaluation framework, the individual MLL evaluation plans were developed, in close collaboration with the GEMINI partner coordinating the MLL and main stakeholders. The methodology outlined in this draft version of the GEMINI evaluation framework was thereby followed and the GEMINI evaluation sheets (see Section 2.6.1 and Appendix A: GEMINI evaluation sheets) formed the basis for the discussions and setup of each MLL evaluation plan.

In the following Chapters 5 to 12, the 8 lead and twinning MLL¹⁰ measures and their evaluation approach are presented, including:

1. A short description of the (mobility) **context** of the MLL, with a section on the current shared mobility services already available in each MLL.
2. A summary of the **objectives** of the MLL
3. A concise **description** of the MLL **measure**, and the expected **outputs**
4. **Test area** and **target groups** of the MLL
5. An overview of the:
 - **city context indicators** that will be monitored
 - the expected impact, the **impact indicators** and data collection methodology
 - the selected **additional indicators**
6. Important elements for the evaluation of the implementation process: the different **stakeholders** involved, their roles and the planned **supporting activities**
7. A planning of each measure visualised in a **Gantt chart**

The baseline of the 3 types of indicator – city context, impact and additional – will be presented in deliverable D3.1 Interim progress report of MLLs implementation, in month 18 (November 2024), as well as a first analysis of the barriers and drivers of the implementation process.

The final impact and process results of the evaluation of the 8 GEMINI MLLs will be published in D3.10 Final Impact Assessment of GEMINI NMS and MLLs, in month 38 (July 2026).

¹⁰ The twinning MLLs start operations later than the lead MLLs, allowing for replication of the positive experiences of the lead MLLs in the twinning MLLs.

5 EVALUATION PLAN OF MLL 1 - AMSTERDAM

5.1 Context

5.1.1 Geography and population Amsterdam

The city of Amsterdam, located in the province of North Holland, is the capital of the Netherlands. The city is divided into 8 districts: Amsterdam Centre, West, East, North, South, New-West, Western Gateway (Westpoort) and Southeast.¹¹ The districts are further divided into neighbourhoods. Since 2022, the city expanded, and has in addition to the 8 districts, 1 urban area Weesp¹², see FIGURE 20.

FIGURE 20: Amsterdam and its districts.
(Source: <https://maps.amsterdam.nl/gebiedsindeling/>)

At the start of 2024, the city of Amsterdam counted almost 930 748 inhabitants. It is expected that the population will increase to over 1 million (1 079 168) by 2025, representing a growth of 16%. This growth is not evenly distributed across the various neighbourhoods in the city. The strongest population growth is expected in the North and Southeast districts, see FIGURE 21. The significant increase in population in the North would be mainly due to further housing construction in the Northern IJ Banks West and Northern IJ Banks East neighbourhoods.¹³ Western Gateway (Westpoort) is an industry area with (hardly) any residents, and is therefore not included in this figure.

¹¹ <https://www.amsterdam.nl/en/districts-neighbourhoods/>

¹² <https://onderzoek.amsterdam.nl/artikel/nieuwe-indeling-naar-wijken-en-buurtten-2022>

¹³ <https://onderzoek.amsterdam.nl/artikel/prognose-bevolking-2024-2050>

FIGURE 21: Expected population growth by 2050 in the different neighbourhoods of Amsterdam. (Source: O&S)

5.1.2 Modal share Amsterdam

FIGURE 22 presents the modal share of residents in Amsterdam, based on the yearly household survey Onderweg in Nederland¹⁴. As in most Dutch cities, cycling is the most popular mode of transport in Amsterdam. Most of the trips by Amsterdam residents are done by bike (34%), followed by walking (30%). Up to 21% of the trips are done by car, 11% by public transport, and 3% by other means of transport.

FIGURE 22: Modal share residents of Amsterdam in 2022. (Source: Onderweg in Nederland, <https://onderzoek.amsterdam.nl/artikel/verkeer-in-cijfers-2024>)

¹⁴ <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/longread/rapportages/2023/onderweg-in-nederland--odin---2022-onderzoeksbeschrijving/2-onderweg-in-nederland--odin-->

Over recent years, Amsterdam residents have reduced their number of daily trips. While in 2005 the average number of trips was still 3.1 per day, by 2022, this had decreased to 2.4 per day. The reason for this decline over the past twenty years is the digitalization of work, shopping, and services. Nowadays, residents of Amsterdam work more from home and make purchases online more often.¹⁵

5.1.3 Car and bike ownership Amsterdam

In 2023, there were 206 837 privately-owned cars in the city. This means that on average, each household in Amsterdam has 0.4 cars (the more than 930 000 inhabitants are spread across 505 705 households¹⁶). This is the lowest number of cars per household of all municipalities in the Netherlands. The number of electric/hybrid cars has been increasing rapidly for years. At the start of 2023, 30 852 were electric/hybrid, good for 12% of the privately owned cars. This number is continuously rising, by the end of 2023, there were approximately 40 000 electric or plug-in hybrid cars in Amsterdam.

FIGURE 23: Number of cars in the city of Amsterdam, with the percentage of electric/hybrid cars. (Source: CBS, Klimaatmonitor, <https://onderzoek.amsterdam.nl/artikel/verkeer-in-cijfers-2024>)

Latest statistics on the number of bicycles in Amsterdam (2017) estimated a total of 904 203 bicycles in the city of Amsterdam.¹⁷ Residents of Amsterdam are increasingly using electric bicycles. The number of Amsterdam households with an electric bicycle increased from 29 800 in 2018 to 57 000 in 2021. Onderzoek en Statistiek reported that in 2023, based on results from a survey including 1 000 cyclists over 20 locations in Amsterdam, roughly three-quarters (78%) cycled with a non-electric bicycle, 19% with an electric bike, and for 3% it is unclear or unknown.¹⁸ Especially fatbikes are increasingly shaping the streets. Because fatbikes do not require a helmet, residents of Amsterdam often use them instead of a moped.¹⁵

5.1.4 Shared mobility Amsterdam

Considering the limited space availability and the growing population and number of visitors, the city of Amsterdam sees a great potential in shared mobility for freeing up public space.

¹⁵ <https://onderzoek.amsterdam.nl/artikel/verkeer-in-cijfers-2024>

¹⁶ <https://kadastralekaart.com/gemeenten/amsterdam-GM0363>

¹⁷ https://openresearch.amsterdam.nl/media/inline/2024/1/4/monitor_fiets_2022-367629848.pdf

¹⁸ <https://onderzoek.amsterdam.nl/publicatie/monitor-fietstevredenheid-2023>

FIGURE 24: Shared mobility offer in Amsterdam.
(Source: <https://kaart.amsterdam.nl/deelvervoer/>)

Amsterdam currently has 4 types of shared mobility: car-sharing, shared bikes, shared e-cargo-bikes and shared mopeds. Shared e-scooters are currently excluded from the shared mobility options in Amsterdam. FIGURE 24 gives an overview of the areas offering shared mobility.

Besides the nationwide available shared bike “OV-fiets” at the train stations, Amsterdam has 1 shared bike provider, Donkey Republic, with 800 bikes, of which approximately 200 e-bikes. In addition, the shared mobility provider Cargoroo offers 110 e-cargo-bikes in Amsterdam.¹⁹

Since April 2024, Amsterdam has 1200 shared mopeds available across the city, operated by the 2 providers Check and Go Sharing (both providers supply 600 shared mopeds).²⁰

Multiple car-sharing providers are active in Amsterdam. Some providers offer cars which are collected and returned to fixed parking spots, other shared cars are either zone-floating (with parking options in a certain neighbourhood) or free-floating (these shared cars can be picked up and dropped off anywhere within the service area). In 2024, 9 shared car providers are operational in Amsterdam: MyWheels, Greenwheels, Diks autodelen, ShareNow, GreenMobility, Sixt share, Check autodelen, Ready2share/Mr Green and Vloto cars. In addition, Amsterdam promotes the sharing of private vehicles with neighbours and friends (peer-to-peer), through platforms like SnapCarr, and the sharing of cars within a (closed) group. The GEMINI MLL pilots the latter shared car option in different areas across Amsterdam. In 2024, around 3 500 shared cars are available in Amsterdam, and this number is increasing every day. This is about 1.7% of the total number of private cars in the city of Amsterdam.²¹

¹⁹ <https://www.amsterdam.nl/deelvervoer/deelfiets/>

²⁰ <https://www.amsterdam.nl/deelvervoer/deelscooter/>

²¹ <https://www.amsterdam.nl/deelvervoer/deelauto/>

5.2 Objectives

Environmental:

- At least 50% reduced car ownership of MaaC members.
- Improved air quality and reduced greenhouse gas emissions thanks to reduced car ownership.
- Easier access to (new and shared) mobility for all people.

Societal:

- Improved social cohesion in the neighbourhood.
- Improved accessibility²² and inclusivity of NMS by offering services outside the service areas of commercial shared mobility schemes and for a larger group of people beyond high-income young professionals.
- More liveable cities thanks to freeing up parking space.

Economic:

- Up-skilling members MaaC communities: improved skills, local resilience, increased capacity local community, taking responsibility, increased confidence.
- Strengthening the independent local economy in order to create a stronger social network.

5.3 Measure description

5.3.1 Challenges in relation to GEMINI

Shared mobility is becoming increasingly more popular in the Netherlands and particularly in larger cities where several commercial mobility providers operate. In smaller cities or in suburban areas, shared mobility is often still not available, mostly due to the lack of a business case for mobility providers. A recent study by Utrecht University shows that in order to remain profitable, shared mobility providers serve higher income groups. In Amsterdam, mobility providers are interested in offering their services in the city centre or the more affluent districts. Most shared mobility users are (white) men aged between 18 and 30 earning close to double of the average Dutch salary. The city of Amsterdam wishes to make shared mobility more affordable and inclusive and offer an alternative to the current commercial offer/proposal.

5.3.2 General description

The Amsterdam MLL introduces an alternative to commercial business and governance models for shared mobility in Amsterdam, coined as “Mobility as a Commons” (MaaC). MaaC comprises a set of initiatives organised by communities in the form of cooperatives with the purpose of meeting the social mobility needs of the community members through shared mobility. The city sees great potential in the MaaC business model. The result envisioned is more affordable community-based mobility, resilient cities, and citizens, where citizens are in charge of their own mobility costs, data ownership, type of modality and platform used, and sometimes free ridership for members of a MaaC cooperative. These are very interesting incentives making people move more and use more sustainable modes that take up less space enhancing an inclusive and sustainable future. At least 5 sub-labs will be piloted in urban and peri-urban Amsterdam. Each Amsterdam sub-lab is expected to have between 50 and 200 members.

²² affordable fees, type of vehicles, platform used for shared modes, use of credit cards, geographic location

Selected/envisoned sub-labs at the start of the GEMINI project:

1. **Already existing MaaC communities ED de Pijp, DeelCentrum, Tuindorp:** Before the start of the GEMINI project, Amsterdam already had three different MaaC communities. These were the very first pilots that also led the municipality of Amsterdam to join the Gemini initiative. The municipality wished to start more communities and to learn from the already existing ones. These are not actual GEMINI Living Labs anymore, but will supply the evaluators with an abundance of qualitative data and lessons learned on the very first steps towards MaaC in Amsterdam.
2. **Spaarndammerbuurt:** Built in the 1900s to house the many dock workers that were working in Amsterdam. In collaboration with the housing company the pilot will explore what MaaC structure fits the residents best. In this community the aim is also to improve social interaction, to create local jobs where possible, to collaborate with local businesses and to train locals to set up the MaaC community.
3. **Nieuw-West:** In the Nieuw-West part of Amsterdam there is a Community Building Initiative that seems promising for the GEMINI project as well: this could be the basis on which a Mobility as a Commons scheme could also grow. The Amsterdam partners are looking for a collaboration with this initiative.
4. **Additional sub-labs answering to an “open call”:** Amsterdam-West, students, max. 5 year rental agreement with the student house.

5.3.3 Output

- At least 5 operational MaaC initiatives in urban and peri-urban Amsterdam
- An umbrella commons structure at city level. An umbrella commons structure is a commons structure which other smaller commons can join. With this they can work together in procurement, handling data, invoicing etc.

5.4 Test area and target groups

FIGURE 25: Amsterdam MLL area visualising the different sub-labs.

Test area: The different sub-labs in the city of Amsterdam, as visualised in FIGURE 25 .

Target group: Residents of Amsterdam with a driving licence and car owners. It is of the absolute essence that anyone can join, however it will be interesting to evaluate which people eventually did join and to then look at the demographics of that group. Only people in the neighbourhood can join an existing MaaC, but everyone can set up a MaaC in their neighbourhood.

5.5 Impact evaluation

5.5.1 City context indicators

TABLE 8: Amsterdam city context indicators and data sources

#	Indicator	Sources
1	Modal split	Data available from the municipality ²³ .
2	Number of road crashes	data.amsterdam.nl
3	Number of seriously injured	
4	Number of road deaths	
5	Density of shared mobility services	Data available from municipality through MDS API on ViaNova Platform www.amsterdam.nl/deelvervoer/
6	Availability of shared mobility services	MDS API on Vianova Platform deelvervoer AMS deelvervoer 2023
7	Availability MaaS	Visie MaaS Amsterdam
8	Car ownership	CBS data
9	Bike ownership	data.amsterdam.nl
10	Congestion levels	maps.amsterdam.nl/verkeersprognoses
11	Parking pressure	maps.amsterdam.nl/parkeerdruk/
12	Quality of cycling network	MRA Snelfiets-netwerk User satisfaction

²³ All public data can be found at data.amsterdam.nl or maps.amsterdam.nl, other data you have to request us specifically so we can ask the right departments

5.5.2 Impact indicators

TABLE 9: Objectives and selected impact indicators to monitor these objectives in the Amsterdam MLL

Impact indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Increase share of NMS in the modal distribution	Modal share NMS in modal split	Survey & data from Amsterdam ²⁴	start & end project	Residents sub-labs
2	Reduction of road risk	-Number of collisions per mode -Number of fatalities, serious and light injuries per mode -Incidents registered by participants in MLL	Data from Amsterdam, own registration		MLL area sub-labs
3	Reduced public parking spaces	Number of public parking spaces	Countings		MaaC participants
4	Improved accessibility to NMS	Affordable fees, type of vehicles, platform used for shared modes, use of credit cards, geographic location	Compare costs per business model (MaaC vs commercial vs privately owned)		-MLL area -Residents sub-labs
5	Improved accessibility PT	Qualitative assessment: -Is there a relation to the usage of PT or other types of transport? -Do people become more mobile overall?	-Interviews members MaaC -Focus group stakeholders		MaaC participants
6	Improved awareness of MaaC	Awareness of MaaC	Survey		MaaC participants
7	Improved social inclusion	-Reduced mobility poverty: number of social interactions and connections -Number of people who make trips that would be impossible before (because of financial reasons) that add to their quality of life.	-Interviews members MaaC -Focus group stakeholders -Mapping of the members and the community in a Value Network and a Knowledge Network	start & end project	MaaC participants
8	Improved social cohesion	Number of social interactions and connections	-Interviews members MaaC -Focus group stakeholders -Mapping of the members and the community in a Value Network and a Knowledge Network	end project	MaaC participants

²⁴ Municipality of Amsterdam works on a monitor for data from shared mobility in an innovation team.

Impact indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
9	Insourcing and upskilling	Identify skills that are being addressed in the neighbourhood that were outsourced before our lab started	-Interviews members MaaC -Focus group stakeholders -Mapping of the local economy in a Value Network and a Knowledge Network		
10	Reduction of traffic related air pollution	NO _x and PM emissions	XIPE model		MLL area sub-labs
11	Reduction of traffic related CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂ emissions			

5.5.3 Additional indicators

TABLE 10: Additional indicators of the Amsterdam MLL

Additional indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Lower car ownership within the MaaC initiatives (not the city as a whole)	-Number of cars before entering the experiment Number of cars at the end of experiment -Number of parking permits	Analysing data query from the initiatives and permits handed out by municipality	6 months	MLL area sub-labs
2	Increased skills within the local community	Number of insourced tasks	Training locals to run their own communities	t.b.d.	MLL area sub-labs
Additional indicators => NMS performance					
#	Indicator		Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Number of vehicles per MaaC/community (per number of cars in the sub-area)		Data from MaaC/community	(start &) end project	Communities
2	Number of users per MaaC/community				
3	Number of trips/week per MaaC/community				
4	Average trip distance per shared mode				
5	Average well-to-wheels CO ₂ emissions shared car per MaaC/community				
6	Travel behaviour MaaC community before and after MaaC		Interviews/survey members	(start &) end project	Members communities
7	Availability and satisfaction charging poles at reserved MaaC parkings				
8	MaaC user satisfaction				

Additional indicators => BM performance			
#	Indicator	Method/Source	Frequency
1	Investment costs	Accounting communities, checks by operator (Townmaking)	once, at start
2	Operational costs		monthly
3	Subsidisation/financial incentive	City of Amsterdam and/or operator (Townmaking)	end project
4	Revenues	Accounting communities, checks by operator (Townmaking)	monthly
5	No. jobs generated	Headcount neighbourhood shops	yearly

5.6 Process evaluation

5.6.1 Stakeholders involved

TABLE 11: Overview of the Amsterdam MLL partners and stakeholders involved, and their role

Stakeholders			
Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - E: Evaluator/ knowledge institution - S: Supplier			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
Citizens	none	P	The citizens make the MaaC communities, without them the communities cease to exist.
City of Amsterdam	City	L	The city coordinates the MLL and is responsible for setting up, running, supervising, monitoring, and evaluating the pilots' activities in all sub-labs.
Townmaking (TM)	NGO	P	Townmaking works together with the citizens in implementing the MaaC and designing the MaaC administration procedures. Townmaking will be closely involved in a qualitative assessment (knowledge mapping) of the different sub-labs.
Cenex	Knowledge institution	E	Cenex is the local evaluation manager, and will do a data driven assessment of MaaC, in collaboration with the MLL partners.
GOODMOOVS	Private company	S	GoodMoovs provides the e-vehicle sharing platform.

5.6.2 Supporting activities

A communication plan will be developed detailing how to communicate MaaC in the different targeted sub-areas, include a campaign video, webpage on the city of Amsterdam website, etc.

5.6.3 Planned implementation phases

TABLE 12: Planned implementation phases of the Amsterdam MLL

Planned implementation phases		
#	Phase	Milestone
1	First pilot stage	Three MaaC communities started in Amsterdam = > finished
2	Implementation of parking policy	New policy in Amsterdam for MaaC communities => in progress
3	Up-scaling: new MaaC communities or more members within existing communities	Five new MaaC communities or significant growth within MaaC initiative => in progress
4	Operational	Communities run by themselves (with minimal help)
5	Evaluation	Evaluation of MaaC and policy guidelines for future initiatives

6 EVALUATION PLAN OF MLL 2 – COPENHAGEN

6.1 Context

6.1.1 Geography and population Copenhagen

The Region Hovedstaden or the Capital Region of Denmark is one of the 5 administrative regions of Denmark, located in the most eastern part of the country (see FIGURE 27). Region Hovedstaden was established in 2007, during the Danish municipal reform, merging the previous 16 Danish counties in 5 regions.

Region Hovedstaden consists of 29 municipalities and includes the municipality and capital Copenhagen. The region has more than 1.9 million inhabitants (1 911 067 on 01/01/2024), Copenhagen city counts 659 350 residents.²⁵ One of the 29 municipalities in Region Hovedstaden, is Rudersdal municipality, located 20 km north of Copenhagen city (see FIGURE 28). Rudersdal is the pilot area of this MLL. It has a population of 57 237 inhabitants (01/01/2024)²⁵.

FIGURE 27: Region Hovedstaden (in red), which includes the municipalities Copenhagen (København) and Rudersdal .
(Source: [Wikimedia Commons](#))

FIGURE 28: Rudersdal municipality. Source: [Google Maps](#)

²⁵ <https://www.statistikbanken.dk/FOLK1A>

6.1.2 Modal share Copenhagen

Copenhagen is considered as one of the most bicycle-friendly cities in the world, even lending its name to the Copenhagenize index²⁶, a world ranking of bicycle-friendly cities.

FIGURE 29: Modal share Copenhagen, 2022.
(Source: Mobilitetsredegørelse 2023, København Kommune)

As shown in FIGURE 29, in 2022, 30% of the trips to, from and in Copenhagen by residents and non-residents, were done walking, 26% by bike and 18% by public transport, leaving 26% of the trips done by car (København Kommune, 2023). Copenhagen residents opt even more strongly for active travel, with 37% of the trips done by walking, 28% cycling, and only 21% of the trips done by car. FIGURE 30 presents the evolution of the modal share of trips to, from and in Copenhagen over the last decade, and the target for 2025. By then, trips done by car should only represent a maximum of 25% of the overall trips, all other trips should be done by walking, cycling or public transport.

FIGURE 30: Modal share trips to and from Copenhagen by residents and non-residents (From 2013 to 2022 and targets set for 2025, Source: Mobilitetsredegørelse 2023, København Kommune)

²⁶ <https://copenhagenizeindex.eu/about/the-index>

6.1.3 Rudersdal: modal share and its climate action plan

Rudersdal is connected to Copenhagen city by the E47 motorway and has a connecting train service to the capital. This is complemented by local and regional bus services covering its residential areas and business parks.²⁷

Nevertheless, the car is the vast majority of citizens' favourite mode, 71% of trips are done by car, 21% by public transport and only 7% by bike. The car is used for commuting and to travel between destinations within the municipal boundaries. In addition to car journeys from Rudersdal's citizens, car journeys from other citizens or other municipalities make up for a relatively large share of the total transport in Rudersdal. This is partly due to a large proportion of commuters who drive through Rudersdal to commute, just as Rudersdal's citizens use other municipalities' roads to travel to and from work (Rudersdal Kommune, 2022).

In light of the current climate crisis and the goals set in the Paris Agreement, Rudersdal municipality adopted in 2022 the Rudersdal climate plan "Klimahandlingsplan for Rudersdal Kommune 2022-2040" (Rudersdal Kommune, 2022). The municipal climate plan is part of Denmark's national project DK2020²⁸, which invites all Danish municipalities to develop ambitious climate action plans to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. It is a detailed plan on how Rudersdal can become climate neutral by 2040 and reduce CO₂ emissions from energy consumption in buildings, the production of goods and services, as well as in transport. Rudersdal's climate action plan has 2 main focuses for mobility:

1. Switching to CO₂-neutral fuels for road transport vehicles:
 - 50% of Rudersdal's passenger cars electric by 2030
 - Installation of publicly accessible charging points for electric cars
 - Zero-emission buses (electric, hydrogen or similar)
 - Etc.
2. Alternative transport modes and habits (reducing the need for transport):
 - Increase the number of cyclists (by 2%)
 - Increase carpooling (by min. 1%)
 - Shift car traffic to public transport (10% more passengers in public transport)
 - Working from home

The Rudersdal climate plan and set-out goals can be an important driver for the implementation and success of the Copenhagen MLL.

6.1.4 Car and bike ownership Copenhagen

TABLE 13: Bike and car ownership in 2022.

Category	2022	Development 2018-22
Population	652 200	5%
Bicycles in total	745 800	11%
Electric bicycles	26 800	367%
Cargo bikes (incl. electric)	40 000	66%
Private cars (total)	142 200	13%
electric cars	4 260 (2023: 7 269)	764%

²⁷ <https://rudersdal.dk/english/business-and-industry-rudersdal/transport-links>

²⁸ <https://www.c40.org/news/local-action-global-impact-denmark-climate-action-planning-dk2020/>

Category	2022	Development 2018-22
plug-in hybrid cars	3 550 (2023: 4 839)	3 416%
Car-sharing (total)	4 390	40%
with fixed permanent parking space	500	192%
without a fixed parking space	1 330	42%
Neighbour to-neighbour cars ²⁹	2 560	27%

Source: Mobilitetsredegørelse 2023, København Kommune.

In 2022, Copenhagen registered 142 400 car owners or 218 cars per 1000 residents, and more than five times more bike owners (745 800) compared to 2018. The number of passenger cars has increased by 13% over the past five years, while the population of Copenhagen has grown by 5% in the same period. The number of bicycles has increased by 11% over the past five years.

The number of electric and plug-in hybrid cars in Copenhagen is growing rapidly. In 2022, there were 4 260 electric cars and 3 550 plug-in hybrid cars in Copenhagen, which is more than double compared to 2021, and the numbers are still rising. In total, electric cars and plug-in hybrid cars account for 5.5% of all private cars in the city.

Car-sharing is also on the rise in Copenhagen. In total, there were just under 4 400 car-sharing vehicles, including neighbour-to-neighbour cars, available in Copenhagen in 2022, an increase of 40% overall since 2018, partly due to the fact that the framework for shared cars with a fixed parking space was expanded in 2022.

6.1.5 Shared mobility Copenhagen

Car-sharing

The city of Copenhagen aims to reduce the number of car trips in the city and associated CO₂ emissions by promoting car-sharing. With the Action Plan for Car-Sharing 2022-2025³⁰, the city has set a goal that all shared cars should be electric by 2027, and half of them by 2025.

TABLE 14 lists the 6 shared car service operational in Copenhagen city in 2022 and the number of vehicles available. Unfortunately, shared car operator and GEMINI partner SHARE NOW shut down operations in Denmark on February 29, 2024³¹.

TABLE 14: Operators and number of shared car vehicles in 2022.

	Operator	Number of cars
1	LetsGo	292
2	GoMore	78
3	Kinto Share	126
4	GreenMobility	600
5	SHARE NOW	731
6	Gomore (neighbour-to-neighbour cars)	2 563
	Total	4 390

With the exception of the Gomore operator, these are shared cars with fixed stations. SHARE NOW stopped its operation in Denmark on 29/02/2024. Source: Mobilitetsredegørelse 2023, København Kommune.

²⁹ Neighbour-to-Neighbour car sharing is a private car sharing scheme where owners of private cars rent their car to others

³⁰ <https://www.kk.dk/politik/politikker-og-indsatser/trafik-og-fremkommelighed/handlingsplan-for-delebilisme-2022-2025>

³¹ <https://www.share-now.com/dk/en/share-now-copenhagen-closing/>

Some usage statistics of shared car services in Copenhagen city are given in TABLE 15. The city of Copenhagen wants to set an example and inspire companies to promote car-sharing for commuting to work.

TABLE 15: Usage of car-sharing services in Copenhagen in 2021 and 2022.

	2021	2022
No. of trips	2 201	3 780
No. of km driven	95 891	132 963
Registered users	448	714

Source: Mobilitetsredegørelse 2023, København Kommune.

Shared e-scooters and bike-sharing

In June 2019, Copenhagen city council decided, that there can be a maximum of 3 200 **shared e-scooters**, divided between a maximum of 4 operators in Copenhagen city, and that the e-scooters may only be parked in defined parking areas, see TABLE 16. These parking areas may not be located in a defined prohibition zone in the city centre, the inner parts of the bridge districts, or also at Svanemøllen Strand.

Statistics on the usage of these e-scooters shows that on average e-scooters are most commonly used in the warmer months and between 15:00 and 18:00. On weekends, the trips are spread more throughout the day.

TABLE 16: Number of authorised shared e-scooters and shared bikes available in Copenhagen 2022.

	Operator	Number of authorised shared e-scooters	Number of shared bikes
1	Bolt	800	1 850
2	Lime	800	2 000
3	Tier	800	1 700
4	Voi	800	/
5	Donkey Republic	/	1 500
	Total	3 200	7 050

Source: Mobilitetsredegørelse 2023, København Kommune.

In 2022 more than 7 000 shared bikes were available in Copenhagen city by 4 operators (TABLE 16). Approximately 5 500 of the bikes are e-bikes, the remaining are pedal-powered.

In December 2022, Bikeshare Danmark A/S, the operating company behind Bycyklen, declared bankruptcy. The white Bycyklen city bike had, since spring 2014, characterised the cityscape of Copenhagen and surrounding areas with more than 130 city bike stations located primarily at train and metro stations.

6.2 Objectives

Environmental:

- Support the goals of the local climate strategy³², such as moving car traffic to public transport and increasing the use of cycling
- Increased use of shared mobility in Rudersdal
- Increased use of public transportation connected to the mobility hub
- Reduced (private & business) car use and car ownership in Rudersdal
- Reduced congestion thanks to reduced car use
- Reduced CO₂ emissions related to reduced car use

Societal:

- Increased liveability in Rudersdal thanks to freeing up parking space
- More inclusive accessibility to NMS for a larger group of people

Safety & Security:

Safer urban areas and streets thanks to reduced car traffic

Economic:

A more attractive Rudersdal for businesses and tourists thanks to improved accessibility of public transport through the mobility hubs and new shared mobility services

6.3 Measure description

6.3.1 Challenges in relation to GEMINI

In Rudersdal, transportation accounts for approximately one third (29%) of the total CO₂ emissions, the majority of which come from passenger cars. The car is the preferred transport mode for the vast majority of citizens. It is used to and from work and between destinations within the municipal boundaries, e.g. to and from leisure activities.

Good transportation habits, including the use of public transport, bicycles, electric cars and sharing mobility can reduce fossil fuel consumption. Changing transportation habits and vehicles can also reduce noise and promote health among Rudersdal's citizens, as well as support a strong social cohesion and sense of local belonging. These aspects are considered critical by Rudersdal municipality. In the DK2020 project, there is a fixed framework for the development of a climate action plan by all Danish municipalities, to support the objectives of the Paris Agreement by committing to be carbon neutral by 2050. For that, Rudersdal's local strategy has consolidated three scopes³²:

1. reducing direct CO₂ emissions from energy consumption in buildings, transport and industry
2. reducing indirect CO₂ emissions from the energy consumed in Rudersdal from e.g. the power plant or heating plant
3. reducing CO₂ emissions associated with the production of goods and services outside Rudersdal

6.3.2 General description

The MLL will investigate the conditions on how NMS can help expand the PT network and/or improve access to the PT network in a peri-urban context. Therefore, multimodal hubs will be created offering at least 3 different shared mobility options: shared e-scooters, shared e-bikes

³² <https://rudersdal.dk/sites/rudersdal.dk/files/2023-05/Rudersdal%20Kommune%20klimahandlingsplan.pdf>

and car-sharing. An expected number of six locations in Rudersdal will be selected based on knowledge of the current movement patterns in the municipality, so that mobility hubs can be positioned to close the gaps in the PT network and increase PT utilization.

Shared cars can be used either as the “first car” for individuals/family who do not own a private vehicle, or act as a “second car” for a few hours a week. Shared bikes and shared e-scooters can serve short range trips from the local mobility hub. The mobility hub will act as a common reference for ride share pick up locations.

The solutions developed in the MLL will be tailored to the needs of the local community, identifying the structure, governance, and business model for a broad roll-out of the concept in similar peri-urban environments (a scalable mobility hub plan). The mobility hubs are meant to provide the citizens of Rudersdal with a safer, more effective, efficient, comfortable and pleasant experience of using alternative transport modes.

6.3.3 Output

- Implementation and a 12-month runtime of an expected number of 6 mobility hubs with at least 3 different shared mobility options (e-scooter, e-bike and car-sharing).
- A scalable mobility hub plan that can be used to implement similar projects in other parts of the region or in other regions.

6.4 Test area and target groups

Test area: Rudersdal Municipality, located approx. 20 km north of Copenhagen

FIGURE 31: Rudersdal municipality

TABLE 17: Target groups of the Copenhagen MLL

Target group	Description
Commuters, visitors and citizens of Rudersdal municipality	<p>Commuters from Rudersdal and other parts of the Capital Region of Denmark</p> <p>Visitors Rudersdal (leisure, tourism)</p> <p>Various groups of adult citizens from different types of households in Rudersdal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Living in dense areas with apartment • Living in single house neighbourhoods

Target group	Description
	<p>Divided in the sub-target groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youngsters: Young people, especially those without a car or those who prefer more sustainable transport options, may be motivated to use shared mobility services as a practical and cost-effective alternative to owning their own vehicle. • Commuters: Commuters who need to get to and from work or public transportation may find shared mobility services a flexible solution, especially if they don't need to use a car all the time. • Seniors: Retired people who may no longer wish to drive or own a car can benefit from shared mobility services as a supplement to public transport or to meet their transport needs in a more flexible way. • Business travellers: Business travellers staying in the area temporarily may find shared mobility services a convenient way to get around during their stay without having to rent a car or rely on public transportation. • Tourists: Tourists visiting the area may find shared mobility services a convenient way to explore the city, especially if they want to avoid having to drive or navigate public transportation. • Environmentally conscious citizens: Citizens who value sustainability and want to reduce their environmental impact may be motivated to use shared mobility services as a greener alternative to driving their own car.
Commuters to business areas	<p>Commuters to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DTU Science Park • small business area named Blokken

6.5 Impact evaluation

6.5.1 City context indicators

TABLE 18: Copenhagen city context indicators and data sources

#	Indicator	Sources
1	Modal split	Danish National Travel Survey
2	Number of road crashes	Danmark Statistik
3	Number of seriously injured	
4	Number of road deaths	
5	Density of shared mobility services	Data from partner shared mobility providers
6	Availability of shared mobility services	Data from partner shared mobility providers
7	Availability MaaS	REGH www.rejseplanen.dk
8	Car ownership	Danish National Travel Survey
9	Congestion levels	Floating car data
10	Quality of cycling network	Mobilitetsredegørelse 2023
11	Public transport usage	https://passagertal.dk

6.5.2 Impact indicators

TABLE 19: Objectives and selected impact indicators to monitor these objectives in the Copenhagen MLL

Impact indicators					
#	Objective/Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Reduction of congestion	Average vehicle speed (peak/off-peak)	Car traffic data	start & end project	MLL area Rudersdal
2	Increase share of NMS in the modal distribution	Modal share NMS in modal split visitors	DTU survey		Citizens Rudersdal
3	Reduction of road risk	Number of collisions per mode	Danmark Statistik		MLL area
4	Reduced car ownership	Car ownership	DTU survey		
5	Increased usage PT	Number of passengers % increased per multimodal hub	DTU survey + Rejsekort Data		
6	Improved awareness of NMS	Awareness of other/new mobility options	DTU survey		
7	Improved acceptance of NMS	Acceptance of other/new mobility options	DTU survey		
8	Reduction of traffic related air pollution	NO _x , PM emissions	XIPE model	end project	MLL area
9	Reduction of traffic related CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂ emissions	XIPE model	end project	MLL area

6.5.3 Additional indicators

TABLE 20: Additional indicators of the Copenhagen MLL

Additional indicators => NMS performance				
#	Indicator	Method/Source	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Number of vehicles per shared mode	Data from NMS provider	(intermediate &) end project	NMS/multimodal hub users
2	Number of users per shared mode			
3	Number of trips/week per shared mode			
4	Average trip distance per shared mode			
5	Number of trips/week per shared mode in combination with PT			
6	NMS user satisfaction			

Additional indicators => BM performance			
#	Indicator	Method/Source	Frequency
1	Investment costs	Data from REGH and NMS provider	end project
2	Operational costs		
3	Subsidisation		
4	Revenues		
5	No. jobs generated		

6.6 Process evaluation

6.6.1 Stakeholders involved

TABLE 21: Overview of the Copenhagen MLL partners and stakeholders involved, and their role

Stakeholders			
Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - O: Occasional participant			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
The Capital Region of Denmark (REGH)	Region	L	REGH will coordinate the MLL. It will create a roadmap for NMS in peri-urban environments
Rudersdal municipality	City	P	Rudersdal municipality is responsible for establishing the physical infrastructure and licensing for shared mobility actors. Identification of the Hubs. Implementing NMS and active modes; measure impact and share best practices.
Helsingborg municipality	City	P	Provide link between Danish and Swedish NMS to ease cross border mobility
Tier	Private company	P	Will provide 80 bikes and e-scooters to the pilots
Green Mobility	Private company	P	Green Mobility will provide no less than 20 cars to the pilot.
Kinto (Toyota)	Private company	P	Kinto will provide no less than 12 cars to the pilots and offer mobility services at and between mobility hubs.
Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU)	University	P	DTU will analyse data related to the MLL
DTU Science Park	University	O	One of the mobility hub will be located at DTU Science park.
Neighbouring Municipalities	Public sector	O	The idea of the scale up plan is to involve municipalities in Region Hovestaden to adapt the design of mobility hubs and the collaboration experience with the sharing providers (SLA)
Frivilgecenter Rudersdal	Volunteer organization	O	Local community about voluntary work in Rudersdal, to onboard new users for sharing service

Stakeholders			
<i>Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - O: Occasional participant</i>			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
Politicians	Public sector	O	Ensure that politicians support and approve the scale up plan, by demonstrating the success of the mobility living lab.

6.6.2 Supporting activities

- Communication campaign
- Safety workshops: workshops will be organised to instruct citizens of Rudersdal on how to safely use shared mobility

6.7 Timing evaluation activities

	2023							2024												2025												2026																		
	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov								
project month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42								
stages	DE							OP																																										
data collection																																																		
Car trips												B		Ix						Ix						R																								
Rejsekort												B													Ix													R												
TIER																							Ix						R																					
Kinto																							Ix						R																					
Green Mobility																							Ix						R																					
TU Survey												B																								R														
GEMINI reporting								D2.1					D3.1																		D3.10																			

FIGURE 32: Timing of the evaluation activities of the Copenhagen MLL

implementation phases

DE	development phase
OP	operational phase

data collection impact and intermediate indicators

B	baseline data
Bs	survey - baseline data
Ix	intermediate data
Ixs	survey - intermediate data
R	result data
Rs	survey - result data

reporting

D2.1	GEMINI evaluation plan
D3.1	Interim progress report of MLLs implementation
D3.10	Final Impact Assessment of GEMINI NMS and MLLs

7 EVALUATION PLAN OF MLL 3 – MUNICH

7.1 Context

7.1.1 Geography and population city of Munich

Munich (München), is the capital of the Free State of Bavaria (Bayern), and the third largest city in Germany, after Berlin and Hamburg, with almost 1.6 million inhabitants (1 590 877 on 31/03/2024³³). An additional 360 000 people commute into the city on a daily basis.³⁴

Munich is known as one of the leading economic centres in Germany, with the lowest unemployment rates among major German cities for many years. In 2023, Munich's unemployment rate was only 4.1%.³⁵ With Germany's largest car companies BMW and Audi headquartered in Munich, the car plays a dominant role in the area and is a main form of transportation for many of Munich's citizens. Nevertheless, Munich has a well-established public transport network, and the importance of cycling has risen significantly in the last two decades (European Mobility Venture, 2021).

With rising population figures in the Munich area, and the road and public transport network reaching its full capacity, the city and surrounding areas face important mobility challenges.

FIGURE 33: The city of München, Münchener Umland and the Metropolregion München in the state of Bayern.
(Source: [Wikipedia](https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/München))

FIGURE 34: MVV-Verbundraum in 2015 and at the end of 2023.
(Source: [Wikipedia](https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/MVV))

FIGURE 33 and FIGURE 34 visualise the Free State of Bavaria, with its capital city Munich, the Munich region (Münchener Umland), the MVV-network area (Münchener Verkehrs- und Tarifverbund (MVV)-Verbundraum)³⁶ and the Munich metropolitan region (Metropolregion München).

³³ <https://stadt.muenchen.de/infos/statistik-bevoelkerung.html>

³⁴ <https://handshakecycling.eu/munich>

³⁵ <https://www.wirtschaft-muenchen.de/produkt/munich-fact-sheet/>

³⁶ Munich Transport and Tariff Association (Münchener Verkehrs- und Tarifverbund)

The MVV-network area includes the city of Munich and the districts of the Munich region and has around 2.9 million inhabitants. The public transport association MVV unites over 40 transport companies together under the motto "one network, one schedule, one ticket". MVV oversees transportation and fare coordination for Munich and its surrounding areas, including the Munich S-Bahn commuter trains, the Munich U-Bahn, the Munich tramway, and buses. It is responsible amongst other things for establishing a unified tariffs and fares structure, revenue distribution, planning, and providing customer information across various transport companies.³⁷

7.1.2 Modal share Munich

Every 5 years, a household survey is held in Germany, Mobilität in Deutschland (MiD), giving details on the travel behaviour in Germany and its different regions and cities.³⁸ The last household survey was held in 2017 (MiD 2017). These results are presented here, i.e. the modal share and car and bike ownership in Munich and its surrounding areas, from the 2 publications Kurzreport Stadt München, Münchner Umland und MVV-Verbundraum (Follmer & Belz, 2018) and Regionalbericht Stadt München, Münchner Umland und MVV-Verbundraum (Belz et al., 2020).

FIGURE 35: Modal share Munich residents for the years 2002, 2008 and 2017. (* stands for restricted time comparison. Source: Follmer & Belz (2018): MiD 2017.)

FIGURE 35 presents the modal share in the city of Munich over recent years. Since 2002, there has been an increased number of trips with public transport or cycling by Munich residents. The share of trips done cycling in Munich grew between 2002 and 2017 from 10% to 18%. The share of public transport trips increased from 21% in 2002 to 24% in 2017. The share of trips made by Munich residents by walking has decreased to 24% in 2017.

³⁷ https://www.mvv-muenchen.de/fileadmin/mediapool/07-Ueber_den_MVV/02-Dokumente/Infofolder_MVV_160513_en.pdf

³⁸ <https://www.mobilitaet-in-deutschland.de/>

The share of car trips decreased over the years from 41% in 2002 to 34% in 2017. Despite a decrease in the share of trips done by car, the total number of daily passenger kilometres travelled by motorised vehicles in Munich has increased from approximately 28 million in 2008 to around 33 million. This increase is due to population growth and slightly longer average journeys. Consequently, the burden imposed by car usage is actually rising. If commuter journeys for work or other purposes are also taken into account, this burden will be even higher. (Follmer & Belz, 2018)

7.1.3 Car and bike ownership Munich

In 2017, 56% of the households in Munich were in the possession of one or more private cars (see FIGURE 36). This means that more than 4 out of 10 urban households in Munich are car-free. In comparison, in Germany overall, in 2017, 77% of the households was in the possession of at least 1 car in 2017, and 83% of the households in Munich region. (Belz et al., 2020)

The MiD household survey of 2017 also shows that young adults today are less car-orientated than their peers in previous years. This is reflected in slightly declining driving licence ownership rates. Among senior citizens, car ownership is growing, especially in the highest age groups. This is mainly due to older women who are more often behind the wheel themselves and more often own a car. (Follmer & Belz, 2018)

FIGURE 36: Car ownership for 1, 2 3 or more cars per household (left) and bike ownership (right) in the city of Munich (Stadt München), Munich region (Münchner Umland) and the MVV-network area (MVV-Verbundraum) in 2017.

(Source: Follmer & Belz (2018); MiD 2017.)

Bike ownership is high in the city of Munich, with 83% of the households in 2017 being in the possession of a pedal bike, e-bike or speed-pedelec (FIGURE 36). The percentage of e-bike or speed-pedelecs was in 2017 however below 5%. With the recent boost in popularity of electric cars the current numbers might be a lot higher. The highest bicycle ownership rate is among children and youth below 17 years. (Follmer & Belz, 2018)

7.1.4 Shared mobility Munich

FIGURE 37 gives an overview of the available multimodal hubs (Mobilitätspunkte) in Munich, with detailed information of the number of car-sharing spots, whether it includes a Munich city MVG bikes-sharing station and bike service station, etc.

FIGURE 37: Multimodal hubs in the city of Munich with details on available (shared) mobility services.
(Source: <https://muenchenunterwegs.de/angebote/verkehrsmittel/sharing>)

As in many other cities, shared mobility has increased in popularity in Munich over recent years. The shared mobility offer is nevertheless volatile. Munich city provides information on the available shared mobility providers on a dedicated website. The following shared mobility providers are in 2024 operational in Munich city³⁹:

- 7 car-sharing providers: Flinkster, FreeNow, Miles, Scouter Carsharing, ShareNow, Sixt share and Stattauto
- 6 bikes-sharing providers: Call a Bike (the nationwide bike-sharing service of the German national railway company Deutsche Bahn), List'n'Ride, MVG Rad (bike-sharing in Munich city and region), Shigo, Swapfiets and Tier
- 5 e-scooter providers: Bolt, FreeNow, lime, Tier, Voi

Car-sharing

MiD 2017 presents some statistics on the percentage of households in Munich with memberships to a car-sharing provider. In 2017, in Munich city, 21% of the households were in the possession of one or more memberships to a car-sharing provider. Within the Inner Ring (Mittlerer Ring) of Munich this percentage rises to 29%. Nevertheless usage is low, around 7 out of 10 car-sharing members use it rarely in everyday life or never return to this offer. (Follmer & Belz, 2018)

³⁹ <https://muenchenunterwegs.de/mobilitaetsanbieter> (accessed in 04/2024)

Bike-sharing and shared e-scooters

The Munich public transport operator (Münchner Verkehrsgesellschaft, MVG) operates the bike-sharing service MVG Rad in Munich city and its surrounding area, since 2015. FIGURE 38 presents the latest statistics of MVG Rad. In 2023, 4 500 bikes were available at over 186 stations, with more than 700 000 rentals that year.

The Munich City Council recently decided for MVG Rad to be phased out in 2025. A new regional bike-sharing system will take its place. The new system will include 5 200 bicycles (of which 3 200 pedal bikes and 2 000 e-bikes) and will be available at over 675 stations in the city.⁴⁰

FIGURE 38: MVG rad bike-sharing statistics for 2023.
(Source: [MVG Mobility in figures, 2023.](#))

Sellaouti et al. (2024) recently published a study on the evolution and characteristics of shared e-scooters usage in Munich. FIGURE 39 shows the monthly number of e-scooter trips in Munich city for the years 2019, 2020, and 2021. The black curve represents the number of trips taken with the MVG Rad shared bikes in both Munich city and the suburban areas.

Since the introduction of shared e-scooters in Munich in 2019, the number of e-scooter rides has been steadily increasing each year, with clear peaks of e-scooter usage in the summer months. The usage rates are higher than for the MVG Rad shared bikes, but it needs to be considered that other shared bike provides are operational in Munich.

⁴⁰ <https://www.mvg.de/services/mvg-rad.html>

FIGURE 39: Number of e-scooter rides in Munich city for each month, in 2019-2021.
(Source: Sellaouti et al. (2024).)

7.2 Objectives

Environmental:

- The city of Munich aims to reduce at least 80% of traffic within the city, with emission-free mobility by 2035 (Mobilitätsstrategie 2035)
- Modal shift visitors Allianz Arena to more sustainable trips during game days
- Improved air quality thanks to modal shift fans
- Reduced greenhouse gas emissions thanks to modal shift fans

Economic:

- Reduce car traffic by 10 – 20% to/from Allianz Arena during game days
- Reduce travel times of car users by 15-20% in game days

Other: The city of Munich aims to shape the local setup together with private shared mobility companies (Mobilitätsstrategie 2035)

7.3 Measure description

7.3.1 Challenges in relation to GEMINI

During sports or other major events, the wider area around Allianz Arena gets very congested and the transport network collapses. There have been observed delays of 2-3 hours for both car and PT users. The PT network is also overloaded during sports events (e.g. underground U6) as the high demand surpasses the capacity of the system. Another major challenge is the congestion in the parking lots in and around the stadium, causing long waiting times. Currently in this specific area, there are no micromobility services available, however the fans can use other share mobility options such as 'Drive-Now', Uber, Free Now, Share Now, SIXT share etc.

7.3.2 General description

The Munich MLL aims to 1) provide easier access to the Allianz Arena stadium with the creation of park-and-ride micromobility options for fans during the 'last-mile' of their trip to/from Allianz Arena for both car and PT users, and 2) reduce congestion and delays by employing traffic and parking management measures around the stadium.

To enable this, the MLL will:

- Develop new **strategies** for the optimization of traffic congestion in the area, based on **traffic model simulations**.
- Introduce a **parking facility** close to Allianz Arena to accommodate **shuttle buses and/or new micromobility services** for fans during the last-mile of their trip to/from Allianz Arena.
- Develop and test new **pricing strategies** in the (existing and new) parking areas.
- Develop a **white label data driven app or an API/web service** which can be used by the fans or Allianz arena visitors through the FC Bayern App/Allianz arena app. This app/API/web service interfaces with mobility providers and can provide combined incentive packages (event ticket, parking, shared mobility services).

The Allianz Arena has a traffic control centre and is an active partner in the living lab. Based on the results of the traffic simulations a strategy will be defined in close collaboration with the Allianz Arena. Different business cases/models will be suggested to attract new mobility providers to provide new NMS.

7.3.3 Output

- Combined pricing and traffic management strategies to optimise traffic flows during large events, based on traffic model simulations
- An improved parking management system at the Allianz Arena parking, possibly reorganization of area opening times, driving directions and rules
- A new parking area close to the Allianz Arena with last-mile options for the visitors of the arena
- 1-2 new mobility providers implementing new business cases/models at the new parking area and at the surrounding area of the stadium
- A white label data driven app or an API/web interface with incentive packages coupled to the FC Bayern App/Allianz arena app

7.4 Test area and target groups

FIGURE 40: Allianz arena, located at the North-East of Munich city. (Source: [Google Maps](#))

FIGURE 41: Floor plan of the Allianz Area.

Test area: The wider Munich city area around the Allianz Arena will be considered during sport and other major events.

TABLE 22: Target groups of the Munich MLL

Target group	Description
Visitors of the arena	Supporters/visitors travelling to the Allianz arena, with a specific focus on the visitors currently coming by car. The following sub-target groups are considered: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Families or groups travelling by car Families or groups travelling by PT (i.e. metro) Visitors travelling individually by car Visitors travelling individually by PT (i.e. metro)
Commuters' or other users' trips in the area	Car commuters in the area of the Allianz Arena before the start of the game. Traffic flows provided by HERE technologies will not be limited to fans' data.
Residents in the area	Residents living and parking their car in the area of the Allianz Arena.

7.5 Impact evaluation

7.5.1 City context indicators

TABLE 23: Munich city context indicators and data sources

#	Indicator	Sources
1	Modal split	Mobilität in Deutschland, Regionalbericht Stadt München, 2020
2	Number of road crashes	Verkehrsunfallbilanz Polizeipräsidium München
3	Number of seriously injured	
4	Number of road deaths	
5	Density of shared mobility services	Statista Research Department data
6	Availability of shared mobility services	
7	Availability MaaS	MVGO
8	Car ownership	- Mobilität in Deutschland, Regionalbericht Stadt München, 2020 - Mobilität in Deutschland, Kurzreport Stadt München, Münchner Umland, 2019
9	Congestion levels	- INRIX Traffic Scorecard - TomTom traffic report Munich
10	Quality of cycling network	Munich Bikeability Index - a practical approach

7.5.2 Impact indicators

TABLE 24: Objectives and selected impact indicators to monitor these objectives in the Munich MLL

Impact indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Reduced traffic congestion	-Average vehicle speed (peak/off-peak) -Time travelled from areas A-D to Allianz Arena	Floating car data Bluetooth ANPR camera data	start & end project	visitors Allianz Arena
2	Increase share of NMS in the modal distribution	Modal share NMS in modal split visitors Allianz Arena	Survey		
3	Reduction of road risk	-Number of collisions per mode -Number of fatalities, serious and light injuries per mode	Police data, hospital data, own registration		Parkings Allianz Arena
4	Improved parking management	No. of cars entering parking /15min	Countings		
5	Improved accessibility PT	No. of new PT parking facilities and stops introduced in the pilot	Countings		
6	Improved awareness of NMS	Awareness of other/new mobility options	Survey and Allianz Arena app		visitors Allianz Arena
7	Improved acceptance of NMS	Acceptance of other/new mobility options	Survey		
8	Reduction of traffic related air pollution	NO _x PM emissions	-Calculated based on reduced car-vkm from traffic simulations - XIPE model	end project	MLL area
9	Reduction of traffic related CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂ emissions			

7.5.3 Additional indicators

TABLE 25: Additional indicators of the Munich MLL

Additional indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Improved parking management	Waiting time parking gate	Countings	(intermediate &) end project	Car users
2	Reduce delays/ travel time inside the parkings	Traffic flow data inside the parking from Allianz	Traffic flow data inside the parking from Allianz		
3	More efficient use of the car	Car occupancy	Counting of occupancy of cars entering parkings		

Additional indicators => NMS performance				
#	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Number of vehicles per shared mode	Data from NMS provider	(intermediate &) end project	MLL area
2	Number of users per shared mode			
3	Number of trips/week (per game?) per shared mode			
4	Average trip distance per shared mode			
6	Travel behaviour before and after use shared mode	Survey	(intermediate &) end project	NMS/multi modal hub users
7	NMS user satisfaction			
Additional indicators => BM performance				
#	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Investment costs	FC Bayern + NMS mobility operators	end project	business model
2	Operational costs			
3	Subsidisation			
4	Revenues			
5	No. jobs generated			

7.6 Process evaluation

7.6.1 Stakeholders involved

TABLE 26: Overview of the Munich MLL partners and stakeholders involved, and their role

Stakeholders			
Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - O: Occasional participant			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
VW AG	Private company	L	VW AG coordinates the Mobility Living Lab and does different analyses and developments. VW AG will do traffic simulations and analytics, develop data driven strategies to optimise the traffic congestion including concepts/business models for NMS and develop the white-label app.
ALLIANZ	Private company	P	The venue owner Allianz will accommodate the new strategies and business model scenarios and perform an Allianz app upgrade.
VMZ Siemens, AIM, YUNEX	Private company	P	VMZ Siemens and YUNEX are the technology providers responsible for the software solution for traffic management and parking infrastructure.

Stakeholders			
<i>Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - O: Occasional participant</i>			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
ATOM	Private company	P	The micromobility platform operator ATOM will provide support in the deployment of e-bikes, e-scooters and micromobility data collection.
City of Munich	City	O	The city has a validation role.

7.6.2 Supporting activities

- Survey to fans through the Allianz Arena & FC Bayern app and website, and live at the Allianz Arena
- Cooperation with the GEMINI MLL Porto, envisioning also a common methodology or framework for large attraction sites
- Workshops and focus groups, aimed at bringing and addressing the requirements of all involved parties and stakeholders, such as the city of Munich, the Munich Public Transport Operator, Allianz Arena, and other mobility providers in line with the Munich Mobility and City Plans.

7.7 Timing evaluation activities

FIGURE 42: Timing of the evaluation activities of the Munich MLL

implementation phases

DE	development phase
IM	implementation phase
OP	operational phase

data collection impact and intermediate indicators

B	baseline data
Bs	survey - baseline data
Is	survey - intermediate data
R	result data

reporting

D2.1	GEMINI evaluation plan
D3.1	Interim progress report of MLLs implementation
D3.10	Final Impact Assessment of GEMINI NMS and MLLs

8 EVALUATION PLAN OF MLL 4 - TURIN

8.1 Context

8.1.1 Geography and population Turin

The city of Turin, located in the northwest of Italy, is the capital of the Piedmont region (Piemonte). It holds a strategic position due to its proximity to France and its location between Milan and Genoa. As a result, Turin serves as a vital transit hub for the movement of people and goods between Italy and France.⁴¹

FIGURE 43: Piedmont region (red) in Italy (left), city of Turin, Metropolitan City of Turin and Piedmont region (right).
(Sources: [Wikipedia](#) and [Wikimedia Commons](#))

FIGURE 43 visualises the Piedmont region in Italy, the Metropolitan City of Turin and Turin city. Based on the latest ISTAT data of 2011⁴², Turin has a population of 850 053 inhabitants and ranks as the fourth-largest city in Italy by population. The Metropolitan City of Turin counts more than 2 million inhabitants (2 238 663), of which 68.34% are over 35 years of age (Caballini et al., 2023). The Piedmont region has a population of more than 4 million inhabitants (4 363 916).

In July 2022, the SUMP of the Metropolitan City of Turin was approved. Its objectives include enhancing accessibility, improving liveability and road safety, and achieving environmental and energy sustainability within the transportation sector, supported by technological innovation.⁴¹

⁴¹ https://urban-mobility-observatory.transport.ec.europa.eu/resources/case-studies/harmony-application-transport-modelling-turin_en

⁴² <http://dati-censimentopopolazione.istat.it/Index.aspx?lang=en>

8.1.2 Modal share Turin

FIGURE 44: Modal share in Piedmont in 2004, 2013 and 2022.
 (Source: [Mobility survey Piedmont, 2022](#))

FIGURE 44 presents the evolution of the modal share of daily trips in the Piedmont region. The majority of trips are done by car, and this share has even increased the last 14 years, from 62% to 66%. The percentage of trips done walking or cycling has remained roughly stable over the years, with a share of 27%. A small percentage of trips is done by PT, and this share has decreased from 10% in 2004 and 2013 to 6% in 2022.

As can be expected, in the city of Turin, a higher share of daily trips are done walking, cycling or by PT, than in the Piedmont region, as shown in FIGURE 45. In the city, in 2022, 48% of the trips were done by car, 41% by walking or cycling, and 12% by PT.

FIGURE 45: Modal share city of Turin, 2022.
 (Source: [Mobility survey Piedmont, 2022](#))

8.1.3 Car ownership Turin

According to ISTAT⁴³, in 2022, 512 687 passenger cars were registered in the city of Turin. For a population of 850 053 inhabitants, this corresponds to a high car ownership rate of 603 cars per 1000 inhabitants.

8.1.4 Shared mobility Turin

Car-sharing

Since 2015, 3 car-sharing providers are active in the city of Turin:

- 2 free floating: Drive Now and Enjoy
- 1 station-based: Blue Torino

In 2019, 1 140 car-sharing vehicles were available across Turin. Since the start in 2015, the number of users grew steadily from 51 000 in 2015 to 209 000 in 2019. The number of annual rentals increased from 484 000 in 2015 to 1.7 million in 2019, just as the mileage increased from 2.3 million kilometres in 2015, to 9.3 million kilometres in 2019.⁴⁴

Bike-sharing, shared e-scooters and shared mopeds

Several bike-sharing, moped-sharing and e-scooter sharing providers are active in Turin⁴⁵:

- 6 **shared moped** operators, each having 500 mopeds distributed across Turin: Helbitz, Bit, Bird, Circ, Dott, Lime (see FIGURE 46)
- 2 **bike-sharing** operators: Movi by Mobike and ToBike, operating together 3 030 shared bikes in the city of Turin.
- 1 **shared e-scooter** provider: Mimoto, operating 250 e-scooters across Turin.

MONOPATTINI IN SHARING - Operatori e unità attive - settembre 2020						
Helbiz	Bit	Bird	Circ	Dott	Lime	TOT
500	500	500	500	500	500	3.000

FIGURE 46: Number of shared mopeds available in Turin in 2020.

(Source: [PUMS Torino Metropoli, Allegato E](#))

In addition, outside the urban area of Turin, the Bicincittà bike-sharing service is active in 3 municipalities:

- Chivasso: with 12 stations
- Pinerolo: with 8 stations
- Rivarolo Canavese: with 3 stations

FIGURE 47 presents a map of the bike-sharing stations operational in Turin and its surrounding area and TABLE 27 summarises the 2019 statistics of the 2 bike-sharing operators operational in the city of Turin.

⁴³ <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx?lang=en&SubSessionId=d8dd4061-c95c-45f8-8061-7fbb51016790>

⁴⁴ [Traffico automobilistico e sosta \(cittametropolitana.torino.it\)](#)

⁴⁵ [PUMS Torino Metropoli, Allegato E](#)

Movi by Mobike is a free-floating system with 1 770 bikes available, ToBike is a station-based system operating 1 330 shared bikes. The free-floating system Movi by Mobike has a higher coverage (43 bikes /m²), more registered users and a higher number of yearly rentals than the station-based ToBike system. However, more kilometres are driven with the station-based system, 2.6 times more than with the free-floating system.

FIGURE 47: Bike-sharing options in the city of Turin and its surrounding area.
(Source: bikesharingworldmap.com)

TABLE 27: Statistics bike-sharing operators in Turin, 2019.

	Type	No. of bikes	No. of registered users	No. of rentals	Mileage (km)	No. of bikes/m ²	No. of bikes/1000 inhabitants
Movi by Mobike	Free-floating	1 700	84 334	1 377 525	1 556 603	43	1.9
ToBike	Station-based	1 330	10 863	934 556	4 098 909	10	1.5

Source: [PUMS Torino Metropoli, Allegato E](#)

8.2 Objectives

Environmental:

- Reduced car use and car ownership, coupled with a decrease in CO₂ emissions from private vehicles.
- Increased share of multimodal trips and the fostering of a positive attitude towards public transport and non-motorized solutions.
- Decreased individual travel time through improved transport efficiency.

Societal:

- Generating eco-responsive behaviour and generating behavioural change to sustainable travel (via MaaS product bundles).
- Addition of alternative transport modes for better connections to/from peri-urban and rural areas.
- Increased accessibility to transport services (including NMS) for a large group of users.

Economic:

- Generating collaboration/new partnerships as key agreements among transport and mobility players will enable the conditions for including a wide range of providers and operators to be part of the MaaS offer.
- Increased customer base for NMS providers given a shift from private cars to other modes of transport, including public transport, car sharing, taxi, etc.

8.3 Measure description

8.3.1 Challenges in relation to GEMINI

In the territory of the Piedmont Region the population and economic activities are concentrated in the metropolitan area of Turin. This phenomenon generates high volumes of traffic and commuting flows, especially by private cars, and creates disparities with the peripheral and mountain areas, which suffer from depopulation and lack of services.

This results in a high levels of car ownership and use. Piedmont has one of the highest rates in Italy, with over 70% of households owning a car. This reliance on cars contributes to traffic congestion, air pollution, and noise pollution, also because of a relatively underdeveloped public transportation system that makes it difficult for many people to live without a car, especially in rural areas. However, the whole region is investing in new bus services, trams and subway lines, as well as in the creation of new bike lanes, pedestrian walkways, cycle lanes and it is expanding existing services and adding new mobility services. Since 2018 knowledge and pilot-based experience with Mobility as a Service (MaaS) has been acquired, also thanks to several projects on this topic, funded either nationally or at EU level, including H2020 Imove project and the National Mobility Vouchers and BIPforMaaS project.

During these pilot-based experiences hundreds of users were enabled to use MaaS mobile apps to book and pay for taxi services, shared e-scooters, bikes and mopeds and also train travel. As a result, the shared mobility market on the territory of the city of Turin, the regional capital, evolved to include at present 4 operators of bike-sharing (free floating), 7 operators of e-scooter sharing and 2 operators of mopeds, proving that the territory and the citizens are mature users of these new mobility services.

At present, single-ticket multimodal travel is not an option yet but, thanks to a Memorandum of Understanding signed in 2019 by all public entities of Piedmont (municipality of Turin, Piedmont region, metropolitan city of Turin, mobility agency, 5T), a common path was defined towards the development of a MaaS ecosystem in Turin and Piedmont.

8.3.2 General description

The Turin MLL builds on the MaaS concept to incentivise a modal shift from private cars to alternative modes, especially during off-peak periods, when the current transportation supply is insufficient to fully meet the needs of user groups. The measure is twofold:

1. Business-to-business use case (B2B): A business community will be established, including different mobility providers and tourism operators, associations and users. The aim is to

facilitate a participatory process through which local communities are directly engaged in the co-design of an innovative holistic service catering for the needs of citizens and tourists alike.

2. Business-to-customer use case (B2C): A MaaS platform facilitating booking and payment of multimodal trips of the different available mobility providers, mainly from the Piedmont region. The platform will be tested with real users to prove the viability of this solution.

The Turin MLL aims at meeting travellers' individual transportation needs through a single interface providing a holistic mobility service covering urban, peri-urban, suburban, and rural areas in Turin and Piedmont region, allowing also for cross-regional/cross-border trips to/from the neighbouring geographical cities and regions through the implementation of an integrated MaaS business model scheme.

8.3.3 Output

- A business community including different mobility and tourism operators, associations and users involved in co-designing a holistic service (B2B)
- A MaaS platform integrating mobility services of a range of providers, allowing trip booking and single-ticket multimodal travel (B2C use case)

8.4 Test area and target groups

Test area:

The target area of the MLL includes urban, peri-urban and rural areas in the city of Turin and Piedmont region.

It also allows for cross-border travel to France. Cross-border mobility scenarios will be implemented through the support of local transport operators and integration of their key services into the MaaS scheme. Particularly, a cross-border mobility scenario to connect Piedmont region to the Italian region of Aosta Valley and the French city of Courmayeur will be tested through the app by providing travellers with access to three interconnected local bus services, i.e. from Lampugnano, Turin to Aosta, operated by Arriva Italia; from Aosta to Courmayeur, also operated by Arriva Italia; and from Courmayeur to Chamonix in France, operated by the French company SAT in collaboration with Arriva Italia.

France – Aosta Valley – Piedmont Region – City of Turin

FIGURE 48: Turin MLL test areas

TABLE 28: Target groups of the Turin MLL

Target group	Description
Users	<p>The B2C pilot targets 5 main end-user groups, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commuters (e.g., workers with children, workers without children, students, daily commuters, occasional commuters, elderly commuters, disabled commuters, mobility restricted users) • Tourists (e.g., domestic, international, oversea, leisure tourists, adventure seekers, cultural tourists) • Businessmen (e.g., business travellers, bleisure, small business owners, corporate executives, conference attendees) • Healthcare facilities (e.g. patients and caregivers, medical staff, visitors to patients) • Venues, attractions and events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Type of venue/attraction/event (e.g., stadium, fair, sports events, theatre, festival, concert, attraction, monuments) ○ Staff of venue/attraction/event (e.g., concession stand and vendor staff, performer’s staff, team sport/player’s staff) ○ Attendees venue/attraction/event (e.g., VIP attendees, local residents, student groups, private car users, public transportation users, taxi users, pedestrian, private bicycle users)
Others	<p>The B2B pilot targets the following stakeholder groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisations (e.g., tourist agencies, policy makers, academia for co-creation initiatives, non-governmental organisations, local government agencies, event organisers) • Mobility providers (e.g., public transport operators, bike- and scooter-sharing providers, car-sharing and car rental operators, shuttle and bus services, taxi

Target group	Description
	and ride hailing operators) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourist agencies (e.g., inbound and outbound tour operators, online travel agencies, destination management companies) • Policy makers (e.g., local, regional, (inter)national authorities) • Academia for co-creation initiatives (e.g., research institutions, universities, innovation hubs, accelerators and incubators) • Local government agencies and bodies

8.5 Impact evaluation

8.5.1 City context indicators

TABLE 29: Turin city context indicators and data sources

#	Indicator	Sources
1	Modal split	IMQ 2022
2	Number of road crashes	- dati.istat.it - istat.it
3	Number of seriously injured	
4	Number of road deaths	
5	Density of shared mobility services	Provided by 5T
6	Availability of shared mobility services	-Monitoring of sharing mobility services in the territory of the municipality of Turin - Quarterly Report -Provided by 5T
7	Availability MaaS	Provided by 5T
8	Car ownership	- dati.piemonte.it - dati.istat.it
9	Congestion levels	-City of Turin traffic supervisor -Provided by 5T
10	Average combined cycling and pedestrian flows	Provided by 5T

8.5.2 Impact indicators

TABLE 30: Objectives and selected impact indicators to monitor these objectives in the Turin MLL

Impact indicators					
#	Objective/Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Reduction of congestion	- Total number of trips (overall and by user groups) - Total number of multimodal trips (overall and by user groups)	Logged trip data and baseline traveller survey	start & end project	MLL area
2	Increase share of NMS in the modal distribution	- Modal share by user group and overall (through data on number and type of services used in each trip) - Customer increase of shared mobility services (including PT and NMS, individually)	Logged trip data and baseline traveller survey		
3	Improved accessibility PT	- PT modal share - Share of NMS-PT multimodal trips - Travel time per individual (overall and by user groups) - Perceived level of satisfaction with NMS - Perceived accessibility to transport in general	Logged trip data, baseline traveller survey, concise in-app post-trip survey		
4	Improved acceptance of MaaS platform	Acceptance of MaaS platform (based on perception level of e.g. cost, convenience, reliability, improved journey information, environmental/health concerns)	Concise in-app post-trip survey		
5	Reduction of traffic related air pollution	NO _x , PM emissions	XIPE model	end project	
6	Reduction of traffic related CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂ emissions			

8.5.3 Additional indicators

TABLE 31: Additional indicators of the Turin MLL

Additional indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	User friendliness MaaS app	-Simple UX/UI and user registration and activations -Speed of the reservation and payment -Simplicity in using a MaaS Service	MaaS app Diagnostics	start & end project	MLL area
2	Certainty availability MaaS services	Number of contracted MaaS operators			

Additional indicators => NMS performance				
#	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Number of providers included in the MaaS app	Logged trip data	(start &) end project	Piedmont region
2	Number of MaaS app registered users			
3	Number trips/week per shared mobility service			
4	Number of tickets/week bought through the MaaS app			
5	Average trip distance per shared mode/multimodal trip			
6	Average satisfaction with the trips (no matter the MSP or the specific mobility service)	Easy and user-friendly in-app rating	Right after every trip	Users
7	Number of app downloads from the Apple and Google stores	Provided by Google Play Console and Apple App Store Connect	Quarterly	Users
Additional indicators => BM performance				
#	Indicator	Method/Source	Frequency	
1	Investment costs	Sum of investment costs during the start-up phase Sum of operational costs each year	Annually	
2	Operational costs			
3	Revenues	Sum of revenues in one year		
4	Profit & loss	Difference between revenues and costs in one year		
5	Profit & loss (in % on revenue)	Percentage of costs versus revenues in one year		
6	Progressive profit & loss (breakeven monitoring)	Progressive sum of annual profit & loss		

8.6 Process evaluation

8.6.1 Stakeholders involved

TABLE 32: Overview of the Turin MLL partners and stakeholders involved, and their role

Stakeholders			
Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - O: Occasional participant			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
TTS	Private company	L	TTS coordinates the Mobility Living Lab (MLL). TTS will additionally support in data collection and the impact assessment.
PLUS	Private company	P	PLUS is the MaaS provider. They will integrate a range of mobility services in their platform making sure they are easily accessible by end users to plan and execute their daily trips.
5T	Private company	P	5T represents the city. They will facilitate stakeholder involvement and support in data collection and the impact assessment.

Stakeholders			
<i>Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - O: Occasional participant</i>			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
Arriva IT	Private company	P	Arriva IT is the public transport operator in the Piedmont region. They will be involved in the co-design and execution of the MLL, via integration of their most relevant services in the MaaS platform.

8.6.2 Supporting activities

- Creation of a local business communities for co-creating a MaaS scheme
- Launch of a communication campaign for user recruitment and awareness
- Coaching activities for citizen engagement

8.6.3 Planned implementation phases

TABLE 33: Planned implementation phases of the Turin MLL

Planned implementation phases		
#	Phase	Milestone
1	Design & Test	Initiate by evaluating existing services and data, engaging with local businesses, and co-designing use cases to lay the foundation for the MaaS-oriented scheme.
2	Test	Secure necessary permits and launch awareness campaigns to prepare for user recruitment and testing, setting the stage for practical implementation.
3	Implementation & Operational	Activate citizen engagement through coaching and define metrics for evaluation, ensuring the community is ready and the impact can be measured.
4	Operational	Launch the operational platform, conducting real-world trials to gather user feedback and performance data.
5	Evaluation	Analyse collected data to evaluate the impact of MaaS on user behaviour and shared mobility uptake, using insights to refine and enhance the scheme.

8.7 Timing evaluation activities

	project month	2023							2024												2025												2026										
		Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42
1) Business-to-business use case (B2B)	phases	DE							OP																																		
	data collection																	B											Ix														
2) Business-to-customer use case (B2C)	phases	DE							OP																																		
	data collection																	B											Ix														
GEMINI reporting									D2.1					D3.1														D3.10															

FIGURE 49: Timing of the evaluation activities of the Turin MLL

implementation phases

DE	development phase
OP	operational phase

data collection impact and intermediate indicators

B	baseline data
Bs	survey - baseline data
Ix	intermediate data
Ixs	survey - intermediate data
R	result data
Rs	survey - result data

reporting

D2.1	GEMINI evaluation plan
D3.1	Interim progress report of MLLs implementation
33.10	Final Impact Assessment of GEMINI NMS and MLLs

9 EVALUATION PLAN OF TWINNING MLL 1 - PARIS-SACLAY

9.1 Context

9.1.1 Geography and population Paris

The Communauté d'agglomération Paris-Saclay (CPS), located in the Essonne department and the region Île-de-France, is a French inter-municipal structure (intercommunalités) that was established in 2016, as part of president Sarkozy's urban renewal plan. Paris-Saclay is located 20 km south of the city of Paris and comprises 27 municipalities. The area is a scientific and technological business cluster and includes research facilities, two major French universities along with higher education institutions (grandes écoles), as well as research and development centres of major companies. Paris-Saclay counted a population of 314 485 inhabitants in 2020, or 132 774 households.⁴⁶

FIGURE 50: Île-de-France region, with the Metropolis of Greater Paris (Métropole du Grand Paris) and Paris-Saclay to its south-west.

(Source: [Institut Paris region](https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/1405599?geo=EPCI-200056232))

FIGURE 50 shows the region of Île-de-France, and its 64 inter-municipal bodies (intercommunalités). These inter-municipal cooperations are able to implement policies in the fields of spatial planning, economic development and housing. The region Île-de-France

⁴⁶ <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/1405599?geo=EPCI-200056232>

consists of 8 departments: Paris, Seine-et-Marne, Yvelines, Hauts-de-Seine, Seine-Saint-Denis, Val-de-Marne, Val-d'Oise, as well as Paris-Saclay's department Essonne. The inhabitants of Île-de-France are called "Franciliens". In 2023, l'Île-de-France counted more than 12 million Franciliens (12 358 900), which represents 18.7% of the French population.⁴⁷

During Sarkozy's reforms in 2016, also the Metropolis of Greater Paris (Métropole du Grand Paris), known as Greater Paris, was established. Greater Paris includes 131 municipalities, comprising Paris and all 123 surrounding inner-suburban municipalities in the Petite Couronne departments (Hauts-de-Seine, Seine-Saint-Denis, and Val-de-Marne), as well as 7 municipalities in 2 outer-suburban departments (Val-d'Oise and Essonne). In 2020, Greater Paris counted more than 7 million people (7 086 619)⁴⁸ and the city of Paris more than 2 million inhabitants (2 145 906)⁴⁹.

9.1.2 Modal share Île-de-France and the city of Paris

FIGURE 51: Modal share inhabitants of Île-de-France (Franciliens; left), and inhabitants of Paris (right): by walking (marche) in grey, by car (voiture) in light blue, by PT (transport en commun) in red/orange, by bike (vélo) in green, by motorised 2-wheeler (2-roues motorisés) in pink, and by other modes (autres) in dark blue.

(Source: https://cdn.paris.fr/paris/2023/12/19/paris_ra2022-18-12-copie-web-ZmS8.pdf)

FIGURE 51 presents the modal share in the region of Île-de-France and Paris city. In 2020, before COVID-19, more than 41.5 million trips were made every day in the Île-de-France region, compared to just under 40.7 million in 2010. On average, a person living in Île-de-France makes 3.76 trips per day on weekdays (compared to 3.88 in 2010).

Walking has been, and remains, the main mode of transport in Île-de-France, with almost 41% of the trips done on foot in 2020, compared to just over 38% in 2010. In 2020, car journeys accounted for a third of all journeys (34%), a decline since 2010, when just under 38% of the trips were done by car. In 2020, almost 22% of the trips were done with PT, 2% cycling and 1.2% with a motorised 2-wheeler.

⁴⁷ <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/6968304>

⁴⁸ <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/2011101?geo=EPCI-200054781>

⁴⁹ <https://www.insee.fr/en/statistiques/serie/001760155>

The modal split of the inhabitants of Paris, moving around in the city, is different. Walking is still the main mode of transportation, with 60% of the trips in 2010 and 65% of the trips in Paris city done on foot in 2020. The second most popular mode of transport is public transport, with a modal share of 28% in 2010 and 26% in 2020, which represents a slight decline. Also the percentage of trips done by car has decreased from 2010 to 2020, from 7% to 4%. The percentage of trips done cycling remained stable, at 3%, although this number might have increased the last 4 years thanks to development of new cycling infrastructure, the expansion of bicycle parking solutions and other actions as part of the Plan Vélo 2021-2026⁵⁰, and the registered increase in the number of cyclists on the cycling lanes by 71% in 2022 compared to 2019⁵¹.

9.1.3 Car ownership Paris

FIGURE 52 presents the percentage of households in the region of Île-de-France, that is in the possession of at least one car, in 2019. Two out of three households (65.6%) in Île-de-France are in the possession of at least one car. In Paris city, this reduces to 33.5% of the households. In the “petite couronne”, 64.5% of the households are in the possession of at least one car. In the “grande couronne”⁵², 83.4% of the households are in the possession of at least one car.

FIGURE 52: Percentage of households in Île-de-France in the possession of at least one car, in 2019. (Source: [INSEE](#))

FIGURE 53: Evolution of purchases of new cars in France, as a function of fuel type. (Source: [APUR \(2022\)](#))

FIGURE 53 presents the evolution of new purchased cars at national level, in France, as a function of fuel type. Annual purchases of new cars have fluctuated since the 1980s between 1.71 million (lowest observed in 1997) and 2.26 million (peak observed in 2009), not counting 2020 when the number of new registrations fell to 1.63 million due to COVID-19.

The figure shows the decrease in diesel car purchases over the last ten years in France, from a share of 77% of new purchased cars in 2008 to 30% of new purchases in 2020. These diesel

⁵⁰ <https://cdn.paris.fr/paris/2021/12/08/2fc9cb8ad6db58b6bfde3e6ccfc4c48c.pdf>

⁵¹ <https://itdp.org/2024/04/02/2023-sta-paris-france-presents-a-bold-vision-for-historic-streets/>

⁵² The grande couronne is the area made up of the 4 departments: Seine-et-Marne, Yvelines, Essonne and Val-d'Oise.

cars are initially replaced by petrol cars (essence) and then cars driving on alternative energy. The percentage of petrol cars of new purchases has been rising steadily since 2008, from 22% to 58% in 2019, but decreasing again to 47% in 2020. In 2020, electric and hybrid cars represent 7% and 15% of new purchases respectively, compared to 2% and 6% in 2019. (APUR, 2020)

9.1.4 Shared mobility Paris

Car-sharing

In the region Île-de-France, 4 main car-sharing models are available:

- **Station-based** car-sharing, where the user picks up and returns the vehicle at the same location
- **Free-floating** car-sharing, where users can pick up and drop off the vehicle anywhere within a defined area
- **Peer-to-peer** car-sharing, where individuals rent their own vehicle via a platform. The user picks up the vehicle from the operator and returns it there
- **Company-based** car-sharing, where a fleet is shared (owned by the company or by an operator) within a company

Station-based car-sharing: In 2015, the city of Paris created the Shared Vehicle Service SVP, which was renamed Mobilib'. Mobilib' is run by several operators and includes offers for cars and commercial vehicles.

At the end of 2022, Mobilib' included⁵³:

- 4 operators: Communauto, Getaround, Ubeeqo and Clem'
- 408 stations, including 186 equipped with electric charging points
- 1 378 parking/pick-up spaces, including 934 for electric vehicles, hybrid or rechargeable hybrid vehicles

Free-floating car-sharing: At the end of 2022, 4 free-floating car-sharing providers were operational: Free2Moove, Sharenow, Zity and Communauto, with a maximum simultaneously authorised fleet of 1 757 electric vehicles.

Bike-sharing

The city of Paris' bike-sharing scheme Velib' was introduced in 2007, and was one of the first bike-sharing schemes worldwide.

FIGURE 54: Evolution of the number of rentals, 2018-2022 (left), and evolution of the percentage of electric Velib' bike rentals, and Velib' pedal-bike rentals (right).

(Source: https://cdn.paris.fr/paris/2023/12/19/paris_ra2022-18-12-copie-web-ZmS8.pdf)

⁵³ https://cdn.paris.fr/paris/2023/12/19/paris_ra2022-18-12-copie-web-ZmS8.pdf

In 2022, Velib' included 1 472 stations, spread over 450 km² and 61 municipalities.⁵⁴ With just under 42.1 million rentals of more than 3 minutes, the number of Velib' journeys increased by 13% compared to 2021.

In addition, 3 commercial bike-sharing providers are operational in Paris: Lime, Dott and Tier. In Paris-Saclay, the Zoov electric bikes-sharing scheme is available (see FIGURE 55).

Shared e-scooters

In 2023, Paris banned shared e-scooters in its city, after a referendum with almost 90% of people voting to ban them, although the turnout was only 7.5%. Therefore, since the referendum, the 15 000 e-scooters previously operated by Lime, Dott and Tier, were removed from the streets of Paris.⁵⁵

FIGURE 55: Zoov shared e-bike stations in Paris-Saclay.
(Source: [Zoov](#).)

In **Paris-Saclay**, only the Clem' station-based car-sharing provider, and the Zoov e-bike-sharing provider are operational.

9.2 Objectives

Environmental:

- Reducing the use of privately owned combustion engine vehicles by making shared electric cars available.
- Reduced greenhouse gas emissions thanks to reduced trips with combustion engine vehicles.

Societal:

Increased liveability in the Paris-Saclay area thanks to reduced car use and reduced number of cars parked on the street.

Economic:

Increased profitability of the business case of Clem' e-car-sharing in Paris-Saclay.

⁵⁴ <https://blog.velib-metropole.fr/velib-en-chiffres/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2023/aug/31/rented-e-scooters-cleared-from-paris-streets-on-eve-of-ban>

9.3 Measure description

9.3.1 Challenges in relation to GEMINI

Paris-Saclay is an area of 185 km² covering 27 communes. The population of the area has known a rapid increase, same with the number of dwellings. EPAPS, the Land Planning Public Authority of Paris-Saclay, oversees the urban planning with the mission of making it a scientific pole of excellence, a French “Silicon Valley”, by bringing higher education schools, universities, and research institutions from Paris to Université Paris-Saclay.

Paris-Saclay is characterized by a very active population with an overrepresentation of higher intellectual professions. The very high growth of very active population and jobs combined with a campus of students, public and private research facilities within the local area of the campus, within Paris-Saclay and between Paris-Saclay and the nearby areas (namely Paris), leads to a noticeable commuting practice which saturates the roads and RER B rail line. This in turn requires diverse, effective, and sustainable mobility solutions. The only heavy PT “crossing” in the area is RER B operated since 1977 (970 000 daily users) with a punctuality of around 84% (April 2022). RER B meets RER C and TGV in the Massy-Palaiseau station (13 620 167 travellers in 2019). A new automatic metro line of 35 km (Orly-Massy-Versailles) is expected to operate in 2026-2030, they will also be joined by the Tramway Express 12 by 2023.

This infrastructure is completed with bus lines. More than 60% of residents use the personal car to go to work compared to 26% using PT (2018 INSEE). This causes traffic jams in the 4 roads accessing Paris-Saclay (RN118, RD36, RD306, RD128) during rush hours especially in the exchange points. Roadworks are implemented in the “schema de transport 2018-2026” mobility plan to tackle this issue. One of the actions taken was to encourage electromobility through a dense infrastructure of charging stations and alternative modes like car-sharing.

Currently 2 shared mobility services are available in the area: 1) the Clem’ car-sharing provider and 2) Zoov shared bikes.

9.3.2 General description

The focus of this MLL will be on the co-creation of mobility offers, customised to the diverse needs of users. Clem’ is the only car-sharing and charging station operator in Paris-Saclay and operates a V2G powered car-sharing station exchanging energy with DrahiX building in Ecole Polytechnique as a demonstrator for a research program. Clem’s Platform and IoT devices can transform any car and charging station into a car-sharing station. The innovative solution allows any public or private entity to share a fleet and control the level of sharing. In this sense, cars from the Université Paris-Saclay and Ecole Polytechnique are included in the Clem’ car-sharing platform together with shared e-cars provided and operated by Clem’, available in the area.

The aim of this pilot is twofold:

1. to increase the profitability of the Clem’ Paris-Saclay business case by attracting more usage of the current e-car sharing in Paris-Saclay
2. to show the positive impact on the environment and local area of shared e-car/mobility services to convince authorities to expand the permit for operation

To enable this, GEMINI partners Clem’ and GoodMoovs will create an innovative set of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for connecting the applications and services of Clem’ and GoodMoovs. The platform will be based on commonly accepted, open and royalty free communication standards and protocols (comparable with what has been realized in the charging sector) and will build upon already commonly accepted APIs. Standardisation will result from the synergy between Clem’ and GoodMoovs, aiming to create a pan-European standard.

9.3.3 Output

- Integrated booking and payment platform for shared e-cars and the charging of private e-cars for GoodMoovs and Clem’ users
- Optimisation strategy for the location, availability and pricing of the shared Clem’ e-cars in Paris-Saclay

9.4 Test area and target groups

FIGURE 56: Paris-Saclay MLL test area.

TABLE 34: Target groups of the Paris-Saclay MLL

Target group	Description
Students	-Students residing in the Paris-Saclay area and using car-sharing for daily commute or buy groceries -Students not residing in the Paris-Saclay area and using car-sharing for spontaneous travels -Students who are travelling in the Paris-Saclay area -Mostly students from Central Supelec, IPP, Institut Polytechnique Paris, INSAE, ENS...)
Employees	-Employees of large institutions and companies -Employees of start-ups and SMEs -Researchers E.g., UPS employees, ENS employees, Servier institute, Thales R&D centre, EDF Lab, CPS and EPA
Inhabitants	-Families who use car-sharing to buy groceries -Residents who use car-sharing for daily commutes (to go to work, to get back from train station, ...) -Residents who use car-sharing for leisure -Residents who use car-sharing as a replacement of a 2 nd car when they need it

9.5 Impact evaluation

9.5.1 City context indicators

TABLE 35: Paris-Saclay city context indicators and data sources

#	Indicator	Sources
1	Modal split	- Paris - bilan des déplacements -Paris-Saclay data: CPS (t.b.c.)
2	Number of road crashes	- ONISR -Paris-Saclay data: CPS (t.b.c.)
3	Number of seriously injured	
4	Number of road deaths	
5	Density of shared mobility services	- Park-in-Saclay - Zoov.eu
6	Availability of shared mobility services	- Paris - bilan des déplacements - Institut Paris region -Paris-Saclay: Clem' car-sharing data
7	Availability MaaS	- Park-in-Saclay - Île-de-France mobilités
8	Car ownership	INSEE Paris-Saclay data: CPS (t.b.c.)
9	Congestion levels	- DIRIF circulation Ile-de-France -Monthly data RN118 and A12: DIRIF sytadin
10	Quality of cycling network	carto-velo.iledefrance-mobilites.fr

9.5.2 Impact indicators

TABLE 36: Objectives and selected impact indicators to monitor these objectives in the Paris-Saclay MLL

Impact indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Increased number of NMS trips	-Yearly number of trips in electric shared car and its evolution. - Number of 1 time user versus regular user	-Data provided by Clem' -Zoov data t.b.d.	start, (intermediate &) end project	MLL area
2	Reduction of road risk	Number of collisions per mode -Number of fatalities, serious and light injuries per mode	-Statistics Clem' -Police data, hospital data (through contact CPS) t.b.d.		
3	Improved accessibility PT-Clem' car-sharing as a first/last-mile solution	Survey questions such as: -Did you use the Clem' car in combination with another mode? -Did you use the Clem' car in combination with another mode?	Clem' survey		

Impact indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
4	Improved awareness of NMS	Awareness of other/new mobility options			Commuters & students Paris-Saclay
5	Improved acceptance of NMS	Acceptance of other/new mobility options'			MLL area
6	Improved social inclusion	Car-sharing available to (lower-income) students thanks to promotional activities Clem': evolution of the age of Clem' user subscriptions	Data provided by Clem'		
7	Reduction of traffic related air pollution	NO _x emissions	XIPE model	end project	
8	Reduction of traffic related CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂ emissions			

9.5.3 Additional indicators

TABLE 37: Additional indicators of the Paris-Saclay MLL

Additional indicators => NMS performance					
#	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group	
1	Number of vehicles per shared mode	-Data from NMS provider Clem' -Publicly available data from Zoov	(intermediate &) end project	MLL area	
2	Number of users per shared mode	-Clem' car-sharing usage data provided by Clem' -Zoov bike-sharing data: t.b.d.			
3	Number of trips/week per shared mode				
4	Average trip distance per shared mode				
5	Travel behaviour before and after use shared mode	Clem' survey		NMS/multimodal hub users	
6	NMS user satisfaction	Clem' survey			
Additional indicators => BM performance					
#	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group	
1	Investment costs	Provided by Clem'	end project	business model	
2	Operational costs				
3	Subsidisation				
4	Revenues				
5	No. jobs generated				

9.6 Process evaluation

9.6.1 Stakeholders involved

TABLE 38: Overview of the Paris-Saclay MLL partners and stakeholders involved, and their role

Stakeholders			
<i>Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - E: Evaluator/ knowledge institution - S: Supplier</i>			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
Clem'	Private company	MLL Leader	Developer of the MML car-sharing and Charge Point Operator (CPO) platform, setting up the hubs and operating the service.
GoodMoovs	Private company	e-mobility operator	Will provide his e-Mobility Service Provider (EMSP) services and try to connect it to the car-sharing operation in Paris-Saclay.
EPAPS, Energy4 Climate lab, Region, CPS	Public entity	Members GEMINI forum	Participants in the co-creation process, validation

9.6.2 Supporting activities

Dissemination activities at different events (Autonomy, European Mobility Week, etc.) including promotional activities to attract new users.

9.6.3 Planned implementation phases

TABLE 39: Planned implementation phases of the Paris-Saclay MLL

Planned implementation phases		
#	Phase	Milestone
1	Design	Choosing the relevant data to be studied along the project
2	Test	Testing of the technical interface with GoodMoovs
3	Implementation	Implementation of the technical exchange with GoodMoovs
4	Operational	Operational testing
5	Evaluation	Getting the data for end project reference

9.7 Timing evaluation activities

	2023							2024												2025												2026												
	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov		
project month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42		
phases	DE																			IM						OP																		
data collection								B						Bs						Ix		Isx						Ix		Isx														
GEMINI reporting																				D2.1												D3.1												

FIGURE 57: Timing of the evaluation activities of the Paris-Saclay MLL

implementation phases

DE	development phase
IM	implementation phase
OP	operational phase

data collection impact and intermediate indicators

B	baseline data
Bs	survey - baseline data
Ix	intermediate data
Isx	survey - intermediate data
R	result data
Rs	survey - result data

reporting

D2.1	GEMINI evaluation plan
D3.1	Interim progress report of MLLs implementation
D3.10	Final Impact Assessment of GEMINI NMS and MLLs

10 EVALUATION PLAN OF MLL TWINNING 2 - LJUBLJANA

10.1 Context

10.1.1 Geography and population Ljubljana

Ljubljana, the capital city of the Republic of Slovenia, is located in the centre of the country, along the Ljubljanica river. In 2023, the city registered almost 300 000 inhabitants (296 228)⁵⁶.

In 2007, Ljubljana city embraced its Vision 2025, aiming to transform the city into a sustainable and liveable urban environment.⁵⁷ A central aspect of this vision was the conversion of the city centre, predominantly characterised by motorised vehicles, into a pedestrian-friendly area, intended to appeal to both residents and visitors. To support this vision, in 2012, the city of Ljubljana introduced its Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP), which was updated in 2017, bringing measures forward to reverse the trend of increased private car use.⁵⁸

FIGURE 58: Ljubljana Urban region (LUR), including the city of Ljubljana.
(Source: [LUR SUMP, 2018](#))

Ljubljana is the economic century of the nation, almost a quarter of Slovenia's employed people work here.⁵⁹ This brings a large flow of commuters to the city, who mostly commute by car. Therefore, in 2018, Ljubljana Urban Region approved its first regional SUMP to deal with this challenge. The Ljubljana Urban Region (LUR) covers 26 municipalities and has approximately 550 000 inhabitants, see FIGURE 58.⁶⁰ In 2018, more than 120 000 people (55%) commuted on a daily basis to the city of Ljubljana from elsewhere (~25% from other municipalities of the LUR and 30% from the rest of Slovenia). In addition, approximately 22 500 employed persons commute to other municipalities (not the city of Ljubljana).⁶¹

⁵⁶ <https://gis.stat.si/#>

⁵⁷ <https://www.ljubljana.si/en/about-ljubljana/vision-of-ljubljana-2025/>

⁵⁸ http://transferproject.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/SUMP-Session-in-Ljubljana_Zdenka-Simonovic.pdf

⁵⁹ <https://civitas.eu/cities/ljubljana>

⁶⁰ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Ljubljanas-leap_PDF-1.pdf

⁶¹ <https://rralur.si/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/SUMP-LUR.pdf>

10.1.2 Modal share Ljubljana

FIGURE 59: Modal share of trips from the LUR to Ljubljana city (left), and the modal share of trips inside the city of Ljubljana (right) in 2013. MOL = city of Ljubljana.
(Source: [LUR SUMP, 2018](#))

FIGURE 59 presents the modal share of trips to the city of Ljubljana as well as the modal share of trips exclusively made in the city, based on the last Representative Survey of Travel Habits in the city of Ljubljana (MOL) and the LUR in 2013.

The majority of trips to the city are made by car (84%). However, inhabitants of Ljubljana use more sustainable modes to travel in the city; although the car is still the dominant source of travel in 2013 (38.2%), 37.5% of the trips are done walking. Public transport trips present a share of 13.3%, and 11% of the trips are done cycling. Recent numbers show that the cycling modal split has increased to 16% in 2022.⁶²

This modal share figures will be updated in the following GEMINI reports, when the latest statistics are available.

10.1.3 Car ownership Ljubljana

At the end of 2023, Ljubljana city counted 163 963 registered passenger cars, 8 006 registered motorcycles and 5 452 registered mopeds.⁶³ This corresponds to a motorisation rate of 553 passenger cars/1000 inhabitants.

FIGURE 60 shows the motorisation rate as well as the average age of cars in Slovenia and its different statistical regions in 2020. Ljubljana is located in the statistical region Osrednjeslovenska (green rectangle). The average age of cars is quite high in Slovenia, with an average of 10.4 years. The motorisation rate is also high, on average 554 cars per 1 000 inhabitants were registered in 2020 in Slovenia. Ljubljana shows one of the lowest motorisation rates and the lowest average car age of the different regions in Slovenia.

⁶² <https://ecf.com/news-and-events/news/how-bicycle-transformed-ljubljana-more-liveable-city>

⁶³ <https://pxweb.stat.si/SiStatData/pxweb/en/Data/Data/2222104S.px/>

FIGURE 60: Motorisation rate (# passenger cars/ 1000 inhabitants) and average car age in Slovenia and its statistical regions.

(Ljubljana forms part of the statistical region Osrednjeslovenska (green rectangle).

Source: <https://www.stat.si/StatWeb/en/News/Index/9389>

At the end of 2020, at national level, half of the registered cars were diesel cars and 48% petrol, 0.8% hybrid and 0.3% electric cars. As elsewhere in Europe, the purchase of hybrid or electric cars is on a rise. Out of all first registered new cars in Slovenia in 2020, 3% were electric cars and 6% were hybrid ones.⁶⁴

10.1.4 Shared mobility Ljubljana

Bike-sharing

In May 2011, the BicikeLJ bike-sharing system was introduced in the city to complement the public transport system in Ljubljana. BicikeLJ is a public-private partnership between the city of Ljubljana and Europlakat d.o.o. At the start there were 300 bicycles at 30 stations available. By the end of 2021, this increased to 820 bicycles at 80 stations. The first hour of use is free of charge, which has been highly appreciated by the users, as 98% of all trips are free.

FIGURE 61 presents some latest statistics of the BicikeLJ bike-sharing system. Since the start of BicikeLJ, the yearly number of bike rentals has been increasing, with exception of the COVID-19 period. A bit more than 1 million bikes (1 047 069) were rented in 2021. On average each available bike is used 8 times a day and the average rental time is 16 minutes. As can be expected, the most popular months for renting out a bike are during the warmer months May to October. At the end of 2021, more than 235 000 users were registered to the BicikeLJ bike-sharing system, of which almost 64 000 active ones.^{65,66} A real-time map of available BicikeLJ bikes is also available online⁶⁷.

⁶⁴ <https://www.stat.si/StatWeb/en/News/Index/9389>

⁶⁵ <https://www.ljubljana.si/en/ljubljana-for-you/transport-in-ljubljana/cycling-in-ljubljana/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.ljubljana.si/assets/Uploads/Kolesarski-letopis-2022-Eng-Web.pdf>

⁶⁷ <https://bikesharemap.com/ljubljana/#/13.037424025542574/14.5069/46.0458/>

FIGURE 61: 2020 and 2021 statistics of the BicikeLJ bike-sharing system in Ljubljana including the evolution of the yearly number of rentals since the introduction of the system (middle figure) and the monthly rentals (bottom figure). (Source: [Cycling Account Ljubljana 2020-2021](#))

Shared e-scooters

Since 2022, Bolt e-scooters are available in Ljubljana city. Ljubljana is the first Slovenian city where Bolt e-scooters are available. Since the start, 300 electric scooters are available in the city, and this number will be adjusted according to needs.⁶⁸

Car-sharing

In July 2016, a 100% electric car-sharing system was introduced in Ljubljana city, which then expanded to the LUR and other Slovenian cities. The system, with all its services (reservations, vehicle unlocking, engine ignition, final payment) accessible through the Avant2Go mobile app, was developed by the Avantcar company⁶⁹. It is a public-private partnership, with partners in various roles, including the National Eco Fund, municipalities and companies. In Ljubljana the car sharing system is increasingly popular, the number of rentals in 2019 went up by 200% in comparison to 2018. The car sharing network in Ljubljana includes over 200 vehicles at 34 public and 51 private locations. Since the introduction of the system drivers travelled over 5 million kilometres with vehicles.^{61,70} Other car-sharing providers are operational in Ljubljana, such as GreenGo⁷¹, offering also electric shared cars.

10.2 Objectives

Environmental:

- Modal shift to more sustainable trips of A1 employees.
- Modal shift to more sustainable trips of Hotel Mons guests and congress attendees.
- Reduced greenhouse gas emissions thanks to modal shift.

Societal:

- Increased awareness about sustainable mobility.
- Improved accessibility and social inclusion for A1 employees who do not have a driving licence and are not able to use the corporate car fleet.

Safety & Security:

Zero accidents with the shared vehicle fleet.

Economic:

- A1 employee fleet cost reduction.
- Time savings for A1 employees thanks to improved reservation process and avoiding traffic jams and city areas closed for motorised vehicles

⁶⁸ <https://the-slovenia.com/en/slovenia/ljubljana-bolt-electric-scooters-for-rent-available/>

⁶⁹ <https://www.avantcar.si/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.ljubljana.si/en/news/ljubljana-second-most-car-sharing-friendly-city/>

⁷¹ <https://green-go.city>

10.3 Measure description

10.3.1 Challenges in relation to GEMINI

At **A1 headquarters**, a corporate standalone building situated 4 km from the Ljubljana city centre, within one of the largest shopping, business and leisure centres in Europe covering 4 750 m² (BTC City Ljubljana), the area deals with the following main challenges:

- Lack of parking spaces and high parking prices
- Quite some areas of the city centre are closed for traffic (beside bikes and e-scooters), which adds to the time consumption
- Time consuming driving due to traffic jams (20 minutes in one direction to the city centre (4 km drive).
- High gas prices, maintenance and insurance costs for the fleet

Another challenge is the mobility situation at hotel Mons. **Hotel Mons** is a 4-star hotel in the suburbs of Ljubljana, 7 km from the city centre. It is a popular destination for congress tourism. As all suburban hotels it lacks connectivity and access to PT infrastructure. Due to the relatively small scale of shared mobility services in Ljubljana, the hotel cannot offer high quality mobility packages and is therefore in search for ways to expand their offering.

10.3.2 General description

Two shared mobility business-to-business (B2B) models will be developed, one for a private company and one for a hospitality organization. It will consist of e-bikes and e-scooters, including charging infrastructure, at private company grounds and at the hotel. The solution will serve the mobility needs of company employees and hotel guests.

The measure entails the following 2 sub-measures:

- 1) The company fleet of the private company A1 at its Slovenia headquarters in Ljubljana will be expanded with electric bikes and e-scooters. A1 is a private provider of communication services with more than 600 employees and more than 800 000 clients. Ten e-scooters and ten e-bikes, including charging infrastructure will be added to the company fleet and a GoGiro software license will be purchased to book and unlock the shared e-bikes and e-scooters.
- 2) Like the A1 setup, a shared mobility point combining e-scooters and possibly e-bikes will be set up for Hotel Mons' guests in front of the building.
By automating and digitalizing the process, the burden on hotel employees is decreased. Aggregated and anonymized data collection on guest habits will be analysed and used to assist in improving the NMS operations.

The e-bikes and e-scooters can be booked through the GoGiro application. This will be an easy-to-use app for the hotel guests and private company employees that will include information on the availability of the vehicles, an easy booking system, and that will be used to unlock the e-bikes and e-scooters. Aggregated and anonymized data will be collected on guest and employees' habits through the GoGiro app.

10.3.3 Output

- A private company fleet at A1 headquarters consisting of 10 e-scooters and 10 e-bikes and charging infrastructure
- GoGiro app to book and unlock e-scooters and e-bikes and to monitor the habits of the users
- A mobility hub at the hotel Mons

10.4 Test area and target groups

Test area 1: A1 Slovenia headquarters in Ljubljana

FIGURE 62: the second test area of the Ljubljana MLL.
(Source: [Google Maps](#))

TABLE 40: Target groups of the Ljubljana MLL

Target group	Description
Employees A1	A1 company car fleet users for short trips (less than 15 km) to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • business meetings with partners • costumer visits • lunch break • personal exit
A1 customers-subscribers (2nd stage)	Short trips (less than 15 km): Free service for selected subscribers: Arrive to A1 premises by PT (bus), collect an e-scooter or a bike, shop within the BTC City, return the vehicle and return home by public transport. Validate the potential of the B2C Maas, include it as a future service or a bonus (added value) for future customers.

Test area 2: Hotel Mons in Ljubljana

FIGURE 63: Hotel Mons, the second test area of the Ljubljana MLL.
(Source: [Google Maps](#).)

Target group	Description
Hotel guests	Hotel guests that will use the services for: reaching the public transport points, visiting the city centre or sightseeing
Congress attenders	Attenders of the congresses organised at / by the hotel for: reaching the public transport points, visiting the city centre or sightseeing.

10.5 Impact evaluation

10.5.1 City context indicators

TABLE 41: Ljubljana city context indicators and data sources

#	Indicator	Sources
1	Modal split	-City statistical reports -Public transport reports
2	Number of road crashes	https://www.policija.si/o-slovenski-policiji/statistika/prometna-varnost
3	Number of seriously injured	
4	Number of road deaths	
5	Density of shared mobility services	-Yearly reports of https://www.lpp.si/ -GreenGo, an electric car-sharing company: https://greengo.city -Bicikelj, bike-sharing company: https://www.bicikelj.si/sl/home -Car-sharing company: https://www.avantcar.si/
6	Availability of shared mobility services	-Enquiry for statistical data sent to every provider: https://www.lpp.si/ -GreenGo, an electric car-sharing company: https://greengo.city -Bicikelj, bike-sharing company: https://www.bicikelj.si/sl/home -Car-sharing company: https://www.avantcar.si/
7	Availability MaaS	- https://www.lpp.si/en -GoGiro
8	Car ownership	Republic of Slovenia Statistical Office (SURs)
9	Congestion levels	TomTom Traffic Index
10	Quality of cycling network	- Copenhagenize Bicycle Friendly Cities Index -City reports

10.5.2 Impact indicators

TABLE 42: Objectives and selected impact indicators to monitor these objectives in the Ljubljana MLL

Impact indicators						
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group	
1	Increase share of NMS in the modal employee car fleet distribution	Modal split employees (during external work meetings)	Survey	start & end project	MLL area	
2	Modal shift hotel guests to sustainable travel	Modal split hotel guests				
3	Reduction of road risk	-Number of damaged vehicles in the fleet -Number of collisions per mode -Number of fatalities, seriously and light injuries per mode	Any damages or reported accidents with the shared vehicles			
4	Improved accessibility PT	Multimodal trip to meetings (e.g. e-bike to train station)	Location data			
5	Improved awareness of NMS	Awareness of new mobility options	Survey		end project	Employees Hotel guests
6	Improved acceptance of NMS	Acceptance of new mobility options				
7	Improved social inclusion	Specific questions on social inclusion in the survey				
8	Reduction of traffic related air pollution	NO _x emissions	XIPE model		end project	MLL area
9	Reduction of traffic related CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂ emissions				
10	A1 employee fleet cost reduction	-Cost NMS fleet/station/year -Cost NMS fleet/employee	Calculated		end project	MLL area

10.5.3 Additional indicators

TABLE 43: Additional indicators of the Ljubljana MLL

Additional indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Environmental, Social, and Governance score	ESG score (score 1-100)	External evaluation	yearly	A1

Additional indicators => NMS performance				
#	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Number of vehicles per shared mode	Data from GoGiro	(start &) end project	Employees A1 Hotel guests an users
2	Number of users per shared mode			
3	Number of trips/week per shared mode			
4	Average trip distance per shared mode			
5	Travel behaviour before and after use shared mode	Survey Interviews	(start &) end project	Employees A1
6	NMS user satisfaction			
Additional indicators => BM performance				
#	Indicator	Method	Frequency	
1	Investment costs	Accounting report	End project	
2	Operational costs			
3	Subsidisation			
4	Revenues			
5	No. jobs generated			

10.6 Process evaluation

10.6.1 Stakeholders involved

TABLE 44: Overview of the Ljubljana MLL partners and stakeholders involved, and their role

Stakeholders			
Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - E: Evaluator/ knowledge institution - S: Supplier			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
GIRO	Private company	L	Giro coordinates the Mobility Living Lab (MLL). Giro will extend the existing GoGiro platform with the new e-mobility services.
A1	Private company	P	A1 will expand its company fleet with e-scooters and e-bikes for their employees and explore shared mobility incentive packages to their customers.
Skupina Asistenca	Private company	P	Skupina Asistenca is responsible for the supply and maintenance of the shared e-scooters and e-bikes.
Insurance companies	Private company	O	Insurance for the new fleet (theft, damage, liability, accident insurance)
Hotel Four Points by Sheraton Ljubljana Mons	Private company	P	Hotel Mons will expand services by offering an easier way around / to city centre.

10.6.2 Supporting activities

- Sensibilisation activities of the A1 employees to use sustainable modes
- Education on e-scooter use
- Showcase for potential B2B customers of the MaaS solution

10.6.3 Planned implementation phases

TABLE 45: Planned implementation phases of the Ljubljana MLL

Planned implementation phases		
#	Phase	Milestone
1	Design	Plan for establishment of the Mobility node: look, feel, purpose, added value.
2	Test	Hypothesis, conversations with stakeholders, requirements.
3	Implementation	Preparation and instalment, platform integration, data imports, surveys.
4	Operational	Run of the use case, Monitoring and data collection.
5	Evaluation	Data analyses and future development.

10.7 Timing evaluation activities

FIGURE 64: Timing of the evaluation activities of the Ljubljana MLL

implementation phases

DE	development phase
IM	implementation phase
OP	operational phase

data collection impact and intermediate indicators

B	baseline data
Bs	survey- baseline data
Ix	intermediate data
Ixs	survey- intermediate data
R	result data
Rs	survey- result data

reporting

D2.1	GEMINI evaluation plan
D3.1	Interim progress report of MLLs implementation
D3.10	Final Impact Assessment of GEMINI NMS and MLLs

11 EVALUATION PLAN OF MLL TWINNING 3 – PORTO

11.1 Context

11.1.1 Geography and population Porto

Porto, Portugal's second largest city, located along the riverbank of the Douro, covers an area of 42 km². The city is quite hilly and has an historic centre which was designated a UNESCO World Cultural Heritage Site in 1996, with sometimes steep, narrow and cobbled streets, bringing forward its mobility challenges. In 2022, the city launched the Porto Climate Pact⁷² to mobilise citizens and organisations towards climate action, aiming to achieve carbon neutrality by 2030.

In 2022, Porto counted 238 298 inhabitants⁷³. The city of Porto is part of the Porto Metropolitan Area (AMP), which was founded in 1991. It comprises 17 municipalities and has an area of 2 041 km². AMP is an intermunicipal entity dedicated to enhancing collaboration among municipalities and institutions responsible for supramunicipal networks. With around 1.7 million residents, the AMP constitutes a significant portion of Portugal's total population, representing approximately 17% of the country's inhabitants (Rocha et al., 2023). The predominant focus on road transport within the mobility system has led to private car usage accounting for 69% of the modal share.⁷⁴

According to the results of the IMob mobility survey published by INE, 2017, the number of daily trips within the AMP surpassed 3.4 million, constituting a significant portion of the region's total mobility (78.9%, see FIGURE 65). This data emphasizes the high level of movements in the area. (Rocha et al., 2023)

FIGURE 65: Percentage of the population within the municipalities of the AMP.
(Source: Rocha et al., 2023)

⁷² https://pactoparaoclima.portodigital.pt/?page_id=5738

⁷³ <https://www.pordata.pt/en/municipalities/resident+population+total-359>

⁷⁴ <https://urbact.eu/articles/porto-metropolitan-area>

11.1.2 Modal share Porto

FIGURE 66 presents the modal share in the Porto Metropolitan Area and in Porto city (right), based on the latest IMob household survey conducted in 2017. As already highlighted, car use is high in the AMP, with 69% of the trips done by car. A good percentage of 19% of the trips is done walking in the AMP, and 10% by PT. Other modes are hardly used in the AMP.

In Porto city, the percentage of sustainable trips is higher than in the AMP, with 31% of the trips done walking, and 18% of the trips done by PT (13% by bus, 5% by metro). Cycling represents a negligible share (0.4%). The car is still the main mode of transport in Porto city, with 49% of the trips done by car.

11.1.3 Car ownership Porto

The Portuguese Automobile Association (ACAP) communicated that by the end of 2021, there were 5.41 million passenger cars registered in Portugal, marking a 2% increase from 2020. Among these, 25% (1.35 million) were first registered before 2001. This presents a large percentage of vehicles that are over 20 years old, having its effect on greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution.⁷⁵ Statista reports an average of more than 500 cars per 1000 inhabitants in Portugal.⁷⁶

In Porto city, 120 547 cars were registered in 2022 and a motorisation rate of 506 cars per 1 000 inhabitants older than 18 years, in line with the national average.

⁷⁵ <https://www.theportugalnews.com/news/2022-05-31/25-of-cars-in-portugal-over-20-years-old/67518>

⁷⁶ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/452097/portugal-number-of-cars-per-1000-inhabitants/>

11.1.4 Shared mobility Porto

Car-sharing

There are currently no commercial car-sharing providers operational in Porto, with the exception of peer-to-peer car-sharing systems, that allow users to rent out their vehicle using an online platform, such as CarAmigo⁷⁷ and Tuuggo⁷⁸. Ride-hailing has rather gained popularity in Porto, with Uber and Bolt as dominant players.

FIGURE 67: Real-time availability of shared e-scooters and bikes in the area of the Porto stadium Estádio do Dragão. (Source: <https://explore.porto.pt/>)

Bike-sharing and shared e-scooters

In June 2020, 3 e-scooter sharing scooter sharing companies started its operation in Porto – Bird, Circ and Hive – with 2000 vehicles and 210 sharing points across the urban area. Specific rules apply for the e-scooter users. Shared vehicles are not allowed during night hours and are collected between 10PM and 6AM. Furthermore, one can only drive these vehicles in the designated cycling lanes, rather than in pedestrian areas.^{79,80}

Nowadays, the city has around 1 200 vehicles available from operators Bird, Circ and Bolt. However, the number of vehicles circulating in the city is often higher because of mobility between neighbouring cities.

In real-time, the number of bikes and e-scooters or e-scooters available at a certain station, can be consulted on the Explore Porto-interactive map (see FIGURE 67). In 2023, the most requested sharing points were: at Via do Castelo do Queijo (next to the sea), at Rua da Constituição and at Rua Nova da Alfândega (next to the river).

⁷⁷ <https://location-voiture-caramigo.com/pt/>

⁷⁸ <https://tuuggo.wixsite.com/>

⁷⁹ <https://www.flatio.com/blog/commuting-alternatives-in-porto#bike-sharing>

⁸⁰ <https://www.themayor.eu/en/a/view/porto-launches-electric-scooter-service-5100>

11.2 Objectives

Environmental:

- Modal shift to more sustainable trips to and from the Estádio do Dragão during games.
- Reduced congestion thanks to reduced car trips to and from the Estádio do Dragão.
- Improved air quality and reduced greenhouse gas emissions thanks to reduced car trips.

Societal:

- Increased accessibility to Estádio do Dragão for more vulnerable social groups (e.g., elderly people and families with children).
- Increased awareness of sustainable mobility initiatives in Porto city and FC Porto.

Safety & Security :

Improved sense of security during games by visitors and city residents.

Other:

Optimization of Porto's PT network during games.

11.3 Measure description

11.3.1 Challenges in relation to GEMINI

A football game at Estádio do Dragão brings a sizable crowd from the city and the country as many fans travel to attend a game. Consequently, there is congestion in the parking lots of the stadium and around the stadium when the fans want to park and leave the parking area, causing long waiting times (mainly on the streets around the stadium).

During the games, there is a low sense of security due to the large crowds that gather around the stadium and in public transport (mostly metro). Therefore, authorities label the most popular league games as "high risk games".

The stadium is reachable by 4 metro lines and 2 bus lines. The Campanhã train station is at about 2 kilometres away but infrastructure for pedestrians connecting the stadium with the train station is poor. Up to 150 bicycle parking spots are available at the stadium and a large car park from a shopping mall is nearby. The existing car parking spaces at the stadium are not significant, they are practically exclusive to FC Porto (FCP) employees, suppliers, and partners. Currently, limited micromobility services are available in the area. There is (e-)scooter and e-bike-sharing in Porto and fans can use other mobility options such as ride-share services Bolt, Uber, and taxi to reach the stadium.

Main challenges include:

1. Improve mobility options and reduce congestion, mainly at the end of the match.
2. Reduce huge congestion at the metro entrance at the end of the match.
3. Manage alternatives to traffic redirection and blocked streets.
4. Limited platforms are available to reach/contact visitors of the stadium.

11.3.2 General description

The Porto MLL aims to expand and complement the existing mobility options to access the FCP football stadium Estádio do Dragão during sport or other events, thereby stimulating the use of more environmentally friendly options to and from the stadium. The Porto MLL will target people who live outside the city centre or even in other Portuguese cities (Braga, Coimbra, Aveiro, or Lisbon) and who travel a considerable distance to watch a game but lack access to easy transportation and suffer from poor integration. The target audience includes adults and families who have been frequenting stadiums more commonly in recent years.

To enable this:

1. PT services before and after games will be optimised
2. A Park & Ride (P&R) for fans travelling from outside the city centre will be piloted
3. Additional, temporary (additional) shared e-scooter and (e-)bikes stations of existing share mobility providers in Porto will be piloted at the stadium, during games
4. App-based mobility services will be offered, testing solutions to access and pay PT combined with micromobility and ride-hailing

11.3.3 Output

- An app for access and payment of the available mobility solutions, including the newly implemented mobility services.
- Improved PT services before and after games by increased service frequency, increased vehicular capacity, and/or the creation of new service lines, if needed.
- The creation of P&Rs for fans during game days.
- Micromobility solutions at the stadium by the creation of (temporary or permanent) parking spots for shared e-scooters and bicycles at Estádio do Dragão.

11.4 Test area and target groups

FIGURE 68: Porto stadium Estádio do Dragão and its surrounding area.

TABLE 46: Target groups of the Porto MLL

Target group	Description
Visitors of the stadium	<p>Supporters/visitors travelling to the Estádio do Dragão.</p> <p>The following sub-target groups are considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Families, groups our visitors travelling by private vehicle: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ From Porto; ○ From Vila Nova de Gaia; ○ From Maia; ○ From Valongo; ○ From Gondomar; ○ From other locations in the south of Portugal; ○ From other locations in the north and east of Portugal.

Target group	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Families, groups our visitors travelling by PT: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ From Porto; ○ From Vila Nova de Gaia; ○ From Maia; ○ From Valongo; ○ From Gondomar; ○ From other locations in the south of Portugal; ○ From other locations in the north and east of Portugal.

11.5 Impact evaluation

11.5.1 City context indicators

TABLE 47: Porto city context indicators and data sources

#	Indicator	Sources
1	Modal split	Censos (2021)
2	Number of road crashes	Pordata platform
3	Number of seriously injured	
4	Number of road deaths	
5	Density of shared mobility services	- Explore Porto - City Open Data
6	Availability of shared mobility services	Data from mobility department (micromobility only)
7	Availability MaaS	- Explore Porto - APP ANDA
8	Car ownership	Data from mobility department
9	Congestion levels	Data from mobility department
10	Quality of cycling network	City Open Data

11.5.2 Impact indicators

TABLE 48: Objectives and selected impact indicators to monitor these objectives in the Porto MLL

Impact indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method/Source	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Reduction of congestion	-Average vehicle speed (peak/off-peak) -Time travelled from areas A-D	-Traffic controller data -VV pilot app	start & end project	MLL area
2	Increase share of NMS in the modal split	Modal share NMS in modal split visitor's stadium	-Porto Digital survey -VV pilot app		Stadium fans
3	Reduction of road risk	-Number of collisions per mode -Number of fatalities, seriously and light injuries per mode	t.b.d.		City level
4	Improved sense of security	Perception of security when using metro and other services	Porto Digital survey		Stadium fans
5	Improved accessibility PT	Improved accessibility to PT for vulnerable social groups (e.g., elderly people and families with children)	Porto Digital survey		MLL area
6	Optimised PT services	-Accuracy of PT service -Commercial speed PT -Average PT occupancy	- Porto Digital survey -Number of validations on public transport -Data provided by transportation stakeholders		Stadium fans
7	Improved awareness of NMS	Awareness of NMS	- Porto Digital survey -VV pilot app		Stadium fans
8	Improved acceptance of NMS	Acceptance of NMS	- Porto Digital survey -VV pilot app		Stadium fans
9	Improved social inclusion	Linked to indicator 5	Porto Digital survey		Stadium fans
10	Reduction of traffic related air pollution	NO _x , PM emissions	-Air quality sensor data - XIPE model	end project	MLL area
11	Reduction of traffic related CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂ emissions	- Calculated based on reduced car-vkm from traffic simulations - XIPE model		

11.5.3 Additional indicators

TABLE 49: Additional indicators of the Porto MLL

Additional indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	User's engagement	Number of Via Verde app pilot-testers	Via Verde pilot app	mid & end project	-Pilot-testers -Stadium fans
2	Improved PT access	Capacity or frequency increases PT	Transportation stakeholder data	mid project	MLL area
3	Improved micromobility access	Number of drop-off/pick-up places in new locations created during the project	Micromobility stakeholder data	mid project	MLL area
4	NMS acceptance level	Number of early adopters of new P&R services or new ticketing services	Via Verde pilot app	mid project	-Pilot-testers -Stadium fans
Additional indicators => NMS performance					
#	Indicator		Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Number of providers included in the Via Verde app		Via Verde pilot app	(start &) end project	MLL area
2	Number of Via Verde app users when app is in production				
3	Number of trips/game per shared mobility service				
4	Number of tickets/game bought through the Via Verde app				
5	Average trip distance per shared mode/multimodal trip				
6	Travel behaviour before and after use shared mode		- Porto Digital survey - Via Verde pilot app	end project	NMS/MaaS users
7	Via Verde app and/or NMS user satisfaction				-Pilot-testers -Stadium fans
Additional indicators => BM performance					
#	Indicator	Method		Frequency	
1	Investment costs	Development Costs (€/hour)		end project	
2	Operational costs	App & Infrastructure maintenance costs (€/month)			
3	Subsidisation	N/A			
4	Revenues	Shared revenue system (%/ #tickets)			
5	No. jobs generated	t.b.c.			

11.6 Process evaluation

11.6.1 Stakeholders involved

TABLE 50: Overview of the Porto MLL partners and stakeholders involved, and their role

Stakeholders			
<i>Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Partner - S: Stakeholder</i>			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
Via Verde Portugal (VVP)	Private company	L	VVP coordinates the Mobility Living Lab (MLL) and is responsible for developing the business model scenarios and for the NMS project management
ATOBE	Private company	P	Company providing the resources for the mobile app development and technical integration
Porto Digital (PD)	Private non-profit organisation	P	Porto Digital will provide access to data on how intercity mobility is affected before and after the measure is implemented. Porto Digital represents the Porto City Council and is in close contact with the PT operators and city stakeholders.
Câmara Municipal do Porto (CMP)	City Council	S	City council is a key stakeholder helping on the management and effective communication, bridging all transportation and security city stakeholders.
Futebol Clube do Porto (FCP)	Football Club	S	Key stakeholder in the project allowing the GEMINI consortium to study and develop NMS pilots to solve the current vehicular congestion in the stadium's vicinity. Also responsible for crowd control and traffic management within stadium grounds (with a maximum limit of a 10 meter off-site perimeter).
Polícia de Segurança Pública (PSP)	National Police Force	S	Police force mainly responsible for providing safety and crowd control around the stadium grounds.
Polícia Municipal (PM)	Local Police Force	S	Local police force mainly responsible for enforcing traffic management rules, and temporary measures contributing to traffic flow improvement.
Proteção Civil Municipal	Civil Protection	S	Civil Protection has a preventive responsibility in the municipality, which is why it promotes activities in favor of preparation, management and reduction of risks, as well as the dissemination of information to residents about preventive measures and self-protection behaviours in the face of existing risks and predictable scenarios.
Centro de Gestão Integrada (CGI)	Council Operations Centre	S	The council's operation centre has the responsibility of coordinating all operations from all different local services (Firehouses, Local Police Force, Cleaning Services, Transportation and Mobility, etc.). It acts as a hub to effectively anticipate, plan and act over any issue within the city limits.
Metro do Porto (METRO)	Underground Tram/Light Rail operator	S	Transportation operator responsible for light train and underground metro services within Porto's metropolitan area. Entity responsible for capacity planning, maintenance, and servicing.
Comboios de Portugal (CP)	National Railway Company	S	Portuguese national railway company covering the entire country, including city centre, urban and peri-urban train services.
Sociedade de Transportes Coletivos do Porto (STCP)	City bus operator	S	Transportation operator responsible for trams and underground metro services within Porto's metropolitan area. Entity responsible for capacity planning, maintenance, and servicing.

11.6.2 Supporting activities

- Citizen involvement: surveys and active participation in pilots to test modal shifts
- Stakeholder involvement: ideation workshops and meetings with key stakeholders at key moments of the project to validate and implement the project.
- Communication campaign (involving all stakeholders, mainly through the communication networks of the city of Porto and FCP): publication of news, use of social networks to publicize project measures and promote their use, create moments of environmental awareness during games, etc.

11.6.3 Planned implementation phases

TABLE 51: Planned implementation phases of the Porto MLL

Planned implementation phases		
#	Phase	Milestone
1	Design	Define and structure a comprehensive project plan
2	Test	Test all hypotheses through pilot-tests
3	Implementation	Development of final NMS service(s)
4	Operational	Run a soft-launch of NMS service (s) and obtain insights
5	Evaluation	Define next steps stemming from all previous phases

12 EVALUATION PLAN OF MLL TWINNING 4 - HELSINKI

12.1 Context

12.1.1 Geography and population Helsinki

The city of Helsinki, the capital of Finland, is located in southern region Uusimaa, on the shore of the Gulf of Finland. The city is home to 674 500 people (12/2023). Together with the cities Espoo, Vantaa and Kauniainen, Helsinki forms the Helsinki Metropolitan Area (HMA), which hosts almost 1.6 million inhabitants (1 582 4521 on 12/2023).⁸¹

FIGURE 70: Helsinki city, Helsinki Metropolitan Area (HMA) and Greater Helsinki Region.
(Source: <https://welcome.hel.fi/welcome-to-helsinki-living-in-helsinki/about-the-city-of-helsinki/>)

The Helsinki Metropolitan Area (HMA) is characterized by various population densities, service networks, and age structures. Population densities vary across the region, with Helsinki having

⁸¹ https://pxdata.stat.fi/PXWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin__vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11ra.px

the highest at 3 074 people/km², followed by Kauniainen at 1 765 people/km², Vantaa at 1 004 people/km², and Espoo at 951 people/km² (in 2022). The densest areas are typically found in Helsinki's city centre and along suburban railway lines. (Willberg et al., 2023)

This MLL focuses on addressing the needs of 2 peri-urban municipalities, Karkkila and Raasepori, located 70 km and 90 km from Helsinki city in the Greater Helsinki Region, and its connection to the city of Helsinki (see FIGURE 73). Karkkila, located to the north of Helsinki, is home to 8 581 people. Raasepori (Raseborg) lies on the Finnish south coast between the cities of Helsinki and Turku and has 27 209 inhabitants.⁸¹

12.1.2 Modal share Helsinki

FIGURE 71 presents the modal share of all journeys in Helsinki in 2021. Walking (46%) and making use of public transport (24%) are the 2 main modes of transport of the inhabitants of Helsinki. Also cycling has gained popularity over the years, reaching now a modal share of 9%. Regarding modal choice in Finland, one needs to consider the seasonal variation in the country. On average the Helsinki snow season lasts for about 97 days, with average temperatures in the region around zero from November to April⁸², bringing its challenges for urban mobility.

FIGURE 71: Modal share of all trips in Helsinki in 2021.

(Source: https://www.hel.fi/static/hel2/tietokeskus/julkaisut/pdf/22_06_15_Helsinki_facts_and_figures_2022.pdf)

Currently there are no figures on the modal share of the commuting trips from the municipalities Karkkila and Raasepori to Helsinki. There have however been recent studies on the organisation of public transport in Länsi-Uusimaa (in Finnish)⁸³, analysing the level of public transport service (bus and train), within Länsi-Uusimaa, giving a first understanding of the accessibility of Helsinki city from those municipalities with public transport. The modal share of

⁸² <https://en.ilmatiiteenlaitos.fi/climate>

⁸³ <https://www.doria.fi/handle/10024/185111>

commuting trips from the municipalities Karkkila and Raasepori to Helsinki will be estimated by means of a survey during the project.

12.1.3 Car ownership Helsinki

In 2024, Helsinki counted 219 281 registered passenger cars or 325 cars per 1000 inhabitants, 7% of those are electric (TABLE 52).⁸⁴ In the municipalities Karkkila and Raasepori car ownership per inhabitant is higher, with around 570 cars per 1000 inhabitants.

Car ownership numbers in Helsinki have increased relatively slowly, while elsewhere in Finland it has increased more quickly. The number of electric vehicles and hybrid vehicles is still low in Finland, but the fastest growth is taking place in Helsinki.⁸⁵

TABLE 52: Car ownership in Helsinki, Karkkila and Raasepori (2024).

Municipality	# passenger cars	% electric cars	population	# cars/1000 inhabitants
Helsinki	219 281	7%	674 500	325
Karkkila	4894	3%	8581	570
Raasepori	15 397	2%	27209	566

Source: [The Finnish Transport and Communications Agency Traficom](#)

12.1.4 Shared mobility Helsinki

Car-sharing

The following commercial car-sharing providers and peer-to-peer sharing options, where the car owners rent their own car to other users, are in 2024 available in Helsinki⁸⁶:

- 5 commercial car-sharing provides: Aimo car sharing, Beast, City Car Club, Green Mobility, Omago, 24Rent
- 3 peer-to-peer services: Autolevi, GoMore, PlanBil

Bike-sharing

Helsinki has over 1 500 kilometres of well-maintained cycling paths⁸⁷. In 2016, a city bike system, the first in Finland, was introduced, starting with 500 bikes at 50 stations across Helsinki. In 2018, the Helsinki city bike system was extended to Espoo. The city bikes are available for seven months from the beginning of April to the end of October. In 2019, the city bike system was introduced in the neighbouring Vantaa city, but a different system from Helsinki and Espoo, and unfortunately the bikes cannot be cross-used between the two systems. However, the Helsinki Regional Transport Authority (HSL) has started planning a cooperation model for the city bike service together with its member municipalities. If implemented, this would provide a single urban cycle service for the whole region, which would be more closely linked to public

⁸⁴ https://trafi2.stat.fi/PXWeb/pxweb/en/TraFi/TraFi_-_Liikennekaytossa_olevat_ajoneuvot/010_kanta_tau_101.px/

⁸⁵ <https://www.hel.fi/static/liitteet/kaupunkiymparisto/julkaisut/julkaisut/julkaisu-35-20-en.pdf>

⁸⁶ <https://helsinginilmastoteot.fi/en/loyd-keinosi-toimia/shared-use-vehicles/>

⁸⁷ <https://welcome.hel.fi/getting-around-helsinki/cycling-in-helsinki-check-out-the-wide-variety-of-scenic-bicycling-routes-in-helsinki/>

transport. The new service would come into operation in 2026.⁸⁸ Besides the yellow city bikes, electric bicycles by Helsinki Freebike are available in a limited area in Helsinki and Espoo.⁸⁶

Overall, there are nearly 4 600 bikes in use and 460 stations in the Helsinki and Espoo areas. There are no city bikes available in Karkkila. In Raasepori the shared bike provider Donkey Republic is operational, with, since the summer of 2023, rental stations in Ekenäs, Karis, Billnäs, Pojo and Fiskars.

Shared e-scooters

FIGURE 72 shows a map of the number of e-scooter providers operational in Helsinki and its surrounding municipalities and cities.

In Helsinki, 6 e-scooter providers are operational in a restricted area: Voi, Tier, Lime, Ryde, Bird and Bolt. Each operator can have a maximum of 700 electric scooters in the restricted area.⁸⁶ There are no e-scooters available in Karkkila or Raasepori.

FIGURE 72: Shared e-scooter providers operational in the Helsinki area.

12.2 Objectives

Environmental:

- Modal shift from private car trips to PT trips by commuters from Karkkila and Raasepori to Helsinki
- Reduced CO₂ emissions and air pollution thanks to reduced vkm by private cars

Societal:

- Improved accessibility and attractiveness to PT for commuting from Karkkila and Raasepori to Helsinki
- Understanding the last 20-40 km problem (from long-distance bus/train connection to destination) in the Greater Helsinki Region for further improvement of PT in the area

⁸⁸ <https://tieto.traficom.fi/en/tilastot/kaupunkipyorat>

Economic:

- Reduced commuting travel time from Karkkila and Raasepori to Helsinki by combining PT with an NMS solution
- Reduce dependency on private cars for commuting to the Greater Helsinki region

12.3 Measure description

12.3.1 Challenges in relation to GEMINI

The suburban, peri-urban, and rural areas in Helsinki region are mostly fairly wealthy, PT is within reasonable price range and covers the region well when it comes to travel in the city centre of Helsinki. However, when moving further away outside the HSL (Helsinki region transit) area to sparsely populated rural areas, the accessibility of PT gets significantly worse causing user inequality and this promotes private car usage especially in trips to Helsinki.

Being one of the fastest growing capitals in Europe, the volume and geographical scale of commuting to Helsinki has expanded remarkably during the last few decades. Due to the expansion of Helsinki city, the increasing last-mile distances that need to be covered to reach the final destination after commuting with PT from the peri-urban area to Helsinki city lead to long transit times with PT, favouring the use of private cars. This increases the challenge to achieve climate neutrality as commuting with private cars from peri-urban areas to Helsinki increases pollution and carbon emission load of the city.

12.3.2 General description

The MLL focuses on the needs of peri-urban municipalities in the greater Helsinki capital region and their connection to the city. New concepts, innovations, and collaboration schemes will be studied and trailed from versatile aspects of mobility.

Two peri-urban municipalities, Karkkila and Raasepori, respectively 70 km and 90 km from Helsinki, have been selected for their pilot based on their lack of coverage by HSL. There is a long-distance transit bus from both municipalities to a centre station in Helsinki city but the travel is long and once in Helsinki the commuters need to find a new transport option to reach their final destination. This pilot aims to find a solution for these “last-10 miles” or “last-20 miles” since travelling by private car is currently the fastest and easiest solution for commuters from peri-urban municipalities.

The aim of this MLL is to co-create and trial innovative concepts and practical schemes with and for commuters from Karkkila and Raasepori to Helsinki to reduce their commuting travel time by combining the current PT option with a NMS solution, such as ride-sharing, a dedicated minibus service tailored to selected user groups and/or shared (e-)bikes.

12.4 Test area and target groups

The Helsinki MLL **test area**: the 2 municipalities Karkkila and Raasepori and their connection to Helsinki city.

FIGURE 73: The Helsinki MLL test area: the 2 municipalities Karkkila and Raasepori and their connection to Helsinki city.

TABLE 53: Target groups of the Helsinki MLL

Target group	Description
Commuters Karkkila - Helsinki area	People living in Karkkila and working or studying in the Helsinki area (Helsinki, Espoo, Vantaa): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • commuters driving alone in a private car • commuters using PT
Commuters Raasepori - Helsinki area	People living in Raasepori area and working or studying in the Helsinki area (Helsinki, Espoo, Vantaa): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • commuters driving alone in a private car • commuters using PT

12.5 Impact evaluation

12.5.1 City context indicators

TABLE 54: Helsinki city context indicators and data sources

#	Indicator	Sources
1	Modal split	-https://www.doria.fi/handle/10024/185111 -https://www.doria.fi/handle/10024/125727 -https://www.karkkila.fi/Liitetiedostot/Liikenne/2016/asukas-kuuleminen_kyselyliite.pdf
2	Number of road crashes	tieliikenneonnettomuudet.stat.fi
3	Number of seriously injured	
4	Number of road deaths	
5	Density of shared mobility services	-https://tieto.traficom.fi/en/tilastot/kaupunkipyorat -https://yle.fi/a/74-20025804

#	Indicator	Sources
6	Availability of shared mobility services	- https://tieto.traficom.fi/en/tilastot/kaupunkipyorat - https://liikkumisvahti.hel.fi/indicators/546 - https://www.hsl.fi/en/citybikes/helsinki - https://www.vertaaensin.fi/blog/sahkopotkulauta - tieto.traficom
7	Availability MaaS	https://www.hsl.fi/en
8	Car ownership	Traficom
9	Congestion levels	suomenvaylat.vayla.fi
10	Quality of cycling network	-Survey and audit - suomenvaylat.vayla.fi

12.5.2 Impact indicators

TABLE 55: Objectives and selected impact indicators to monitor these objectives in the Helsinki MLL

Impact indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Increase share of NMS in the modal distribution	Modal share NMS in modal split MLL area	Survey	start & end project	Commuters in the pilot
2	Reduction of road risk	-Number of collisions per mode -Number of fatalities, serious and light injuries per mode	tieliikenneonnettomuudet.stat.fi		MLL area
3	Improved travel time commuters from Kakkila and Raasepori	PT travel time from Karkkila and Raasepori, between commuters' home and work addresses	Start project: Google maps + www.matkahuolto.fi (PT routeplanner) End project/ actual travel time		
4	Improved accessibility and attractiveness PT	Survey questions: Do inhabitants of the municipalities have easier access to PT and are they more willing to use PT	Survey		
5	Improved awareness of NMS	Awareness of other/new mobility options	Survey		
6	Improved acceptance of NMS	Acceptance of other/new mobility options	Survey		
7	Improved social inclusion	Improved access to jobs and studies by public transport	Survey		

Impact indicators					
#	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
8	Reduction of traffic related air pollution	NOx and PM emissions	XIPE model		Commuters in the pilot
9	Reduction of traffic related CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂ emissions			

12.5.3 Additional indicators

TABLE 56: Additional indicators of the Helsinki MLL

Additional indicators => NMS performance				
#	Indicator	Method/Source	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Number of vehicles per shared mode	Data from NMS provider	(intermediate &) end project	MLL area
2	Number of users per shared mode			
3	Number of trips/week per shared mode			
4	Average trip distance per shared mode			
5	Travel behaviour before and after use shared mode	Survey		NMS users
6	NMS user satisfaction			
Additional indicators => BM performance				
#	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group
1	Investment costs	Survey of operators	end project	business model
2	Operational costs			
3	Subsidisation	Survey of operators, municipalities & HSL		
4	Revenues	Survey of operators		
5	No. jobs generated			

12.6 Process evaluation

12.6.1 Stakeholders involved

TABLE 57: Overview of the Helsinki MLL partners and stakeholders involved, and their role

Stakeholders			
<i>Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - E: Evaluator/ knowledge institution - S: Supplier</i>			
Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role
Forum Virium Helsinki (FVH)	City	L	MLL leader responsible for organising the “last 20 km” pilot in the Helsinki area; Procurement of the pilot operation, communications and stakeholder engagement, and contributing to the pilot activities in the municipalities.
Metropolia University of Applied Sciences (MUAS)	Knowledge institution	P	MUAS is organising the activities in the municipalities. Communication with Karkkila and Raasepori municipalities, organising the commuter pilot group from those municipalities and possibly organising the “first 20 km” pilot in Karkkila and Raasepori area (if needed for the pilot group).
Uusimaa Regional Council	Governmental	0	Support in dissemination of the activities and up-scaling.
Karkkila, Raasepori	Municipality	0	Support for MLL activities regarding infrastructure, land use, promotion and successful trials in the municipalities.
Helsinki Regional Transport Authority (HSL)	Regional Transit Authority	0	Support in dissemination of the activities and up-scaling.

12.6.2 Supporting activities

Citizen workshop in Karkkila and Raasepori: to understand the needs of the commuters and organise a pilot group

12.6.3 Planned implementation phases

TABLE 58: Planned implementation phases of the Helsinki MLL

Planned implementation phases		
#	Phase	Timing
1	Design	1.4.2024 - 31.12.2024
2	Implementation	1.1.2025 - 31.7.2025
4	Operational	1.8.2025 - 30.6.2026
5	Evaluation	1.1.2026 - 1.7.2026

13 CONCLUSION

This document presents the first version of the GEMINI evaluation framework, a comprehensive and consistent approach to evaluate the impact and implementation process of new and shared mobility solutions.

Three types of indicators were introduced:

1. city context indicators to give an overall understanding of the mobility situation in the city (e.g. modal split, car ownership),
2. impact indicators to monitor the expected impact of the implemented NMS in the MLL area, and
3. additional indicators to understand the functioning of the NMS and gain additional insights into the overall impact of the implemented measure.

Furthermore, specific tools were presented, such as the Common Impact Model, a method and tools to smoothen the acceptance of new technical solutions, and the XIPE model, an Excel-based tool to estimate the saved CO₂ emissions and air pollutant PM and NO_x emissions due to the introduction of shared mobility in a city.

Based on the methodology outlined in the GEMINI evaluation framework, this document also presents the detailed evaluation plans of the 4 lead and 4 twinning MLLs. The MLL evaluation plans give an overview of the urban context and specific objectives of each MLL, the expected outputs, the target groups and outline the impact and process activities planned, along with the specific (city context, impact and additional) indicators to be monitored throughout the project's duration.

The individual MLL evaluation plans were developed in close collaboration with the GEMINI partner coordinating the MLL and the GEMINI main stakeholders. These plans are the result of multiple meetings aimed at defining and refining the objectives of each MLL and deciding on the final selection of the indicators to be monitored. In most MLLs, the NMS or MaaS app operator is a dedicated GEMINI partner and sometimes even coordinates the MLL (e.g. in Porto, Paris-Saclay). This provides a unique opportunity to access certain indicator data, such as the number of trips per week, which operators might otherwise be hesitant to share due to business competitiveness concerns. Conversely, in some MLLs, the city or municipality is not a dedicated partner (e.g., Ljubljana, Paris-Saclay), making it challenging to obtain certain non-publicly available mobility data at city or municipality level. Actions will be taken over the course of the project to deal with this challenge.

The MLL evaluation plans serve as a robust foundation to commence the baseline data collection activities, to be documented in GEMINI deliverable D3.1 in month 18 (November 2024), and the intermediate and final evaluation results, to be published in GEMINI deliverable D3.10 in month 38 (July 2026).

In addition, a chapter of this deliverable is dedicated to the identification of possible threats when implementing smart mobility services, and specifies requirements for effective data protection, based on reported cases (examples). It gives insights into the vulnerability of smart services and MaaS, highlighting that when considering smart mobility or smart products in common, the physical hardware is often forgotten. The analysis identifies that vandalism, manipulation, and theft of physical components of the Cyber-Physical System may lead to malfunction or failure. Furthermore, the chapter introduces the guidelines to the EU framework of GDPR.

Over the course of the project the GEMINI evaluation framework will be updated and finetuned based on further validation and optimisation of the approach during the project. The final version of the GEMINI evaluation framework (D2.3) will be delivered in month 41 (October 2026) of the GEMINI project.

REFERENCES

- Actuators in IoT - GeeksforGeeks. (2024, April 29). Retrieved from GeeksforGeeks: <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/actuators-in-iot/>
- Ambient Innovation: GmbH. (April 2024). Künstliche Intelligenz: Chance & Risiken. <https://ambient.digital/wissen/blog/kuenstliche-intelligenz-chancen-risiken/>
- APUR (2020), Évolution 2012-2021 du parc automobile les tendances de renouvellement du parc immatriculé dans le Grand Paris, Avril 2020, https://www.apur.org/sites/default/files/evolution_parc_immatricule_zfe_m.pdf?token=ulviCfL
- Belz, K. et al. (2020): Mobilität in Deutschland – MiD Regionalbericht Stadt München, Münchner Umland und MIV-Verbundraum. Studie von infas, DLR, IVT und infas 360 im Auftrag des Bundesministeriums für Verkehr und digitale Infrastruktur (FE-Nr. 70.904/15). Bonn, Berlin.
- Caballini, C., Vittoria Corazza, M., Delponte, I., (2023). Turin, Rome and Genoa: comparison of the level of maturity of three large Italian cities towards Mobility as a Service. Transportation Research Procedia; Volume 69. 2023. Pages 163-170. ISSN 2352-1465. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2023.02.158>
- EC - AI Act. (2024, April). AI Act. Retrieved from Shaping Europe’s digital future: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>
- EC - Data Act. (2024, April). Data Act. Retrieved from Shaping Europe’s digital future: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-act>
- EC - Data economy. (20. February 2024). Data Act: measures for a fair and innovative data economy. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_1113
- EC - Data Governance Act. (2024, April). European Data Governance Act. Retrieved from Shaping Europe’s digital future: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-governance-act>
- EC - GDPR. (2024, April). Compliance Guidelines. Retrieved from General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): <https://gdpr.eu/>
- EC - IoT. (April 2024). Europe's Internet of Things Policy. Von Shaping Europe’s digital future: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/internet-things-policy>
- EC - New Rules. (17. January 2024). European Data Act enters into force, putting in place new rules for a fair and innovative data economy. Von Shaping Europe’s digital future: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/european-data-act-enters-force-putting-place-new-rules-fair-and-innovative-data-economy>
- EC - Trustworthy AI. (April 2024). Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI. Von Shaping Europe’s digital future: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>
- Engels, D. (2021). CIVITAS 2020 process and impact evaluation framework. CIVITAS SATELLITE D2.4. https://civitas.eu/sites/default/files/D2.4_CIVITAS_2020_process_and_impact_evaluation_framework_final_with_annexes.pdf abgerufen

- EUR-Lex - AI Act. (2021, April 21). Artificial Intelligence Act - EUR-Lex - 52021PC0206 - EN - EUR-Lex. Retrieved from EUR-Lex: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021PC0206>
- EUR-Lex - Data Act. (22. December 2023). Data Act - Regulation - EU - 2023/2854 - EN - EUR-Lex. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32023R2854>
- EUR-Lex - DGA . (2022, June 03). Data Governance Act - Regulation - 2022/868 - EN - EUR-Lex. Retrieved from EUR-Lex: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022R0868>
- EUR-Lex - DPD. (1995, November 23). EUR-Lex. Retrieved from Directive - 95/46 - EN - Data Protection Directive - EUR-Lex: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A31995L0046>
- EUR-Lex - GDPR. (27. April 2016). General Data Protection Regulation - Regulation - 2016/679 - EN - GDPR - EUR-Lex. Von EUR-Lex: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>
- European Mobility Venture (2021). Munich, Copenhagen, Oslo, Amsterdam. 2021 Report. https://www.mos.ed.tum.de/fileadmin/w00ccp/ftm/05-Lehre/05-9-Internationale_Studentenprojekte_globalDrive/euMOVE_2021_Report_fun_size_compressed.pdf
- Follmer, R. und Belz, J. (2018): Mobilität in Deutschland – MiD Kurzreport Stadt München, Münchner Umland und MVV-Verbundraum. Studie von infas, DLR, IVT und infas 360 im Auftrag des Bundesministers für Verkehr und digitale Infrastruktur (FE-Nr. 70.904/15). Bonn, Berlin. www.mobilitaet-in-deutschland.de
- Gabler Wirtschaftslexikon. (13. July 2021). Revision von Cyberphysische Systeme - Definition. Von Gabler Wirtschaftslexikon: <https://wirtschaftslexikon.gabler.de/definition/cyber-physische-systeme-54077/version-384624>
- Guo, Y., Zhang, Y. (2021). Understanding factors influencing shared e-scooter usage and its impact on auto mode substitution. Transportation research part D: transport and environment, 99, 102991. Doi: 10.1016/j.trd.2021.102991
- ITF (2023), “Measuring New Mobility: Definitions, Indicators, Data Collection”, International Transport Forum Policy Papers, No. 114, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://www.itf-oecd.org/sites/default/files/docs/measuring-new-mobility-definitions-indicators-data.pdf>
- INE—Instituto Nacional de Estatística (2017). Mobilidade e Funcionalidade do Território nas Áreas Metropolitanas do Porto e de Lisboa: 2017. INE: Lisboa, Portugal, 2018. ISBN 978-989-25-0478-0. Available online: <https://www.ine.pt/xurl/pub/349495406>
- Rocha, H., Lobo, A., Tavares, J.P., Ferreira, S. (2023). Exploring Modal Choices for Sustainable Urban Mobility: Insights from the Porto Metropolitan Area in Portugal. Sustainability 2023, 15, 14765. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152014765>
- Rudersdal Kommune (2022). Klimahandlingsplan for Rudersdal Kommune 2022-2040. <https://rudersdal.dk/media/1095/download?inline>
- København Kommune (2023). Mobilitetsredegørelse 2023. Teknik- Og Miljøforvaltningen Mobilitet, Klimatilpasning og Byvedligehold, <https://www.kk.dk/sites/default/files/2023-06/Mobilitetsredeg%C3%B8relsen%202023.pdf>

Follmer, R. & Belz, J. (2020). *Mobilität in Deutschland – MiD Kurzreport Stadt München, Münchner Umland und MVVVerbundraum*. Study by infas, DLR, IVT and infas 360 on behalf of the German Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (FE-Nr. 70.904/15). Bonn, Berlin. www.mobilitaet-in-deutschland.de.

Petrovich, B., Murphy, B., Mikkelsen, T., & Kuivalainen, M. (2021). The Common Impact Model: A standardized methodology for community acceptance of decarbonized multivector local energy systems. *Ecocity World Summit 2021 Proceedings*.

Plusserver GmbH. (25. 04 2024). Was sind Smart Services? IoT sorgt für mehr Kundenorientierung. Von plusserver: <https://www.plusserver.com/blog/smart-services-datenbasierte-dienstleistungen-und-produkte-mit-mehrwert/>

Privacy International. (2024, April 17). What Is Privacy? Retrieved from <https://privacyinternational.org/explainer/56/what-privacy>

Sellaouti, A. et al. (2024), Evolution and characteristics of shared e-scooters usage in Munich, Germany – Results of an over 8 million trips data analysis, *Transportation Research Procedia*, Volume 78, 2024, Pages 40-46, ISSN 2352-1465, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2024.02.006> .

Tikoudis, I., Martinez, L., Farro, K., García Bouyssou, K., Petrik, O., Oueslati, W. (2021). Exploring the impact of shared mobility services on CO2. *OECD Environment Working Papers 175*. OECD Publishing. [https://one.oecd.org/document/ENV/WKP\(2021\)7/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/ENV/WKP(2021)7/en/pdf)

Valenza, F. a. (2023). A Hybrid Threat Model for Smart Systems. *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, 20(5), 4403-4417.

Willberg, E., Fink, C., Toivonen, T., The 15-minute city for all? – Measuring individual and temporal variations in walking accessibility, *Journal of Transport Geography*, Volume 106, 2023, 103521, ISSN 0966-6923, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2022.103521> .

Zhou, F., Zheng, Z., Whitehead, J., Perrons, R. K., Washington, S., Page, L. (2020). Examining the impact of car-sharing on private vehicle ownership. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice* 138, 322-341. Doi: 10.1016/j.tra.2020.06.003.

APPENDIX A: GEMINI EVALUATION SHEETS

MLL X – CITY: TITLE

Objectives

List the environmental, societal, safety & security, and economic objectives. If possible quantify the target.

Environmental (e.g. green areas, reduced emissions and air pollution, sustainability, etc.):

Societal (e.g. neighbourhood cooperation, social inclusion, accessibility, gender considerations, etc.):

Safety & Security (e.g. reduced road risk, commuters' perception of safety, cybersecurity, etc.):

Economic (e.g. congestion and other time-related objectives, regional growth, competitiveness, etc.):

Other (e.g. good functioning sharing system):

Measure description

Situation before

Describe the situation in the city or site before the implementation of the measure, including any problems and challenges in relation to the measure. Include key data sources for the information given.

General description

Give a description of the main elements of the measure

Output

List the direct results of the measure (e.g. the acquisition of 5 electric buses, ...)

Supporting activities

Discuss the supporting activities of the measure. Examples of such activities are communication campaigns, stakeholder involvement and citizen engagement activities.

Test area and target groups

Include figure

Target group	Description
	Describe the target groups and divide each target groups in sub-target groups where relevant, e.g. target group: football fans travelling to and from games, sub-target groups: car users, bus travellers, metro travellers, pedestrians, cyclists, etc.
	Sub-target group 1: Sub-target group 2:

Stakeholders

List and describe the role of the main partners and actors involved during the different stages of the measure.

Type of organisation: City - Public transport company - Knowledge institution (e.g. university) - Non-Governmental Organisation - Private company - Other

Level of activity: L: Leading role - P: Principle participant - O: Occasional participant

Actor	Type of organisation	Level of activity	Role

City context indicators

The city context indicators give an overall understanding of the city context in relation to mobility, e.g. it is a more car-oriented city (car-ownership is high), the city has a robust cycling infrastructure etc. These indicators are usually measured at city level, depending on the availability of the data.

No.	Indicator	Definition	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group

Impact indicators

Key indicators to understand the impact of the implemented measures. These are linked to the GEMINI objectives and the main specific objectives of your MLL.

No.	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group

Additional indicators

Indicators to understand specific aspects of the functioning of the measure affecting the impact or observed aspects helping to understand the implementation process and impact of the measures.

No.	Expected impact	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group

Additional indicators => NMS performance

No.	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group

Additional indicators => BM performance

No.	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Area/Target group

Planned implementation phases		
No.	Phase	Milestone
1	Design	
2	Test	
3	Implementation	
4	Operational	
5	Evaluation	

Barriers		
Barrier field	Description	Action to overcome the barrier

Drivers		
Driver field	Description	Action to make use of the driver

APPENDIX B: Reported cases to identify threats

#1 GIS – Data disclosure

Theft of registration data of all people living in Austria

User context

In Austria, public service broadcasting (radio and television) is financed by a household levy. Every household that operates a broadcasting reception system is obliged (with exceptions) to pay this fee. Anyone who does not register their receiver is in breach of the principle of fairness and is also liable to prosecution.

Business model

GIS (Gebühren Info Service GmbH) is responsible for the collection and distribution of broadcasting fees. At the same time, it is also responsible for ensuring the fairness of fees and therefore addresses households in which no radio receivers are registered.

In Austria, anyone with a legitimate interest can query the current or last registered main residence of a person living in Austria from the central population register. In this case, this also applies to the GIS.

When searching for fee avoiders, the registration data from the central Austrian population register is compared with a building database.

Incident date

2020 (2023)

Incident description

An external IT company was commissioned by GIS to merge and restructure the two databases. As part of the contract, the two databases were also handed over to the contracted IT company. The personal data included name, date of birth, residential address, bank details and scans of ID cards.

Normally, generic data sets are used to test individual routines rather than real data. However, it is likely that an employee of the external IT company used the real registration data for a test and also made it available unsecured via the internet. As a result, nine million data records of people living in Austria were available unencrypted on the internet for around a week.

A hacker could have used this period to download or steal this data.

Identified risks

- Automated analysis of personal data
- Unsolicited telephone surveys

References

- <https://www.derstandard.at/story/2000142955237/was-der-verlust-von-neun-millionen-datensaetzen-der-gis-bedeutet>
- <https://www.derstandard.at/story/2000142922619/verbrecher-erbeutete-neun-millionen-meldedaten-aus-datenbank-der-gis>
- <https://www.gis.at/unternehmen/aufgaben>

- <https://www.wien.gv.at/amtshelfer/dokumente/verwaltung/meldeservice/einzelauskunft.html>
- <https://www.all-about-security.de/die-vier-haeufigsten-owasp-api-sicherheitsbedrohungen/>

#2 British Airways – Data breach

A false site diversion led to a 500,000 people’s data breach

User context

Customers booking flights or accessing British Airways' website or mobile app.

Business model

British Airways operates as a major airline, providing passenger and cargo services globally. It relies heavily on its online platform for ticket sales, reservations, and customer interactions.

Incident date

The data breach occurred between August 21 and September 5, 2018.

Incident description

Hackers exploited vulnerabilities in British Airways' website and mobile app, directing users to a fraudulent site where their personal and financial information was harvested. Approximately 500,000 customers were affected, with data including names, addresses, email addresses, and credit card details compromised.

Identified risks

- Risk of financial loss for affected customers due to unauthorized use of their credit card information
- Risk of identity theft and fraud for individuals whose personal information was exposed
- Reputational damage to British Airways, leading to loss of customer trust and potential decline in sales

References

- BBC News. (2018). British Airways breach: How did hackers get in?. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-45408224>
- Information Commissioner's Office. (2018). Statement: British Airways data breach update. Retrieved from <https://ico.org.uk/about-the-ico/news-and-events/news-and-blogs/2018/09/statement-british-airways-data-breach-update/>
- British Airways data breach - Wikipedia

#3 TRENITALIA – Data breach

Data breach targeting ticket vending machine

User context

Commuters and travelers purchasing train tickets from Trenitalia vending machines.

Business model

Trenitalia is the primary operator of train services in Italy, offering various passenger transportation services, including regional, national, and international routes. Ticket vending machines are a crucial part of their sales and service delivery model.

Incident description

Hackers targeted Trenitalia's ticket vending machines, exploiting vulnerabilities to gain unauthorized access to customer data. The breach resulted in the compromise of sensitive information such as payment card details, personal identification data, and travel itineraries of affected customers.

Identified risks

- Risk of financial loss for customers due to unauthorized transactions using compromised payment card information
- Potential for identity theft and fraud using the exposed personal identification data
- Reputational damage to Trenitalia, leading to loss of customer trust and potential legal repercussions

References

<https://www.cybersecurity360.it/nuove-minacce/attacco-a-trenitalia-ferrovie-bloccata-vendita-biglietti-e-un-ransomware/>

#4 EasyPark – Data breach

Safeguarding user privacy in parking apps

User context

In this digital age, parking applications have improved the way users find and pay for parking spaces. However, recent incidents of data breaches have raised concerns about the security and privacy of user information within these applications. EasyPark, a Swedish company renowned for its mobile and web applications that assist users in locating parking spaces, caters to millions of users worldwide. The user base encompasses a diverse range of individuals, including commuters, travelers, and city residents, who rely on EasyPark's services to streamline their parking experiences. Users entrust the app with sensitive location data and payment information, expecting secure and reliable service delivery to facilitate their parking needs.

Business model

EasyPark is a popular parking app used by millions of users across Europe to find, book, and pay for parking spaces conveniently. The app operates on a business model that monetizes through transaction fees and partnerships with parking operators and municipalities. Users benefit from features such as real-time parking availability, digital payment options, and navigation assistance to parking spots. The core of EasyPark's business model revolves around convenience, efficiency, and user satisfaction.

Incident date

The breach was discovered in December 2023, and reportedly exposed sensitive user data in Europe.

Similarly, in 2021 EasyPark's USA operations suffered a data breach that also exposed the personal information of thousands of users, including email addresses and payment card details.

Incident description

EasyPark experienced significant data breaches, compromising the personal information of millions of users. In 2023, the breach was discovered and reportedly exposed sensitive user data. This includes names, phone numbers, addresses and email addresses. Such information is particularly valuable for conducting phishing attacks. The breach is said to have affected millions of users. Additionally, some digits of their users' credit card/debit card or IBAN were also leaked during the breach.

While "some digits of a credit card" were stolen, EasyPark claimed that the hackers didn't have enough data to make unauthorized transactions or wire fraud. However, they would have enough information on EasyPark users to mount phishing attacks, identity theft, or similar. Therefore, caution was advised, especially when receiving messages claiming to be coming from the company. Users were also advised to reset their account passwords and update their login credentials on all other platforms where they may have used the same username/password combination.

This is not the first time EasyPark has faced a security breach. In 2021, the company experienced a similar incident that compromised the data of 21 million users. The recurrence of such breaches keeps raising questions about the robustness of EasyPark's cybersecurity measures across Europe and the US and its ability to safeguard user information.

Identified risks

The exposed data put millions of users at risk of identity theft, fraud, and phishing. Users were advised to be vigilant about unsolicited communications and to monitor their accounts for any unusual activity. Although EasyPark issued guidelines on steps users should take to protect their personal information, the data breach in EasyPark exposed users to various risks, including:

- **Identity theft** - hackers could use stolen personal information for identity theft and fraudulent activities.
- **Financial fraud** - user payment details compromised in the breach could be used for unauthorized transactions and financial fraud.
- **Privacy invasion** - exposure of location information could compromise user privacy and safety, leading to potential stalking or surveillance. Intel from data breaches, or data leaks, could easily be used for malicious purposes, possibly invading the data subject's privacy.
- **Trust and reputation damage** - EasyPark's data breaches erode user trust and confidence in the company's ability to protect user personal information. Users may feel betrayed and vulnerable, leading to a loss of trust in the brand. Negative publicity surrounding the breach can further damage the company's reputation, resulting in decreased user engagement.

References

- EasyPark. (2023). Update on EasyPark data breach. <https://www.easypark.com/en-nl/comm>
- Porcedda, M. G. (2018). Patching the patchwork: appraising the EU regulatory framework on cyber security breaches. *Computer law & security review*, 34(5), 1077-1098.
- Meyvis, B. J. L. (2022). *Privacy-friendly Parking Billing* (Master's thesis).
- Gaspari, F. Policy and legal challenges in implementing smart cities. *Smart Governments, Regions and Cities*, 51.

- Techradar. (2023). EasyPark data breach may affect millions of customers. <https://www.techradar.com/pro/security/easypark-data-breach-may-affect-millions-of-customers>
- DSS, W. I. P., & COMPLY, W. N. T. (2010). Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard (PCI DSS). *Payment Card Industry Security Standards Council (PCI SSC)*.
- Goldman, E. (2020). An introduction to the california consumer privacy act (ccpa). *Santa Clara Univ. Legal Studies Research Paper*.
- The Guardian. (2023). Hackers steal customer data from Europe’s largest parking app operator. <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2023/dec/26/hackers-steal-customer-data-europe-parking-app-easypark-ringgo-parkmobile>

#5 Waze – Data breach and data misuse

Waze data breach and misuse – real-time user tracking vulnerabilities

User context

Google Waze is a popular free GPS navigation software app available both on Android and iOS which is designed to help commuters navigate traffic by socially connecting users. Users are able to update the app with many different traffic-related content so that other users can avoid those trouble spots.

Business model

Waze operates on a crowd-sourced model, where users contribute data about traffic conditions, accidents, and other incidents to improve navigation accuracy. For example, if there is an accident that occurs in one person’s location, the user can click the app on the phone and make a warning comment in real-time. This allows commuters to reroute the path that is travelled in order to avoid these complications. From traffic-avoiding re-routes, real-time safety updates and low gas price alerts, Waze is a community that enables millions of people to interact through the app on a daily basis. Waze monetizes its platform through location-based advertising and partnerships with businesses seeking to reach potential customers based on their real-time location data.

Incident date

In 2016, Waze was reportedly under attack but denied that hackers are able to manipulate its systems.

Incident description

Reports emerged about a data misuse incident involving Google Waze, wherein attackers exploited a vulnerability to access sensitive user information. This breach allowed unauthorized access to users' location data and personal information stored within the app's servers. Attackers could potentially track users' whereabouts and access their personal details, posing a significant threat to user privacy and security. However, Waze released statements stating that was not the case and reassured app users that strangers could not search or find Waze users on the map and follow them. The company added in a blog post that their ecosystem was built on trust and deep respect for its customers. They added that they are constantly reviewing and adding safeguards to protect users and that Wazers' account data was safe. Waze also recommended to users who were worried about their privacy to activate the "invisible mode".

To prove otherwise, a handful of researchers were allowed to discover ways to exploit vulnerabilities within Waze. Some examples:

1. University of California Santa Barbara researchers – discovered that they could create “ghost riders” that could attack other users. The fake user profiles they created could be used to spy on other real profiles (Wazers) that were close to their location, allowing the fake users to monitor other users movements as well as creating fake traffic jams or alerts. The team of researchers were able to track an American reporter across two US states for three full days using the fake profiles. After so doing, they reported to Waze which appreciated their work and told them that they had implemented safeguards to address this vulnerability and prevent ghost riders from affecting system behaviour.
2. Two students were assigned by Technion – Israel Institute of Technology – to hijack the Waze app by fake bots. The students, with the assistance of their advisers, created a virtual program that successfully caused the app to report fake traffic jams. The assignment had no evil intention to cause damage to the app but instead wanted to demonstrate what a malicious hacker could do by creating fake traffic jams on the app.

Identified risks

- **Data breach** – the primary risk is a data breach, compromising users' sensitive information stored within the app, including location data, personal identifiers, and navigation history. This exposes users to privacy violations, identity theft, and targeted advertising based on their location.
- **Loss of trust** – a data breach decreases user trust in the company's ability to protect their privacy and security. Users may perceive the app as untrustworthy and refrain from using it, resulting in decreased user engagement. Additionally, on Waze's side, decreased user trust can potentially lead to loss of market share.
- **Reputational damage** – negative publicity surrounding the data misuse incident tarnishes the company's reputation and brand image. Customers may associate Waze with privacy concerns and data insecurity, impacting its credibility and competitive position in the market.
- **Regulatory non-compliance** – data misuse may violate data protection laws and regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe. Failure to comply with regulatory requirements exposes the company to legal liability, fines, and penalties.
- **User safety** – Intel from data breaches, or data leaks, could easily be used for malicious purposes, possibly invading the data subject's privacy.

References

- Garg, R. (2018). Open data privacy and security policy issues and its influence on embracing the Internet of Things. *First Monday*.
- International Association of Privacy Professionals. Waze responds to, downplays reports of security exploit. (2016). <https://iapp.org/news/a/waze-responds-to-downplays-reports-of-security-exploit/>
- Silicon UK. (2016). Waze Flaw Means Hackers Could Now Follow You Home. <https://www.silicon.co.uk/security/security-management/waze-flaw-tracking-hackers-cars-190968>
- Skov, J. (2017). New Urban Mobility Ecosystem.

- Hack Read. Waze app has more than 130 million active monthly users globally and that makes it a lucrative target for hackers. (2020). <https://www.hackread.com/waze-app-vulnerability-attackers-tracking-users-location/>
- ICO. Understanding and assessing risk in personal data breaches. (2023). <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/advice-for-small-organisations/understanding-and-assessing-risk-in-personal-data-breaches/>.
- King, N. J., & Raja, V. T. (2012). Protecting the privacy and security of sensitive customer data in the cloud. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 28(3), 308-319.
- Goldman, E. (2020). An introduction to the california consumer privacy act (ccpa). *Santa Clara Univ. Legal Studies Research Paper*.

#6 Blink Mobility - data breach

Data leak exposes user information from car-sharing service Blink Mobility.

User context

Blink Mobility is an app-based electric car rental platform. Riders can find a nearby car, pick it up by unlocking it via their app & then drop it off at designated parking stations. The app allows riders to begin their membership, find & rent vehicles, use them as the vehicle's smart key, see their rental history, and manage their membership.

Business model

BlueLA powered by Blink Mobility, is a 100% electric car-sharing service and part of the City of Los Angeles' mobility strategy. The service is available to anyone over 18 years of age with a valid driver's license. Members have access to a network of shared electric vehicles 24-hours a day, seven days a week, at self-service locations throughout central Los Angeles. It is a point-to-point service, which means you can return the vehicle at any of the designated BlueLA powered by Blink Mobility locations.

In 2015, The City of Los Angeles was awarded a grant from the California Air Resources Board through [California Climate Investments](#) - a statewide initiative that puts billions of cap-and-trade dollars to work reducing greenhouse gas emissions, strengthening the economy, and improving public health - to pilot electric vehicle car-sharing in low-income communities of Los Angeles. Former BlueLA Car sharing began operating the service in partnership with the Los Angeles Department of Transportation (LADOT).

Blink Mobility acquired fledgling BlueLA in late 2020 and implemented a robust million-dollar improvement initiative bringing all-new electric vehicles and upgraded charging stations to the program as well as an improved mobile app and member experience.

Project implementation and outreach efforts are supported by the LA Mayor's Office of Sustainability, Shared Use Mobility Center, and a committee of community-based organizations.

Incident date

2023

Incident description

Blink Mobility left a misconfigured MongoDB database open to the public. Its metadata was then indexed by search engines and discovered by Cybernews researchers on October 17th.

The investigation revealed that the database contained more than 22,000 users with 181,000 records, mostly about car rentals.

The database included the personally identifiable information of Blink Mobility customers and administrators.

Identified risks

The actual root cause of the data leak was the misconfiguration of the Data Storage (MongoDB) which allowed the access without any authentication method to be enforced. Additionally, it is against best practices for a data storage to have publicly accessible endpoints.

References

- <https://blinkmobility.com/about-blink-mobility/>
- https://tracxn.com/d/companies/blink-mobility/_InY0Ik180Eg3CQIayrkQAB9StqiXS9uWWbFGxl_S5wY
- <https://blinkcharging.com/business-models/>
- <https://chaslescorp.com/data-leak-exposes-user-information-from-car-sharing-service-blink-mobility/>

#7 Blablacar – Data theft

Hackers copy user data from BlaBlaCar's defunct car-pooling platforms, mitfahrgelegenheit.de and mitfahrzentrale.de.

User context

BlaBlaCar, a prominent carpooling platform, facilitates ride-sharing services through its online platform, connecting drivers with passengers for shared journeys. The platform caters to a diverse user base, including commuters, travellers, and individuals seeking cost-effective transportation options. BlaBlaCar users typically value convenience, affordability, and environmental sustainability, opting for shared rides to reduce expenses and carbon emissions (BlaBlaCar 2022).

Business model

BlaBlaCar operates on a peer-to-peer ride-sharing model, allowing drivers to offer available seats in their vehicles to passengers traveling in the same direction. The platform leverages real-time dynamic algorithms to match drivers and passengers based on their travel preferences, departure times, and routes. BlaBlaCar emphasizes user safety and trust, implementing verification processes and user reviews to ensure a secure and reliable ride-sharing experience. By facilitating ride-sharing, BlaBlaCar aims to optimize vehicle occupancy, reduce traffic congestion, and promote social connections among users.

Incident date

The BlaBlaCar data breach occurred at the end of October 2015.

Incident description

BlaBlaCar is operated by a company called Comuto which has divisions in 21 countries. In October 2015, cybercriminals targeted Comuto Deutschland's defunct car-pooling platforms,

mitfahrgelegenheit.de and mitfahrzentrale.de, stealing user data from their databases. The attack affected around 15% of the users of these portals. The stolen information included more than 600,000 bank account details, 101,000 email addresses, 15,000 mobile phone numbers, usernames, and physical addresses of customers (Schirmmacher 2016). It is believed that the breach was orchestrated by a Russian hacking group. It compromised archived data from the two German car-pooling platforms, which were merged with BlaBlaCar in 2015. However, Comuto confirmed that there is no evidence of misuse of the leaked data. Additionally, they also claimed that the breach did not affect the data of its current BlaBlaCar users, since its data is protected and stored separately from the cloud solution. The incident was attributed to human error in the anonymization process of the acquired platforms' databases and a hotline was set up to identify and support the affected users.

Identified risks

Due to the sensitivity of the leaked data, this cyber attack was claimed to be a “very targeted attack”. However, it was a relief that the individual data sets were not systematically linked to each other. For instance, the exposed account number could not be linked to the corresponding names or email IDs, reducing the risk of cyber theft.

Nevertheless, the BlaBlaCar data breach has raised concerns about user privacy and data security, potentially leading to a loss of trust among customers. The unauthorized access to sensitive information, including bank account details and personal contact information, exposes affected users to risks such as identity theft, financial fraud, and phishing attacks. Hence, the incident emphasizes the importance of robust cybersecurity measures and compliance with data protection regulations.

References

- 600,000 car-sharing users' details stolen in cyber-attack. (2016, November 29). The Local Germany. <https://www.thelocal.de/index.php/20161129/600000-car-sharing-users-details-stolen-in-new-cyber-attack>
- BlaBlaCar (2022). Bus oder Mitfahrt? Jetzt günstige Fahrten finden. BlaBlaCar. Retrieved 15 February 2024, from <https://www.blablacar.de/>
- Data theft at carpooling provider BlaBlaCar—Online portal of IT Management. (2016, November 29). <https://www.it-daily.net/shortnews/daten-diebstahl-bei-mitfahr-anbieter-blablacar>
- Goud, N. (2016, November 29). Cyber attack on German Car sharing website leaks critical details. Cybersecurity Insiders. <https://www.cybersecurity-insiders.com/cyber-attack-on-german-car-sharing-website-leaks-critical-details/>
- Ostermaier, S. (2016, November 29). mitfahrgelegenheit.de und mitfahrzentrale.de: Daten von ehemaligen Nutzern gestohlen. <https://stadt-bremerhaven.de/mitfahrgelegenheit-de-und-mitfahrzentrale-de-daten-von-ehemaligen-nutzern-gestohlen/>
- Schirmmacher, D. (2016, November 29). Hacker kopieren Nutzer-Daten von Mitfahrgelegenheit.de und Mitfahrzentrale.de. Security. <https://www.heise.de/news/Hacker-kopieren-Nutzer-Daten-von-Mitfahrgelegenheit-de-und-Mitfahrzentrale-de-3507285.html>
- Wirtschaftswoche. (2016, November 29). Hackerangriff: Daten von Mitfahrgelegenheit.de bei BlaBlaCar-Betreiber gestohlen. <https://www.wiwo.de/unternehmen/dienstleister/hackerangriff-daten-von-mitfahrgelegenheit-de-bei-blablacar-betreiber-gestohlen/14908938.html>

#8 Careem - Data breach

A security breach that compromised personal information of 14 million Careem customers and 558 800 captains (drivers).

User context

Careem, is a ride-hailing/ car booking platform based in UAE and operating across 13 countries and 90 cities with its major prominence in the MENA, Turkey, and Pakistan (Careem, 2018). Its services are primarily accessed through smartphone applications, catering to a diverse range of users in urban centres. Careem's customer base consists of individuals seeking convenient transportation options, often tech-savvy and residing in metropolitan areas.

Business model

Careem's business model revolves around providing on-demand transportation services through its mobile application. It utilizes sophisticated algorithms to match customers with nearby captains, offering real-time ride booking and tracking. Dynamic pricing mechanisms are utilized to fluctuate fares in response to demand, thereby maximizing revenue while also ensuring a sufficient number of drivers are available during periods of high demand.

Incident date

The cyber breach was identified on 14th January 2018, but published by Careem on 23rd April 2018.

Incident description

The breach compromised the names, email addresses, phone numbers, and trip data of all the individuals who signed up for Careem services before January 14th. Notably, passwords and credit card information remained unaffected. The breach impacted approximately 14 million riders and 558,800 drivers (captains) (Kharpal, 2018).

Identified risks

Sensitive information like the customers' credit card numbers and passwords were stored on an external third-party PCI-compliant server, which uses highly secure protocols and is typically employed by international banks around the globe to protect financial information. Due to this level of security, there was no evidence of exposed credit card numbers or passwords. However, the incident posed significant risks to customer privacy and data security, undermining trust in Careem's services. Even though no evidence of fraud or misuse was reported, the breach highlighted vulnerabilities in Careem's security infrastructure, necessitating immediate action to address concerns and reinforce data protection measures.

References

- SOPHOS News (2018, April 25). Ride-hailing service Careem lost 14 million users' data... in January. <https://news.sophos.com/en-us/2018/04/25/ride-hailing-service-careem-lost-14-million-users-data-in-january/>
- Dawn.com. (17:06:58+05:00). Careem users' personal data compromised in massive data breach. DAWN.COM. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1403401>
- Dickey, M. R. (2018, April 23). Ride-hailing app Careem reveals data breach affecting 14 million people. TechCrunch. <https://techcrunch.com/2018/04/23/careem-data-breach/>

- Dubai's Careem hit by cyber attack affecting 14 million users. (2018, April 24). Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/article/idUSKBN1HU1WJ/>
- Careem (2018, April 23). *Important Careem Security Information*, Careem Blog. Retrieved 16 February 2024, from <https://blog.careem.com/posts/security>
- Kharpal, A. (2018, April 23). *Middle East Uber rival Careem says data of 14 million drivers and riders stolen in cyberattack*. CNBC. <https://www.cnbc.com/2018/04/23/careem-says-data-of-14-million-drivers-and-riders-stolen-in-cyberattack.html>
- Khaleej Times (2018, April 23). *Dubai's Careem admits to data breach of 14 million users*. Retrieved 16 February 2024, from <https://www.khaleejtimes.com/uae/dubais-careem-admits-to-data-breach-of-14-million-users>

#9 Uber - Data breach

Data breach that exposed personal information of Uber users and drivers

User context

Uber represents a prominent ride-hailing company, providing its services through smartphone applications. Through these apps, users can conveniently request rides, receiving details such as pickup times, vehicle locations, and fare estimates in advance. Typically, Uber users tend to be tech-savvy individuals, often younger with higher incomes, and residing in urban areas near city centres (Gomez et al., 2021).

Business model

Utilizing real-time dynamic algorithms, Uber's platform flexibly adjusts fares to reflect fluctuations in supply and demand. This system, known as dynamic pricing or "surge pricing", automatically increases fares during periods of high demand when the supply of drivers is limited in specific areas. Consequently, passengers may experience higher fares during peak demand times. However, users are typically notified of fare increases before requesting a ride. This dynamic pricing strategy is integral to Uber's business model, allowing the company to optimize revenue and efficiently manage demand fluctuations (Rangel et al., 2022).

Incident date

The Uber data breach occurred in 2016.

Incident description

During the data breach that occurred in 2016, hackers gained unauthorized access to Uber's systems and obtained personal information of approximately 57 million Uber users and drivers. The stolen data included names, email addresses, phone numbers, and driver's license numbers. Initially, Uber attempted to hide the breach by paying \$100,000 to the hackers to delete the stolen data and maintain secrecy about the incident. However, the breach was later revealed in 2017, leading to significant backlash and legal repercussions for Uber.

Identified risks

The incident, along with the attempted cover-up, resulted in a loss of customer trust and raised concerns about Uber's commitment to data security and privacy. The lack of transparency and the company's handling of the breach further damaged its reputation, ultimately affecting its position among consumers, investors, and regulators.

References

- Gomez, J., Aguilera-García, Á., Dias, F. F., Bhat, C. R., & Vassallo, J. M. (2021). Adoption and frequency of use of ride-hailing services in a European city: The case of Madrid. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 131 (August). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2021.103359>
- Rangel, T., Gonzalez, J. N., Gomez, J., Romero, F., & Vassallo, J. M. (2022). Exploring ride-hailing fares: an empirical analysis of the case of Madrid. *Transportation*, 49(2), 373–393. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-021-10180-w>
- <https://sk.sagepub.com/cases/uber-cyber-breaches?token=85cb0558-90d8-44eb-a808-1fdec74c6ce6e2242575ce1027c2f32bf66a6e528b48016e833ab1a5b724ba1410aaa97770d>
- <https://www.trendmicro.com/vinfo/pl/security/news/cybercrime-and-digital-threats/uber-breach-exposes-the-data-of-57-million-drivers-and-users>
- <https://news.sophos.com/es-es/2022/10/06/condenan-al-ex-cso-de-uber-por-encubrir-una-mega-brecha-en-2016/>
- <https://www.cybersaint.io/blog/uber-hack-undisclosed>

#10 Bycyklen – Database hacked

The database of the Bycyklen shared bike provider in Copenhagen city was hacked and deleted, disabling access to the shared bikes.

User context

Bycyklen is a paid bicycle sharing system featuring electric bicycles equipped with a GPS routing device allowing users to book rides with their Android and iOS apps.

Business model

Bycyklen is a company providing on-demand electric bicycle booking services. The company provides electric bicycles which can be locked/unlocked electronically, tracked using GPS, and it includes a tablet for users to control the bike and view information. Users can book a bicycle online through the Bycyklen webpage or directly from the tablet attached to the bicycle. Once booked, users can open their bikes using their unique user id and pin. Bicycles can be picked up and returned to any of the pre-specified docking stations.

Incident date

4-5 May 2018

Incident description

The computer system responsible for controlling and managing operations of Copenhagen city's bicycle sharing system Bycyklen was hacked by unknown hackers with in-depth knowledge of how the system worked.

The Bycyklen bikes work in conjunction with an Android tablet that connects to the Bycyklen database which stores details of the bikes scattered around the city. Without the database, users cannot retrieve the bikes from their racks.

The hackers deleted the Bycyklen database. Therefore, users were unable to access the 1 860 Bycyklen bikes and the bikes had to be manually rebooted by the company.

It is unclear which vulnerability the hackers exploited. No user data was stolen.

The company communicated that it did not store payment card information but that only user e-mail addresses, phone numbers, and PIN codes are stored on the server, and that all user PINs and passwords are stored in an encrypted format (so-called “salted password hashing”), which makes it impossible for hackers or the company itself to read the data. Users were nevertheless advised to change their PIN codes. The company further communicated that it seemed a rather “primitive” hack, probably carried out by a person with a great deal of knowledge of the structure of the Bycyklen system.

Identified risks

Details are limited on how the hackers were actually able to delete the database. Was the system really “hacked” or did a Bycyklen employee have the knowledge and power to delete the Bycyklen database?

From the limited information available, it seems there was insufficient security to access and/or delete the internal database.

References

- https://tracxn.com/d/companies/bycyklen/_K4jCuvjB6AOp5NVV8BGU100MI9vuG_0137i31RiFiLM
- <https://portswigger.net/daily-swig/breach-shuts-down-bike-sharing-system>
- <https://www.hackread.com/copenhagen-citys-bicycle-sharing-system-hacked/>
- <https://www.bleepingcomputer.com/news/security/hacker-shuts-down-copenhagen-s-public-city-bikes-system/>
- <https://shared-micromobility.com/hackers-attacked-bycyklen-in-copenhagen/>

#11 CityScoot - GDPR violation

On March 16, 2023, the Commission Nationale de l’Informatique et des Libertés (CNIL, France) fined a scooter rental company €125 000 for various GDPR violations, including for example the unlawful collection of geolocation data.

User context

Cityscoot offers fully electric, free-floating scooters via a mobile application. The service operates in Paris, Milan, and Turin.

Business model

Any adult over 18 who is authorized to drive a 50cc equivalent scooter can use the service. Riders born before 01/01/1998 do not need a permit to use the service. Riders born after 01/01/1998 must have a valid driver’s license.

Registration is free. Riders pay for their rentals per minute. Cityscoot charges the outstanding balance when it reaches 10 euros or more. Otherwise, riders are charged at the beginning of the following month for their rental.

There are different pricing models per city, though it is difficult to find consistent pricing information across the Cityscoot website.

In Paris:

- The basic Cityscoot rate in Paris is €0.46 per minute.
- Riders can pay for a monthly subscription: €129 per month for up to 500 minutes.
- Paris also offers a 24-hour CityPass for €30, with unlimited minutes.
- Riders can buy pre-paid “CityRider” packs. These packs cost €70 for 250 minutes, €32 for 100 minutes, or €17 for 50 minutes.
- CityPacks cost €75 for 250 minutes, €34 for 100 minutes, €18 for 50 minutes, or €11 for 30 minutes.
- Cityscoot also offers “CityPro” to employers. These packs cost €26 for 100 minutes.

Cityscoot’s mobile application offers a navigation service to find a scooter near the user’s location. To accommodate this, all scooters are equipped with an embedded tracking device that allows both Cityscoot and its riders to know the position of the scooters via the app. Via this tracking device, Cityscoot collected data every 30 seconds to know the position of the scooter while it was in use.

After finding and booking a scooter, users have 10 minutes to reach and unlock it using a code that is displayed within the application. Riders can cancel their reservation for free within that period. Reservations are also automatically cancelled when the rider does not unlock the scooter within the 10 minutes.

Scooters are equipped with a helmet, which is stored within the saddle. Cityscoot also takes care of charging the scooters.

Cityscoot is partnered with Allianz, which insures riders during their rental. Coverage is included in the rental price, and users are automatically subscribed. Insurance covers accidents and dead batteries.

Scooters can be parked in any space authorized for motorized two-wheelers within the “Cityscoot Zone”. Riders are responsible for any parking fines incurred within their rental. To stop a rental, riders must either press a button on the scooter keypad or use the mobile application.

Incident date

In May 2020, CNIL organized an investigation into Cityscoot’s website and mobile application. The final decision was made in March 2023.

Incident description

In 2020, the CNIL conducted a number of investigations on topics related to everyday concerns of the French people, including for example geolocation for local services. In this context, CNIL launched an investigation into Cityscoot’s data collection practices.

Three main results of the investigation:

1. All scooters were equipped with electronic boxes that contained a SIM card and a GPS geolocation system. Geolocation data was collected every 30 seconds while the scooter was active and every 15 minutes while it was not. Cityscoot also kept a record of this data for 12 months in an active database, then 12 months in intermediate archiving, after which, it was anonymized. According to Cityscoot, this data was collected to handle traffic offenses, handle complaints and claims, manage theft, offer user support, and prevent overbilling.

CNIL ruled that the data collection every 30 seconds was too excessive for these purposes, and fined Cityscoot €100 000 for a GDPR violation.

2. Cityscoot had contracts with 15 data processors that did not contain all the information required by GDPR. CNIL found that these contracts were incomplete. For example, one processor did not explain what will happen with the data at the end of the contract, while another did not describe any measures they would take to ensure the security of the data. The €100,000 fine noted in point 1 also considers this violation.
3. Cityscoot's website did not contain any information about cookies and did not ask for consent for processing users' data when creating an account, logging in, or undergoing the forgotten password procedure. Data was collected and transmitted to Google for analysis, via a reCAPTCHA mechanism. For this violation, CNIL fined Cityscoot €25,000.

Identified risks

According to CNIL's restricted training deliberation in March 2023, when a vehicle is rented, its geolocation data can be associated with a person and thus constitutes personal data. Cityscoot kept separate databases of scooters, reservations, and customers, but this data could also be cross-referenced. Furthermore, although geolocation data is not part of a special category of data within the GDPR, CNIL also noted that this type of data can be considered 'sensitive', as it can impact the rider's freedom of movement and reveal information such as his/her workplace, residence, etc. Therefore, collecting geolocation data every 30 seconds is excessive in relation to the purposes for which Cityscoot outlined.

References

- Alerion Avocats: <https://www.alerionavocats.com/en/vehicle-tracking-french-dpa-sanction/>
- BDK Advokati: <https://bdkadvokati.com/cnil-consistently-censures-continual-collection-of-geolocation-data/>
- Cityscoot: <https://www.cityscoot.eu/en/paris>
- CNIL: <https://www.cnil.fr/en/geolocation-rental-scooters-cityscoot-fined-eu125000#:~:text=On%2016%20March%202023%2C%20the,by%20geolocating%20them%20almost%20permanently>
- <https://www.cnil.fr/fr/geolocalisation-de-scooters-de-location-sanction-de-125-000-euros-lencontre-de-cityscoot>
- European Data Protection Board: https://edpb.europa.eu/news/national-news/2023/french-sa-fines-cityscoot-125-000eu_en
- GDPR Hub: [https://gdprhub.eu/index.php?title=CNIL_\(France\)_-_SAN-2023-003](https://gdprhub.eu/index.php?title=CNIL_(France)_-_SAN-2023-003)
- Legifrance: https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/cnil/id/CNILTEXT000047346903?page=1&pageSize=10&query=2016%252F679&searchField=ALL&searchType=ALL&sortValue=DATE_DECISION_DES_C&tab_selection=cnil&typePaging=DEFAULT
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/scoot-capture-cnil-takes-precise-geolocation-recaptcha-odia-kagan/>
- Rodl & Partner: <https://www.roedl.it/it/temi/data-protection-bites/4-2023/french-cnil-fine-against-french-sme-multiple-infringement-data-protection-cookies-regulations>

#12 Lyft – Privacy abuse

Lyft investigates whether its employees abused rider data.

User context

Lyft provides ride-sharing services via an app where it matches users with nearby drivers who will pick them up and take them where they want to go. After creating an account and logging in to the app, the user just taps the request in the app, including origin and destination point. Through the Lyft app a carefully-screened driver will be on their way to the user – at the pickup point. The user sees a photo of its driver and the car, as well as their ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival). In addition, the user can watch the location of the vehicle as it approaches them on a map, and call the driver if something changes, e.g. starts raining, the road is blocked etc. Finally, once the driver arrives, the user confirms the name and destination, get in to start the ride.

Business model

Lyft Inc., founded in 2007, is a leading American mobility services company. Operating in the United States and Canada, Lyft provides on-demand ride-sharing through its marketplace, connecting drivers and riders. The company offers a diverse range of transportation options, including flexible car rentals, rentals for long-distance trips, and shared bikes and scooters for short rides. Additionally, Lyft integrates third-party public transit data into its app to provide comprehensive transportation solutions.

Incident date

Lyft had to investigate anonymously posted allegations that some employees abused their position by spying on customers' private data in 2018. Following these claims, Lyft spokeswoman Alexandra LaManna said in an emailed statement to BBC News "Maintaining the trust of passengers and drivers is fundamental to Lyft".

Incident description

Lyft faced a scandal involving the unauthorized access and misuse of customers' private data by its staff. The incident came to light when anonymous claims were posted online alleging that employees were abusing customer insight software to access personal information, including trip data. In more detail, the unauthorized access to Lyft's backend software allowed employees to view unmasked personally identifiable information, including location and movement logs, financial details and private communications. The accusations included instances of staff looking up the trip data of former romantic partners and tracking high-profile users such as celebrities. In response to the allegations, Lyft initiated an investigation into the claims and acknowledged that the specific actions described in the post would be a violation of the company's policies, potentially leading to termination of employees' contracts.

Identified risks

This case highlights two main issues: a) misrepresenting the extent to which it monitored its employees' access to personal information about users and drivers, and b) the necessary steps to secure that data.

- Data misuse and security problems:
 - Security of data
 - Exposed personal data
- Privacy violations and trust damage
- Vulnerabilities in systems

References

- <https://www.lyft.com/blog/posts/how-does-lyft-work>
- <https://www.forbes.com/companies/lyft/>
- <https://finance.yahoo.com/quote/LYFT/profile/>
- <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-42827636>
- <https://www.cnet.com/news/privacy/lyft-reportedly-limits-employees-access-to-customer-data/>
- <https://www.vox.com/2014/11/21/11633164/lyft-limits-employee-access-to-data-after-recode-report>
- <https://techcrunch.com/2018/01/25/lyft-god-view/>
- <https://www.thedrive.com/tech/27516/lyfts-new-data-restrictions-may-not-be-enough-to-keep-creepy-employees-from-snooping-on-users>

#13 Ledger – Cyber attack

Dump of the content of a Ledger customer database

User context

A digital key is required to access a crypto wallet. This key is accessed either online or via special hardware (e.g., a USB wallet stick). In the case of a USB wallet stick, the crypto wallet can only be used if the stick is plugged into the computer. To protect this stick from theft or misuse, it is usually stored in a safe.

Business model

Ledger is developing hardware wallet technology that provides the highest level of security for crypto assets. Their products combine a Secure Element and a proprietary OS designed specifically to protect the customers assets.

Ledger only sold these wallet sticks online (as of 2020.07).

Incident date

Ledger informed customers about a data leak in July 2020.

Incident description

At that time, Ledger managed contact data (name, address, account creation date, email and telephone number) in its own customer database. This database could be queried from outside with special authorization via an API.

Identified risks

Hackers gained access to this database with a compromised API key and extracted customer data. According to official reports, initially around 1 000 000 email addresses and 10 000 complete customer data records were stolen. At a later stage, a further 270 000 complete customer data records were stolen.

Even though no crypto wallet data was stolen, the stolen data records contained customer names, addresses and telephone numbers as well as the creation date of the customer account. The age of the account can be used to identify presumably wealthy customers to make specific threats to them. These threats include phone calls, SPAM e-mails and visits at home. The combination of home address and telephone number seems particularly critical here. There is also a risk that these contact details will be distributed further on the Darknet.

References

<https://www.ledger.com> (2024.02.11)

#14 Public Hospital - Cryptolocker

Cryptolocker-ransomware attack to public hospital.

User context

Hospital staff accessing email systems and computer networks for administrative and clinical purposes.

Business model

The public hospital provides healthcare services, including medical treatment, diagnostics, and patient care. Computer systems are an integral part of managing patient records, scheduling appointments, and communication among healthcare professionals.

Incident date

The incident occurred between 2015 and 2016.

Incident description

A cryptolocker ransomware attack targeted the hospital's computer network, initiated through the opening of a malicious email by a user. The ransomware spread, affecting the cardiology department initially. To contain the spread, immediate measures were taken to isolate the physical LAN (Local Area Network), initially confining the virus to one wing of the hospital. Subsequently, backups of critical information were made for practicality. Swift identification and effective countermeasures were pivotal in mitigating the impact. The hospital staff received specific training on identifying suspicious emails containing links to prevent further incidents.

Identified risks

- Risk of patient data loss or compromise due to the ransomware attack
- Potential disruption of hospital operations and patient care
- Financial losses associated with remediation efforts and potential ransom payments

#15 TfL Oyster cards - Credential stuffing

Transport for London customers unable to check balance or top up their Oyster cards in London.

User context

Transport for London (TfL) oversees the public transportation network in London, including the Tube, Overground, and bus services. The Oyster Card system, introduced in June 2003, is a key component of London's public transport infrastructure (Burgess 2019). Oyster cards are used by millions of commuters and travellers to conveniently pay for travel across various modes of transportation. The Oyster Card website allows users to manage their accounts, top up card balances, purchase season tickets, and set up automatic payment schedules. TfL's customers, who rely on the Oyster Card system, typically include commuters, tourists, and residents of London, many of whom are tech-savvy individuals familiar with using digital services for transportation purposes.

Business model

TfL's Oyster Card system operates on a prepaid fare collection model, where users preload their Oyster cards with funds to pay for transportation services. The system offers convenience and flexibility to users, allowing them to tap their cards on card readers to access trains, buses, and other forms of transportation seamlessly. The Oyster Card system also provides data insights to TfL, enabling the organization to analyze travel patterns, optimize service routes, and improve overall efficiency. By offering an integrated and user-friendly payment solution, TfL aims to enhance the travel experience for passengers and encourage the use of public transportation in London.

Incident date

The Oyster card data breach occurred in August 2019.

Incident description

Transport for London (TfL) detected unauthorized access to user accounts on its Oyster Card website in August 2019. However, the Oyster Online service was not directly breached. Instead, malicious actors exploited some exposed user login credentials obtained from non-TfL websites, using a technique known as credential stuffing. This affected approximately 2000 of over 2.5 million active user accounts (TfL Oyster Hack, 2020). Although no customer payment details were compromised, TfL took immediate action to protect customer data by temporarily suspending all online and contactless Oyster accounts. The Oyster website was thus 'temporarily unavailable' for all users and users could only update their Oyster cards using the app and at ticket machines in stations. The organization also initiated additional security measures, notified the impacted customers of the incident and recommended them to contact the customer service team in case of any suspicious activity in their accounts.

Despite the breach, TfL reassured customers that its own systems remained secure, and the payment systems across the London transport network continued to operate without disruption.

Identified risks

Despite of being an indirect breach caused due to the reuse of password on multiple websites, the Oyster Card hack resulted in a loss of customer trust and raised concerns about Transport for London's (TfL) commitment to data security and privacy. The unauthorized access to user

accounts, coupled with the exploitation of exposed login credentials, exposed customers to potential risks such as identity theft, fraud, and unauthorized access to personal information.

References

- Breach of Oyster data (1) | London City Hall. (2020). <https://www.london.gov.uk/who-we-are/what-london-assembly-does/questions-mayor/find-an-answer/breach-oyster-data-1>
- Burgess, M. (2019, August 8). TfL kills the Oyster website as customers are hit by a dumb hack. Wired UK. <https://www.wired.co.uk/article/tfl-oyster-hack-customer-service>
- TfL Oyster Hack | London City Hall. (2020). <https://www.london.gov.uk/who-we-are/what-london-assembly-does/questions-mayor/find-an-answer/tfl-oyster-hack>
- TfL's Oyster service taken offline after hack. (2019, August 8). The Independent. <https://www.independent.co.uk/tech/tfl-oyster-tube-service-top-up-online-down-not-working-hack-a9047441.html>

#16 CODT – Cyber attack

Ransomware attack on Colorado department of transportation

User context

The CDOT is a US state agency that is funded by the state of Colorado. Its main goal is to offer multi modal transportation system for Colorado.

Business model

As a state agency, the CDOT does not have any business model.

Incident date

February 2018

Incident description

Between February 21-23, 2018, a threat actor executed a ransomware attack on the Colorado Department of Transportation (CDOT) that ultimately affected roughly half of the Department's computers.

Root cause analysis revealed several vulnerabilities related to a newly created Internet-accessible virtual server with direct connection to the CDOT network and administrative privileges that did not have OIT security controls in place. This server was compromised within two days of creation and was under SamSam ransomware attack within one additional day. Containment, eradication, and recovery of services required approximately four weeks.

Though CDOT operations were degraded, CDOT continued to execute its core mission to provide a multi modal transportation system for Colorado. This success may be attributed to a sound Continuity of Operations Plan that allowed CDOT to continue to operate.

Identified risks

Operation of the system was down for 4 weeks

References

- <https://coloradosun.com/2020/02/03/how-samsam-ransomware-took-down-cdot-and-how-the-state-fought-back-twice/>
- <https://www.itskrs.its.dot.gov/2019-I00856>

#17 DPD – AI Chatbot fails

Chatbot insults company

User context

A disappointed customer of the parcel delivery service DPD simply wanted to ask customer service about the whereabouts of his delivery. Customer service, an AI-powered chatbot, was unable to help him and not a single question was answered satisfactorily.

When the customer realized that he was dealing with a chatbot, he made fun of it, was able to elicit answers from the chatbot that were unfavorable for the company and ultimately made these answers public on a social media platform.

Business model

For a full service the parcel delivery service DPD also provides a customer service that can be contacted through multiple channels. One of these channels is a less cost intensive chatbot controlled by artificial intelligence to answer customer questions.

Incident date

The musician Ashley Beauchamp released the unfavorable chat history with the DPD chatbot on January 18, 2024.

Incident description

The original post of Ashley Beauchamp on X (Twitter):

“Parcel delivery firm DPD have replaced their customer service chat with an AI robot thing. It’s utterly useless at answering any queries, and when asked, it happily produced a poem about how terrible they are as a company. It also swore at me.”

The parcel delivery company DPD has replaced its customer service employees with an AI-supported chatbot. Unfortunately, this chatbot got out of control and one customer even managed to get insulted by this chatbot and this chatbot even criticized its own company.

For example this chatbot even convinced that:

- DPD is the worst delivery service in the world, and
- that one should never recommend this courier service

and the chatbot could also be forced:

- to recommend better delivery services, or
- to respond with more hostility.

Identified risks

Chatbots may misinterpret or misunderstand queries, particularly those containing complex or ambiguous sentences. This can result in incorrect responses or confusion.

Quality and content of Training Data is important to create the wanted behaviour of the chatbot.

So, if the training data is biased, this bias will also drive the behaviour of this service. This can lead to unintended prejudices and discriminatory or unfair responses or to response against the company or the customer.

In principle, AI systems could also get out of control in other directions or exhibit unforeseen behavior, which could lead to other undesirable consequences.

References

- <https://www.foxbusiness.com/technology/dpd-ai-error-causes-chatbot-swear-calls-itself-worst-delivery-service-disgruntled-user-report>
- <https://twitter.com/ashbeauchamp>
- <https://www.derstandard.at/story/3000000204016/dpd-chatbot-schimpft-ueber-den-schlechten-service-der-eigenen-firma>
- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/de/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

#18 google.com - #googlemapshacks

Artists 'fools' Google Maps by creating a virtual traffic jam.

User context

Google Maps is a navigation platform - web and app based - that offers a route planner for different modes and real-time traffic information, complemented by aerial photos, satellite imagery and terrain data. The platform was launched in 2005 and has over 1 billion active users monthly worldwide. In 2007, Google Maps began offering traffic data as a colored overlay on top of roads and motorways to represent the speed of vehicles on roads. Since then, Google Maps has been almost indispensable, helping motorists to find the quickest route to their destination despite accidents or congestion. This has also led motorists to be guided through more remote or residential areas in their "search for the fastest routes", sometimes causing inconvenience in these areas. Google Maps is able to collect this real-time traffic data by collecting data from road authorities, by tracking the location and speed of mobile phones and by using historical patterns of traffic on roads.

Business model

Like most of Google's products, Google Maps generates a substantial portion of its revenue through advertising. Further, businesses can create location-based promotions and offers through Google Maps or businesses can create and manage their listings on Google Maps. In addition, Google Maps allows businesses to integrate Google Maps into their applications and websites using the Google Maps API, for a usage fee. The geolocation data Google Maps collects, including traffic patterns and user behaviour, can be licensed to third-party companies, including government agencies, for a fee. Also, subscription-based services are offered (e.g. Google Maps Platform Premium Plan), providing advanced features and dedicated support to businesses and developers. And lastly, ride-hailing services like Uber are integrated in Google Maps for which Google may receive a commission or referral fee. Google Maps was estimated to have a revenue of over 11 billion dollars in 2023, making it one of Google's most lucrative businesses.

Incident date

2020

Incident description

Under the project name #googlemapshacks, the German artist Simon Weckert managed to fool Google Maps' complex algorithms in a simple way. Armed with a trolley full of smartphones, all sharing their location data with Google, Weckert wandered the streets of Berlin, creating a non-existent traffic jam around the buildings of Germany's Google headquarters. The result was that Google Maps detected as many as 99 cars within a square metre. And this led Google Maps to direct other road users along an alternative route.

FIGURE 75: #googlemapshacks. Artist Simon Weckert walking in Berlin with a trolley full of smartphones and a visual of the traffic jam it created in Google Maps.

(Source: <https://www.simonweckert.com/googlemapshacks.html>)

Identified risks

This is a case of misuse of data by deliberately manipulating the input data used for a tool. Although this was an example showcased by an artist, there have been examples of residents using the same “technique”, as a response to one of the inconveniences of the Google Maps offer – the shortcut routes through residential areas. With a group of concerned residents they stood with their mobile phones near a highly used shortcut route by motorists to create a virtual traffic jam, so that, for that time period, motorists were directed through different roads by Google Maps to avoid the virtual congestion.

References

- <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/investing/061115/how-does-google-maps-makes-money.asp>
- <https://www.feedough.com/how-google-maps-works-makes-money/>
- <https://medium.com/technology-hits/google-maps-a-simple-explanation-on-how-it-detects-traffic-jams-ce6940489c9c>
- <https://www.ad.nl/auto/zo-gemakkelijk-neem-je-google-maps-in-de-maling-opzienbarende-actie-tegen-sluipverkeer~a4e6dd27/?referrer=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com%2F>
- <https://www.simonweckert.com/googlemapshacks.html>

#19 TESLA – Security flaw with keyless entry

Tesla Model S key fobs vulnerable to a low-tech hack

User context

The Model S from US manufacturer Tesla is, like many modern cars, equipped with a 'keyless start' option. With that system, a car key no longer needs to be physically inserted into the lock, but can remain in your jacket pocket or bag. If the key comes near the car, you can open the door and start the car.

Business model

The Tesla business model operates as a Direct-to-Consumer (D2C) business model as it sells directly to the customer, cutting out middlemen such as dealerships, and offering its own charging station network. Currently, Tesla's business model is based on three foundations: selling model, servicing, and charging network. Its most important revenue stream is the sale of electric cars, representing more than 80% of its revenue, which is estimated at more than 20 billion dollars (July 2023). The other 20% of income includes automotive services and vehicle leasing, but also sales of solar energy systems and storage products (about 1.5 billion dollars).

Incident date

September 2018

Incident description

A team of researchers from COSIC, an IMEC research group at KU Leuven, discovered that Tesla has serious weaknesses in the Passive Keyless Entry and Start (PKES) system they used to open the car. The PKES system, designed by the company Pektron, can be found in the Tesla Model S, and in models from McLaren, Karma Automotive and Triumph, among others.

The researchers found that the Tesla Model S's PKES system uses an outdated DST40 cipher⁸⁹. That algorithm, once a Texas Instruments trade secret and very widely used in, for example, petrol cards and car security, was cracked back in 2005. This makes the system unsuitable for modern cars. Retrieving the cryptographic key allows making a copy of the car key to open and start the car.

For this study, the researchers used a Raspberry Pi, a power bank (an external battery), a device with an antenna to receive and send low frequencies, and one for high frequencies. The Tesla sends out a signal at least once a second to check whether the key is nearby. The researchers first passed along the car with the antenna and picked up that signal. Then they passed by the person with the key. Near that person, they captured the key's "response" to the car's signal. By combining these, they were able to crack the cryptographic security and open the car to drive away with it.

The researchers notified Tesla of their findings. The car manufacturer verified and confirmed the findings and gave a 10 000 dollar reward to the research group.

Identified risks

Contactless keys have been targeted by car thieves for years. Through a so-called relay attack, the signal of the car is pinged and boosted. Whereas normally the distance between vehicle and handheld transmitter should be maximum one metre to open it, this can now be done at a distance of several hundred metres by copying and "extending" the signal.

That security was fairly easy to crack because Tesla used an encryption method that has been obsolete since 2005: the DST 40 system. Tesla received this system from a supplier.

References

- <https://businessmodelanalyst.com/tesla-business-model/>
- <https://www.esat.kuleuven.be/cosic/passive-keyless-entry/>
- <https://www.esat.kuleuven.be/cosic/news/fast-furious-and-insecure-passive-keyless-entry-and-start-in-modern-supercars/>
- https://www.standaard.be/cnt/dmf20180910_03729486?utm_source=standaard&utm_medium=social&utm_campaign=send-to-a-friend

#20 Jeep Cherokee - Remote car-jacking

Remote car-jacking incident involving a Jeep Cherokee

User context

The Jeep Cherokee, manufactured by Fiat Chrysler Automobiles (FCA), is a popular choice among modern consumers looking for advanced safety features and modern technology integration, including internet connectivity and remote access systems for today's tech-savvy drivers who want convenience and connectivity from their vehicles.

Business model

Fiat Chrysler Automobiles (FCA) is a global automotive brand operating in over 40 countries, with an expansive sales and distribution network that extends across more than 135 countries. Established in 2014 through the merger of Fiat and Chrysler, FCA's main strengths are its diverse product portfolio and strong global presence. In January 2021, FCA merged with Groupe PSA to form Stellantis, one of the largest automotive companies globally.

Incident date

The remote car-jacking incident involving a Jeep Cherokee occurred in 2015.

Incident description

Two hackers exploited vulnerabilities in the Jeep Cherokee's software systems to gain unauthorized access and control over critical functions remotely. This breach in cybersecurity posed significant safety risks to drivers and passengers, allowing hackers to manipulate various vehicle systems, including steering, brakes, and acceleration. Similar incidents involving cybersecurity vulnerabilities have also been reported with other vehicles, such as the Nissan LEAF, the Tesla Model S and the Fabia III by Škoda Auto.

Identified risks

The remote car-jacking incident exposed several risks associated with the increasing integration of internet-connected features in modern vehicles. These risks include compromised vehicle safety, potential accidents due to remote manipulation of critical systems, and threats to personal security and privacy for vehicle occupants (Lee & Madnick, 2021).

References

- Lee, C. W., & Madnick, S. (2021). Cybersafety approach to cybersecurity analysis and mitigation for mobility-as-a-service and internet of vehicles. *Electronics (Switzerland)*, 10(10), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10101220>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MK0SrxBC1xs>
- <https://www.trendmicro.com/vinfo/pl/security/news/internet-of-things/car-hacking-issues-spark-change-in-the-automotive-industry>
- <https://thehackernews.com/2015/07/car-hacking-jeep.html>
- <https://thepaymentsassociation.org/article/navigating-the-cyber-highway-the-growing-threat-of-automotive-hacking/>
- <https://cheshnotes.com/fiat-chrysler-automobiles-marketing-mix/>

#21 ToBike - Vandalism

ToBike bike-sharing service shutdown in Turin due to vandalism

User context

Residents and visitors in Turin who utilized ToBike's bike-sharing service.

Business model

ToBike operated as a bike-sharing service in Turin, providing users with access to bicycles for short-term rental at various stations across the city.

Incident date

The cessation of ToBike's operations was announced for February 2023.

Incident description

ToBike, a bike-sharing service managed by Bicincittà Italia Srl (literal translation: "Bikes in city"), decided to cease its operations in Turin due to persistent and uncontrollable vandalism targeting its bicycles and stations.

Over the years, the service faced significant challenges, including thefts, damages to bicycles and stations, and a decrease in the number of available stations.

In 2022 alone, approximately 900 bikes were vandalized or stolen, leading to substantial financial losses and operational disruptions.

ToBike publicly criticized the lack of support from local authorities in addressing the ongoing vandalism issues, emphasizing that private entities should not bear sole responsibility for combating such antisocial behavior.

Despite efforts to repair damaged stations and mitigate risks, the vandalism persisted, forcing ToBike to terminate its services.

Identified risks

- Persistent vandalism targeting bicycles and stations.
- Financial losses due to thefts and damages.
- Operational disruptions impacting service availability and reliability

References

- https://torino.corriere.it/notizie/cronaca/23_febbraio_11/bici-in-sharing-tobike-cessa-l-attivita-troppi-vandali-il-comune-non-ci-ha-protetti-263549a6-7a24-48fa-ae7-d8efe1602xk.shtml?refresh_ce
- <https://www.bikeitalia.it/2023/02/14/il-bike-sharing-a-torino-chiuso-per-vandalismo/>

#22 Share - Thefts & vandalism

Share Now car-sharing service shutdown in Turin due to car thefts and vandalism

User context

Residents and visitors in Turin who relied on Share Now's car sharing service for transportation needs.

Business model

Share Now operated as a car sharing service in Turin, providing users with access to vehicles for short-term rental at various locations across the city.

Incident date

The suspension of Share Now's operations happened in August 2023.

Incident description

ShareNow suspended its car sharing service in Turin due to a significant surge in car thefts, resulting in the disappearance of 30 vehicles from its fleet.

The company attributed the decision to concerns over safety and security, following a series of incidents where their cars were stolen or vandalized.

Despite efforts to address the issue, including the installation of black boxes to monitor and prevent such behaviors, the problems persisted.

Identified risks

The surge in car thefts and vandalism posed multifaceted risks to ShareNow's operations and its user base:

- **Security concerns:** the brazen thefts and acts of vandalism compromised the safety and security of users relying on ShareNow's vehicles for transportation, raising fears of potential confrontations or accidents involving stolen cars.
- **Financial losses:** the loss of 30 vehicles represented a significant financial blow to Share Now, not only in terms of the value of the stolen cars but also the revenue potential lost from disrupted operations and diminished consumer trust.
- **Operational disruptions:** the suspension of car sharing services in Turin disrupted the daily routines and travel plans of ShareNow's customers, highlighting the vulnerability of mobility services to external threats and criminal activities.

References

- <https://www.alvolante.it/news/share-now-torino-rubate-30-auto-387993>
- https://www.lastampa.it/torino/2023/10/16/news/predoni_car_sharing_ladri_auto_torino-13786891/

- <https://www.torinoggi.it/2023/10/10/mobile/leggi-notizia/argomenti/cronaca-11/articolo/oltre-200-tentativi-di-rubare-lauto-in-car-sharing-ecco-perche-share-now-ha-sospeso-le-sharing.html>

#23 Turin Micromobility – Vandalism

User context

Residents and visitors in Turin relying on micromobility services faced challenges due to recurring incidents of vandalism targeting electric scooters used for sharing purposes.

Business model

The micromobility companies in Turin provided electric scooters for short-term rental, offering users convenient and eco-friendly transportation options. However, the effectiveness of this model was compromised by incidents of vandalism and damage to the shared scooters and bicycles.

Incident date

The incidents of vandalism occurred shortly after the introduction of electric scooters for sharing, with reports dating back to December 2019, and continuing into January 2020.

Incident description

Instances of vandalism targeting electric scooters were reported in various areas of Turin, including Porta Nuova and Piazza Castello, in the city centre.

Vandals damaged and abandoned the scooters, requiring immediate repairs and relocation by the micromobility companies.

The situation mirrored previous incidents involving free-floating bicycles in the city, highlighting the persistent challenge of combating incivility and disrespect towards public property.

Identified risks

The surge in vandalism against electric scooters posed several risks to both users and service providers:

- **Safety concerns:** damaged scooters posed safety hazards to users and pedestrians, potentially leading to accidents or injuries.
- **Financial losses:** the costs associated with repairing or replacing vandalized scooters incurred financial losses for micromobility companies, impacting their operational sustainability.
- **Operational disruptions:** the need for frequent repairs and maintenance disrupted the availability and reliability of micromobility services, inconveniencing users and undermining confidence in the service.

References

- <https://www.torinotoday.it/attualita/monopattini-vandalizzati.html>
- <https://www.lastampa.it/torino/2020/01/10/news/i-monopattini-nel-mirino-dei-vandali-cento-casi-nei-primi-venti-giorni-1.38311088/>
- <https://www.lastampa.it/torino/2019/12/15/news/monopattini-vandalizzati-e-rubati-la-micro-mobilita-in-sharing-si-trasforma-in-un-incubo-1.38214130/>

#24 Car2Go - Vehicle theft

More than 100 of the company's 400 cars in Chicago were stolen via its own app.

User context

Car2Go provides an urban car-sharing service through a user-friendly app. Customers through the app can locate, reserve, and unlock vehicles. Utilizing the app, users access real-time information about nearby fleet availability and can reserve specific vehicles. The keyless entry system facilitates a smooth unlocking process upon arrival, eliminating the need for physical keys. Once the users are inside the vehicle, they can retrieve the physical keys from the glove compartment, for using the car and starting their ride

Business model

Launched in Chicago in June 2018, Car2Go introduced a short-term car rental concept, allowing customers to rent cars by the minute. The service provides a varied fleet, including both upscale Mercedes-Benz CLA and GLA models and compact Smart cars, catering to diverse urban mobility needs. Car2Go's business model focuses on delivering a flexible and efficient solution for urban transportation, meeting the rising demand for convenient, on-demand mobility in urban settings

Incident date

Car2Go launched in Chicago in the summer of 2018, with 400 Daimler cars rolled out on the city streets. In April 2019, Car2Go faced a major setback in Chicago when more than 100 of its 400 vehicles were stolen using the company's own mobile app. This unexpected incident prompted Car2Go to temporarily suspend its services in Chicago. Most cars have since been recovered, but a representative for Car2Go said Chicago vehicles have been put out of service until further notice.

Incident description

Car2Go experienced a significant disruption in Chicago when over 100 high-end vehicles, including Mercedes-Benz and Smart models, were stolen through the platform. This led to a temporary suspension of its services. On that day, there was a noticeable increase in rentals for Car2Go's higher-end cars, and these rentals lasted much longer than the company's average 90-minute ride. In addition, employees at Car2Go headquarters in Austin observed dozens of their cars to be frozen on a digital map as well as within Chicago, there is a 29 square mile area where the vehicles were supposed to be dropped off, but they haven't been limited from exiting that zone at any point.

FIGURE 76: Disruption Car2Go

Initially, investigators believed that thieves had hacked into the mobile app without being detected. Police stated that the company's software was somehow involved in the scheme, leading some to speculate that it was hacked or manipulated. Despite earlier reports of the app being hacked, Car2Go explained in a statement that the app is secure, treating the issue as a fraud case. Car2Go clarified that the cars were stolen through fraud, involving forged or stolen driver's licenses and counterfeit credit cards. No personal or confidential user information is said to have been compromised.

It is still unclear what the hacking exactly enabled the perpetrators to do. However, the compromised app appears to have opened the doors and given the thieves free rein with easily stolen cars. Chicago police spokesman mentioned, "The Chicago police department was alerted by a car rental company that some of their vehicles may have been rented by deceptive or fraudulent means through a mobile app." Finally, despite the company's assurance of app security, the incident raised concerns about the vulnerability of the platform. While the Chicago police successfully recovered most of the stolen vehicles and charged suspects, a police statement noted, "Due to the information provided by the company, numerous vehicles have been recovered. The investigation is ongoing." Police have charged 21 suspects in connection with the stolen vehicles.

Identified risks

In online marketplaces and app-enabled gig-economy, the concept of online identity has always been vague and a cause for concern. In more detail the relevant risks identified in this case include:

- Risk for identity theft and bypassing background checks
- Susceptibility to deceptive or fraudulent means of renting vehicles
- App hacking or inadequate security measures to prevent high-end vehicle theft
- Concerns about the overall security and integrity of user information

References

- <https://www.texasmonthly.com/news-politics/car-thefts-austin-based-car2go-in-chicago-show-the-vulnerability-app-based-lifestyles/>
- <https://www.caranddriver.com/news/a27192115/thieves-car2go-steal-100-cars/>
- <https://www.cbsnews.com/chicago/news/car2go-temporarily-suspends-service-in-chicago/>
- https://www.autoblog.com/2019/04/17/car2go-app-hacked-chicago-100-cars-stolen/?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xlLnNvbS8&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAALXhYvlz4tMKTPrDM69Jj-88MDm8P7m7_VloptLaco-JUnDuW3mmGP9NPYocTRsyqkWm90GNPf_u43jGAf3pqj9AbMan4-u6eQkEp2LzD7oqP_NWp5NEhVRs4nkvdkjyKNqGxGpx4wtF0ih0S8i877cceop0z0bpEAuM0kYI5WBX
- <https://www.theverge.com/2019/4/17/18412750/daimler-car2go-share-now-app-chicago-car-fraud-theft-arrests-stolen-benz>
- <https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2019/apr/19/car2go-app-out-of-service-chicago-stolen-vehicles>
- <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2019-07-11/mercedes-thieves-showed-just-how-vulnerable-car-sharing-can-be>
- <https://www.nbcbayarea.com/news/local/bay-legal-uberlyft-scam-law-enforcement-struggles-to-catch-fraudulent-rideshare-drivers/6836/>
- <https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2019/apr/19/car2go-app-out-of-service-chicago-stolen-vehicles>

#25 Autolib /Reachnow – Customer misbehaviour

Autolib's operational challenges and compromised service quality due to customer misuse of the service

User context

Autolib was an electric car-sharing service launched in Paris in December 2011 and operated until 2018. To access the service, users needed to meet specified licencing requirements and have a membership card. The user base of Autolib primarily consisted of individuals seeking convenient and environmentally friendly transportation solutions within the city and its surrounding areas.

Business model

The business model of Autolib was centred around offering an environmentally conscious and convenient car-sharing service within urban and surrounding areas. The service aimed to provide an easy car-sharing experience, offering users flexibility and accessibility in their transportation choices, all while supporting the public administration's goal of mitigating local greenhouse gas emissions through the car-sharing program established in collaboration with the Bolloré Group (Gonzalez and Quadros, 2022).

Autolib's business model relied on a network of self-service vehicle stations strategically located throughout Paris and its outskirts, allowing customers to pick up and drop off vehicles at their convenience. The service was designed to promote sustainable transportation practices and provide an alternative to private car ownership, aligning with the city's efforts to foster eco-friendly mobility solutions. However, operational challenges led to the discontinuation of Autolib's services.

Incident date

There is no specific date associated with this incident, as it refers to a series of events occurring during Autolib's operational period.

Incident description

The customer misbehaviour incident refers to events where customers did not use the Autolib service appropriately. This included various types of misconduct, such as failure to return vehicles to the designated location, engaging in reckless driving behaviours, and causing vehicle damage or vandalism. These incidents presented operational challenges and potentially compromised the quality of service provided by Autolib (Pieper & Woisetschläger, 2024; Gortz-Bonaldo et al., 2021).

Identified risks

The incidents of customer misbehaviour presented risks to the safety and integrity of Autolib's vehicle fleet, potential financial losses due to damage or misuse, and reputational damage to the company. Identified risks in this context include safety concerns arising from careless vehicle handling, potential negative impacts on customer experience, and profitability due to limited social accountability and customer misbehaviour.

References

- Gonzalez, P.P., Quadros, Q. (2022): Digital Transformation and New Business Models in Urban Mobility: The Case of Carsharing in Brazil, 2022 Portland International Conference on Management of Engineering and Technology (PICMET), Portland, OR, USA, pp. 1-12, doi: 10.23919/PICMET53225.2022.9882629.
- Gortz-Bonaldo, M., Do Nascimento, D.E., Hue (2021): The relevance of solution demand networks in the context of functional economy and product-service systems: Autolib case. *Liberdade, Democracia e Cidadania - desafios atuais em tempo de crise do capital*, v. 8 n. 57.
- Pieper, N., & Woisetschläger, D. M. (2024). Customer misbehavior in access-based mobility services: An examination of prevention strategies. *Journal of Business Research*, 171(November 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.114356>
- <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-france-autos-autolib-idUSKBN1JH2CM/>
- <https://www.fleeteurope.com/en/smart-mobility/france/analysis/shake-paris-car-sharing-wheels-have-come-autolib?a=BUY03&t%5B0%5D=Renault&t%5B1%5D=PSA&t%5B2%5D=Free2Move&t%5B3%5D=BMW&t%5B4%5D=Daimler&curl=1>
- <https://www.france24.com/en/20180731-france-liberty-paris-bikes-cars-share-autolib-velib-rent>

#26 Lyft - E-bike malfunction

User context

Lyft's mechanic and electric bikes are ideal for short trips, errands, and commuting to and from public transit. All electric bikes feature a pedal-assist feature, providing more help as you pedal harder. This feature caters to people of all fitness levels, and the bikes are equipped with built-in GPS, connected to Lyft's app for tracking distance and battery life. The pedal-assist is powered by a 500W motor and an enormous battery claimed to have a 60-mile range. This suggests the ability to go through multiple rides without requiring a complete charge due to its

substantial capacity. A network of sensors monitors the bike, issuing warnings in case of battery problems or breakdowns.

The process is straightforward: unlock the bike by scanning its QR code with the Lyft app or Clipper card, hop on and start cruising, and finally, when reaching the destination, find an open space at any Bay Wheels docking station. The lock-in light turning green indicates a successful parking. Electric bikes can also be parked at public racks for a nominal additional fee. Users can also reserve an electric bike up to 10 minutes ahead of time to ensure availability.

Business model

Lyft app users can choose from various ride options, including immediate and individual rides or shared ones. Lyft collaborates with independent contractors who carry out rides on the platform's behalf. In addition to car rides, users can book buses, trains, e-bikes, and scooters. They also have the option to rent vehicles from companies like Hertz and SIXT. As the intermediary, Lyft manages payment processing, driver-rider matching, and ensures safety. In return for these services, Lyft earns various fees. Over time, Lyft has evolved from a ride-hailing matchmaker to a versatile transportation platform. "The success of our business model depends significantly on our ability to efficiently attract and retain drivers and riders in the local markets in which we operate and increase the amounts that riders spend on our platform over time."

Lyft, through its respective app, offers bike services in many U.S. cities, including Chicago, Columbus, Denver, Los Angeles, Minneapolis, New York City, etc. Lyft provides various bike options, such as the Classic Bike designed for ease of use in metropolitan areas and Electric Bikes suitable for short trips and commutes. Availability, however, varies between cities.

TABLE 59: Bikes renting pricing scheme

	Single ride	Day pass	Month pass	Bay Wheels	Lyft Pink
Classic bike prices	30 min for \$3.49, then \$0.30/min	30 min free, then \$0.30/min	45 min free, then \$0.20/min	45 min free, then \$0.20/min	45 min free, then \$0.20/min
E-bike prices	\$3.49 unlock + \$0.30/min	Free unlocks + \$0.30/min	Free unlocks + \$0.15/min	Free unlocks + \$0.15/min	Free unlocks + \$0.15/min (+bike-sharing benefits)

Incident date

In 2008, Lyft recalled 2,500 e-bikes from its bike-share programs in New York City, Washington, due to users reports of oversensitive front brakes that caused them to flip over the handlebar. Furthermore, in 2019, after two battery fires occurred for unknown reasons within Lyft's e-bike fleet, the company decided to remove its rentable electric bikes from San Francisco. Consequently, Lyft made its thousand e-bikes in San Francisco "unavailable to riders". As a result, riders are currently unable to rent these e-bikes via the cellphone app until Lyft deems them safe for use.

Incident description

In April 2019, Lyft had to remove 3,000 pedal-assist bikes due to complaints about a problem with the front-wheel brake. Several incidents involving e-bike malfunctions have garnered attention, particularly concerns about oversensitive front brakes that resulted in riders flipping over the handlebars. Additionally, Uber admitted to receiving similar complaints from users of their e-bike services, experiencing harder-than-expected stops, leading to incidents where individuals were thrown over the handlebars.

The bike manufacturer genZe produced one generation of Lyft's Ford Go Bike Plus e-bikes, as stated in a press release. It remains unclear whether they were responsible for Lyft's alleged fleet of e-bikes. In a statement provided to the San Francisco Examiner and other media outlets, a spokesperson from Shimano stated that the company had issued brake installation requirements that were not adhered to by the manufacturers of "some" of the bicycles in question. According to the spokesperson, "With regards to this specific case, based on the information we have, this is not a Shimano brake issue as the specification requires the use of a power modulator for this brake. It appears this specification was not followed by manufacturers of some of the bicycles in question." Both Uber and Lyft are under investigation for utilizing brakes from the Japanese bike company Shimano in a portion of their e-bike fleets. Responding to these allegations, Shimano, the brake system provider, defines a power modulator as a device that enhances braking control within a specific range, cautioning that exceeding the effective operating range could result in brake malfunction. Specifically, the brakes might operate more forcefully than intended, potentially causing wheel lock-up.

Uber responded to the brake-related problems by installing a "hardware modification" to its e-bikes, later identified as a power modulator by Shimano. Uber's JUMP e-bikes in San Francisco underwent replacement or received the power modulator, and the company is in the process of replacing its entire fleet with a new braking system across various U.S. cities. Lyft, on the other hand, did not directly address Shimano's assertions or the existence and quality of a power modulator when reached for comment. Instead, the company referred to its original statement on the e-bike recall, emphasizing that a third-party engineering firm is analyzing the braking issue's cause. The situation underscores the significance of addressing safety concerns associated with e-bike malfunctions to ensure the well-being of riders.

FIGURE 77: Lyft e-bikes that caught fire

Finally, in July 2019, Lyft experienced a concerning episode where its e-bikes caught fire within days of each other. Although no one was riding the bikes during these incidents, and no injuries were reported, Lyft took swift action by temporarily removing its e-bikes from the streets of San Francisco, San Jose, and Oakland. The company investigated the matter and identified a battery issue without providing specific details on the root cause. To address the problem, Lyft announced collaboration with a different battery supplier as a solution.

Identified risks

- Public safety
- Vulnerabilities in third-party components
- Misuse or manipulation of physical devices
- Responsibility of the operators
- Involvement of external service providers

References

- <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/2019/04/16/uber-fixed-electric-bikes-that-had-similar-problems-bikes-lyft-recalled/>
- <https://www.digitaltrends.com/cars/lyft-to-return-its-electric-bikes-to-san-francisco-after-battery-fires/>
- https://www.sfexaminer.com/archives/lyft-halts-e-bike-program-after-bicycle-batteries-catch-fire-in-sf/article_df4a546d-4d4d-5bf0-b948-4608f72fa476.html
- <https://www.lyft.com/bikes/bay-wheels/pricing>
- https://www.sfexaminer.com/news/the-city/ford-gobike-jump-brake-manufacturer-fires-back-this-is-not-a-shimano-brake-issue/article_9635477b-3c48-5118-8423-3564884f8200.html

#27 VanMoof - Bankruptcy

Products purchased by customers no longer work after a service provider goes bankrupt.

User context

Anyone who uses a bicycle as an alternative means of transportation has to be able to cope with inclines and headwinds and has to protect their bike from theft. VanMoof wants to address these issues of cycling in urban areas with smart e-bikes that are minimalistic in design and affordable, but also stylish and equipped with smart technology. To this end, technical limitations resulting from tried-and-tested concepts are to be thrown overboard and new bikes with completely new functions are to be developed, offering high quality at an affordable price. Together with a specific smartphone app, features are provided to:

- unlock the bike,
- store the personalized shifting behavior of the automatic gearshift,
- locate the position of the bike,
- diagnose the condition of the bike,
- update the e-bike's firmware and
- alert the owner in the event of theft.

Independently from the e-bike the app will also include a navigation function.

Business Model

VanMoof manufactures e-bikes and achieves a value-added share of up to 80% focusing on the target group of 25 to 45-year-olds. To make it easier for VanMoof bike owners to ride, maintain and secure their bikes, VanMoof also offers services, some of which are subject to a charge.

These include:

- All-inclusive maintenance
 - For €300 per year, the bike will be proactively checked and serviced. The insurance cover includes costs for spare parts and labor.
- Smart theft protection
 - For €350 per year, the location of your VanMoof bike is tracked and the bike will be returned in the event of theft, or replaced if it cannot be found.

The app is intended to create a VanMoof-enthusiastic community via various online offers and thus keep VanMoof's image high.

Incident date

VanMoof filed for insolvency in July 2023.

Incident description

VanMoof had sold 150,000 e-bikes by 2019 and had 190,000 customers worldwide in 2023. At the time of its insolvency, VanMoof had accumulated 144 million euros in debt.

Identified risks

Smart Functions on VanMoof bikes are only available with the associated app, and this app in turn only works when the necessary servers are accessible. If the servers were to be shut down due to the company's insolvency, essential functions of the VanMoof bikes would no longer be available. In the worst-case scenario, the bike can no longer be used.

VanMoof bicycles are not developed and built in accordance with the norms and standards customary in the bicycle industry. As a result, VanMoof bikes cannot be repaired using commercially available spare parts. While established specialist bike workshops were already unwilling to accept VanMoof bikes, original spare parts will no longer be available when VanMoof is dissolved.

References

- <https://www.vanmoof.com/de-AT> (2023.11.14)
- <https://www.vanmoof.com/news/de-DE/about/> (2023.11.14)
- <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5cbcd466e66669416519accd/t/5d07a1b50a6b3a00019178e4/1560781257403/Vanmoof+Strategy+Master.pdf> (2023.11.14)
- <https://www.bike-magazin.de/magazin/hintergruende/insolvenz-von-vanmoof-so-gehts-weiter/> (2023.11.15)
- <https://www.linkedin.com/in/thomasrkoehler/> (2023.11.15)
- <https://t3n.de/news/vanmoof-pleite-e-bike-besitzer-wissen-reparatur-faq-1565116/> (2023.11.15)
- <https://www.businessinsider.de/wirtschaft/mobility/vanmoof-baut-e-bikes-nach-der-philosophie-von-elon-musk-r3/> (2023.11.20)
- <https://tech.eu/2023/09/01/lavoie-acquires-vanmoof/> (2023.12.11)

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